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ConcePTION

WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology and data catalogue and quality support

D7.14 Report on data characterisation

Lead contributor	Vjola Hoxhaj (1-UMCU)
	Email v.hoxhaj@umcutrecht.nl
	Constanza Andaur Navarro (1 – UMCU)
	Judit Riera Arnau (1 – UMCU)
Other contributors	Miriam Sturkenboom (1 – UMCU)
	Rosa Gini (10 – ARS)
	Olga Paoletti (10 – ARS)
	Hedvig Nordeng (14 – UOSL)
	Vera Mitter (14 – UOSL)
	Luigi Magnaloc (14 – UOSL)
	Saeed Hayati (14 – UOSL)
	Christine Damase-Michel (21 – CHUT)
	Anna-Belle Beau (21 – CHUT)
	Anthony Caillet (21 – CHUT)
	Odette de Bruin (1-UMCU)
	Maria Giner-Soriano (1 – UMCU/IDIAP)
	Dan Ouchi (1 – UMCU/IDIAP)
	Maria Aragon (1 – UMCU/IDIAP)
	Cecile Droz-Perroteau (1 – UMCU/BPE)
	Regis Lassalle (1 – UMCU/BPE)
	Jérémy Jové (1 – UMCU/BPE)
	Caroline Dureau (1 – UMCU/BPE)
	Clara Caverro-Carbonell (33 – RDRU FISABIO)
	Laia Barrachina-Bonet (33 – RDRU FISABIO)
	Amanda Neville (22 – FERR)
	Marco Manfrini (22 – FERR)
	Aurora Puccini (22 – FERR)
	Luca Cammarota (22 – FERR)
	Maarit Leinonen (31 – THL)
	Visa Martikainen (31 – THL)
	Sue Jordan (23 – USWAN)

Daniel Thayer (23 – USWAN)
Alex Coldea (23 – USWAN)
Hywel Evans (23 – USWAN)
Karin Swart-Polinder (1 – UMCU/PHARMO)
Thom Lysen (1 – UMCU/PHARMO)
Jesse van den Berg (1 –UMCU/PHARMO)
Kirsten Lum (37 – JANSSEN)
Anja Geldhof (37 – JANSSEN)
Anna Pierini (32 - CNR-IFC)
Francesca Gorini (32 - CNR-IFC)

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Abstract

In this deliverable, we describe the characterisation of electronic health record data sources participating in the ConcePTION project, specifically in Work Package 1 (WP1) and Work Package 7 (WP7). We also describe the INSIGHT tool and other tools developed to facilitate interpretation and visualisation of the results from data characterization.

INSIGHT- A tool to assess data quality and fitness-for-purpose

The INSIGHT tool was developed as an open-source tool that allows identification of potential data quality issues on the ConcePTION common data model (CDM) standardized data instances through the systematic execution and summary of more than 588 configurable Data Quality Assessments (DQA). These DQAs (also known as indicators) are aggregated into three-levels and help assure the integrity of the extraction-transformation-loading (ETL) of the data source into the ConcePTION CDM (Level 1), internal consistency (Level 2), and provide a high-level characterization (Level 3). The output of Level 3 can be used to guide the fit-for-purpose assessment of electronic health record (EHR) data sources. For more details on the design and methodology, refer to the protocol (EUPAS50142) and peer-reviewed publication.¹

ConcePTION Data Characterization

Data quality is crucial for credible use of RWD, therefore is a critical step in assessing whether RWD are fit for research purposes. Data quality assessment involves a systematic evaluation of data quality dimensions, relevance, and fit-for-purpose assessment with the aim of ensuring robust and reliable research outcomes. In this deliverable, participating data sources were converted in the ConcePTION CDM and then characterized.

A total of 13 data sources from 11 Data Access Providers (DAPs) (UOSL, THL, PHARMO, CHUT, BPE, RDRU_FISABIO, SIDIAP, ARS, CNR, USWAN, FERR) and 7 European countries (NO, FI, NL, FR, ES, IT, WA) were included in this study, which had specific requests as to the type of data that needed to be extracted and converted into the ConcePTION CDM. USWAN populated the highest number of ConcePTION CDM tables (15) and EFEMERIS, which only includes pregnant women, 11 out of 16 tables in total. The MEDICAL_OBSERVATIONS table was present in only 5 data sources. CNR was unable to provide real data and performed all WP7 activities such as ETL and level 1 and 2 using dummy data, thus further results are not shown. All data sources demonstrated high structural coherence, ensuring consistent ConcePTION CDM table formatting, mandatory variable presence, and vocabulary usage across all datasets.

The number of individuals on the source population ranged from 8,225 in CHUT POMME 10 to 5.1 million in SIDIAP. Between 1 January 1995 and end of data availability, the number of individuals included in the study population ranged from 16,595 individuals in CHUT POMME 10 to 6,410,050 in BPE. The follow-up went from 35,838 to 66,287,101 person-years in CHUT POMME 15 and FERR, respectively.

As requested per protocol, women of childbearing age were available in most data sources, except for ARS. In some data sources such as EFEMERIS and THL, only pregnant women were included. End of pregnancy and interruption of pregnancy codes or meanings were available in all DAPs providing pregnancy data except for RDRU_FISABIO where interruptions of pregnancy were not identifiable by law. Pregnancy episodes were identified across most DAPs, except for CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15, where data comprises only children, and no relevant data was available for FERR and ARS Registration timing after birth varies across DAPs, with most data sources such as UOSL (28.8%), BPE (12.4%), PHARMO (26.2%), FERR (19%), and USWAN (54%), showing a peak in registrations at birth (week 0), reflecting alignment with early postnatal care.

Data sources such as ARS, UOSL and THL provided broad healthcare coverage and diagnostic information across multiple registries, spanning from the mid-1990 to 2021, while data sources like CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15, offered narrower time spans, primarily focusing on hospitalization records. Vocabularies used predominantly include ICD10 derivatives. Conditions such as anxiety/depression, epilepsy, gestational diabetes and migraine were consistently documented across most DAPs. Medicines and vaccine uptake or

dispensing data across DAPs, varied widely in provenance and time span, with ARS, UOSL, and USWAN offering extensive long-term coverage, while CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15 have more limited periods focused on community pharmacy dispensing. Therapeutic classes such as antiepileptics (N03A) and antidepressants (N06A) are widely represented.

Several limitations regarding data sources shown in this deliverable are likely due to issues during the standardization to the ConcePTION CDM, thus to data instance, rather than to issues on local sources. Furthermore, results in this study reflect data availability up to 2021 and DAPs may have improved their ETL to address some of the abovementioned limitations in new data instances. Further efforts will focus on addressing these limitations through improved methodologies, enhanced data quality checks, and stakeholder collaboration.

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Abbreviations

By order of appearance in this deliverable:

RWD	Real World Data
RWE	Real World Evidence
CDM	Common Data Model
CONCEPTION CDM	ConcePTION Common Data Model
EU PE&PV	European Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance research network
VAC4EU	Vaccine Monitoring Collaboration for Europe
WP	Work Package
D	Dataset
DAPs	Data Experts and Access Provider
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Science and Informatics
EMA	European Medicines Agency
DQA	Data Quality Assessment
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
DQF	Data Quality Framework
DRE	Digital Research Environment
UOSL	University of Oslo
EFEMERIS	Evaluation chez les Femmes Enceintes des MEDicaments et de leurs RISques
POMME	Prescription Médicaments Mères Enfants
CHUT	Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse
BPE	Bordeaux PharmacoEpi
SNDS	Système National des Données de Santé
RDRU_FISABIO	Rare Disease Research Unit of the Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencian Region
SIDIAP	Sistema d'Informació per al Desenvolupament de la Investigació en Atenció Primària (Information System for Research in Primary Care)
IDIAP	Institut Universitari d'Investigació en Atenció Primària Jordi Gol
PHARMO	Institute for Drug Outcome Research in The Netherlands
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
USWAN	University of Swansea
SAIL	Secure Anonymised Information Linkage Databank (for Wales)
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ARS	Agenzia Regionale di Sanità
FERR	Univerisity of Ferrara
IMER	Indagine sulle malformazioni congenite in Emilia-Romagna
D2	ConcePTION table dataset
T1	Transformation
SNOMED	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine
ICD	International Classification of Disease
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification System
GP	General Practitioner
CSV	Comma-Separated Values

1. Introduction

The IMI ConcePTION project was established in 2019 (www.imi-conception.eu), bringing together 88 stakeholders across Europe with the aim of creating a learning healthcare ecosystem that can use real-world data (RWD) to generate real-world evidence (RWE), which may be used for clinical and regulatory decision making.

To make the best use of RWD for the generation of evidence across many data sources in a scalable rapid and reproducible manner, many groups and consortia have turned to the use of common data models (CDMs). In the ConcePTION project, we have agreed upon a study-independent (generic) syntactically harmonized CDM, the ConcePTION CDM.² The ConcePTION CDM is utilized by various research networks such as IMI-ConcePTION, SIGMA, VAC4EU and the EU PE &PV network, which conduct regulatory required studies on RWD.

Given the general exclusion of pregnant people from non-obstetric clinical trials, RWD sources constitute a fundamental data source for IMI-ConcePTION to achieve its aim of providing information about the safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding. However, it is also relevant to evaluate whether RWD sources are of sufficient quality to answer questions regarding event phenotyping, drug utilization and drug safety.³ Currently, there are several theoretical frameworks regarding data quality for observational data, especially for electronically recorded data. The article by Khan et al. has served as a foundational reference in the field as it introduces three main data quality dimensions: conformance, completeness, and plausibility which have also been introduced by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in their Data Quality Framework (DQF).^{4,5} Besides turning to CDMs, RWE research networks have also adopted tools to assess data quality such as the Data Quality Dashboard by OHDSI.⁶⁻⁸ In IMI-ConcePTION, we developed INSIGHT, a tool to assess data standardized to the ConcePTION CDM.¹

In INSIGHT, we followed a three-level complexity approach which consecutively assesses conformance to CDM, temporal plausibility, and data characterization, following similar approach used by SENTINEL.⁹ INSIGHT consists of over 588 data quality assessments (DQAs), allowing researchers to assess defined indicators of quality which can then be re-mapped to the theoretical quality dimensions as proposed by EMA.⁵ Level 1 provides information about the conversion and completeness of all variables converted into the ConcePTION CDM, for example, format of date variables and missing variables. Level 2 delves into clinical or biological plausibility of events, including assessment of events happening after death or before birth, and Level 3 undertakes data characterization with a pre-defined start of follow-up and codes, providing information about diagnoses, medicines, vaccines, and pregnancies.¹

DAPs in IMI-ConcePTION were invited to participate in the Deliverable 7.14 Data Characterization. This deliverable provides the detailed assessment on the fit-for-use and fit-for-purpose of 13 electronically recorded healthcare data sources (UOSL, THL, PHARMO, EFEMERIS, POMME 10, POMME 15, BPE, RDRU_FISABIO, SIDIAP, ARS, CNR, SAIL, FERR) from seven European countries (NO, FI, NL, FR, ES, IT, WA).

1.1 Objectives

In this deliverable, we aim to describe the participating data sources that have contributed to Work Package 7 (WP7, Deliverable 7.14) and to some extent, also to WP 1 (WP1, Deliverable 1.7) deliverables.

Specific objectives are:

- 1) To assess the syntactic harmonization to the ConcePTION CDM of local data sources
- 2) To assess the format coherence, structural coherence, and uniqueness of records in each harmonized data source
- 3) To describe the completeness, frequencies, and distributions of ConcePTION CDM variables in the included data sources across ConcePTION CDM tables.
- 4) To assess rates of diagnoses and medication use and vaccine uptake
- 5) To discuss and assess the relevance and fit-for-purpose of each data source for certain use cases, as follows:
 - a. Assessing medication use and vaccine uptake in the general population by age, sex, and data provenance
 - b. Assessing medication use in women of childbearing age, in pregnancy, and during breastfeeding
 - c. Calculation of incidence rates of events in the general population
 - d. Calculation of prevalence rates of events during pregnancy and before/after: this requires that the onset and ending of a pregnancy is known, as well as the events that occur before/ during and after pregnancy.
 - e. Assessing severity of specific maternal conditions: this requires that healthcare use, or disease severity markers/measures are available.
 - f. Assessing prenatal and antenatal outcomes in relation to drug exposure for signal generation and signal evaluation: this requires that pregnancy duration is known, follow-up is available, and the relevant outcomes and exposures can be measured as well as confounding factors.
- 6) Perform external validation by benchmarking rates with published literature and between data sources, as well as perform verification within each data source to assess plausibility of data.

2. Methods

2.1 Data Sources

All relevant organizations (hereafter called DAPs) with access to population-based data sources, for this reports, that is — *data sources that capture person-time of follow-up of a defined dynamic or fixed population during which medicine use and/or events can be observed/linked*, which aimed to participate in one or more of the demonstration projects in WP1 of ConcePTION were invited to participate in the WP7 Deliverable 7.14 Data characterization. We provide a description of the participating data sources. In addition, we summarize the 13 participating data sources and 11 DAPs in [Table 1](#).

2.1.1 Norwegian National registries (UOSL [NO])

The core data that University of Oslo (UOSL) has access to, are the health care administrative data banks of the entire Norwegian population, which represents approximately 5.6 million inhabitants, with about 56,000 deliveries yearly. Norway has a universal public healthcare system, consisting of primary healthcare services and specialist healthcare services. Many population-based health registries were established in the 1960s, with use of unique personal identifiers facilitating linkage between registries. The mandatory national health registries were established to maintain national functions. They are used for health analysis, health statistics, improving the quality of healthcare, research, administration and emergency preparedness. Since January 2004, all pharmacies in Norway have been obliged to send data electronically to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health on all prescribed drugs (irrespective of reimbursement) dispensed to individuals in ambulatory care.

Linked data were used from the following national health registries:

- The Medical Birth Registry of Norway (MBRN)
- The National Patient Register (NPR)
- Norwegian Control and Payment of Health Reimbursement (KUHR)
- Norwegian Prescribed Drug Registry (NorPD)

The NPR and KUHR offer health data, including inpatient and outpatient diagnostic codes, including immunocompromised status. The MBRN includes all pregnancies from 12 gestational weeks onwards independent of their outcome. It provides detailed information on maternal health, gestational age, and several pregnancies and birth outcomes and the newborn. Prescription data, including comedication, can be linked from the Prescribed Drug Registry (NorPD). The department of Pharmacy at the University of Oslo is the DAP for Norwegian registry data. The registries are linked using a unique pseudonymized personal identifier, and all analyses will be conducted on secure servers within the University of Oslo's servers, "Tjeneste for Sensitive Data" (TSD) platform, a specialized service for managing sensitive data.

2.1.2 EFEMERIS (CHUT [FR])

EFEMERIS is a cohort of pregnant women covered by the French Health Insurance System in Haute-Garonne (South-west France), built to conduct drug utilisation and medication safety studies in pregnant women (www.efemeris.fr). EFEMERIS data collection started in July 2004. It is ongoing and updated once a year.

EFEMERIS comprises data on: all prescriptions redeemed in out-patient pharmacies, prior to and during pregnancy; administrative and medical data about the mother and the child through children's certificates filled in during the compulsory medical examinations at birth, 9 and 24 months; data about Terminations Of Pregnancy

for Foetal Anomaly (TOPFAs); and the nature and date of termination of pregnancy (elective termination, still-birth, and spontaneous abortion). This was approved by the French Data Protection Agency on 7 April 2005 (authorisation number 05-1140).

Everyone requesting data access and doing statistical analyses is signing a confidentiality agreement form. All requests need to include at least one EFEMERIS investigator. Access requests to EFEMERIS for research purposes must be approved by the Steering Committee and data providers. Currently data on 1191,095 mother-outcome pairs are recorded in EFEMERIS for the period between mid-2004 to end of 2022. Part of the EFEMERIS dataset (only data from 2004-2013) has been linked with the RHE31 dataset (Haute-Garonne Child Disability Registry), providing exhaustive data about validated medical diagnosis of severe NDD at the age of 5 and/or 8 years. The disabilities registered in the REH31 include autism spectrum disorders (ASD), pervasive developmental disorders (PDD), severe sensory impairments, motor disabilities and trisomy 21.

2.1.3 POMME 10 & POMME 15 (CHUT [FR])

The French POMME [PrescriptiOn Médicaments Mères Enfants (Prescription-Drugs-Mothers-Children)] cohorts hold anonymised data on children from conception and during their childhood. POMME cohorts are subsets of EFEMERIS data where the children are followed up over time, it includes children born between 1 July 2010 and 30 June 2011 (POMME-2010) and between 1 July 2015 and 20 June 2016 (POMME-2015). POMME-2010 includes more than 8000 children and POMME-2015 more than 10,000 children. The cohorts are updated annually. Currently, available data concern children until 10 years of age for the POMME-2010 cohort and until 5 years of age for the POMME-2015 cohort. In addition to data already collected in EFEMERIS, POMMEs records data on medicines and medical care prescribed and reimbursed to the children during childhood. (<http://www.efemeris.fr/communications.html>).

2.1.4 SNDS (BPE [FR])

The Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS) is the French nationwide healthcare database. It currently covers the overall French population (about 67 million persons) from birth (or immigration) to death (or emigration), even if a subject changes occupation or retires (42,43). Using a unique pseudonymised identifier, the SNDS merges all reimbursed outpatient claims from all French health care insurance schemes (DCIR database), hospital-discharge summaries from French public and private hospitals (PMSI database), and the national death registry. SNDS data are available since 2006 and contains information on:

- General characteristics: gender, year of birth, area of residence, deprivation index, etc.
- Death: month, year and cause.
- Long-term disease registration associated with an ICD-10 diagnostic code.
- Outpatient reimbursed healthcare expenditures with dates and codes (but not the medical indication nor result): visits, medical procedures, nursing acts, physiotherapy, lab tests, dispensed drugs, vaccines and medical devices, etc. For each expenditure, associated costs, prescriber and caregiver information (specialty, private/public practice) and the corresponding dates are provided.
- Inpatient details: primary, related and associated ICD-10 diagnostic codes resulting from hospital discharge summaries with the date and duration of the hospital stay, the performed medical procedures (but no results), lab tests (but no results) and the related costs. Drugs included in the diagnosis-related group cost are not captured. However, expensive drugs (i.e., the ones charged in addition to the group cost) are.
- Mother and child linkage: there is a link to identify and track the newborn in the national hospital discharge summary database (PMSI) during the birth stay for deliveries with a gestational age ≥ 22 weeks. This linkage is possible for live births, stillbirths, and therapeutic abortions after 22 weeks. Follow-up of infants after birth is possible through linkage of the infant to the social security numbers of the parents.

Bordeaux PharmacoEpi (BPE), a research platform of the University of Bordeaux specialized in real world studies, was the DAP for SNDS data. Outpatient data (DCIR) are uploaded to the SNDS throughout the year. It is known that a lag of around 6 months is required to obtain 90% of dispensings. Inpatient data (PMSI) are uploaded in one time, at the end of the following year. Hence, we consider that complete SNDS data of year Y are available in January of the year Y+2. SNDS access is regulated: each study involving a human being with or without data extraction from the SNDS requires approval from the Comité Ethique et Scientifique pour les Recherches, les Etudes et les Evaluations dans le domaine de la Santé (CESREES) to assess scientific quality of the study, and authorization from the Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés (CNIL), the French data protection authority, and thereafter, an agreement with the SNDS data holder (CNAM) is needed for data extraction.

2.1.5 PHARMO [NL]

The PHARMO Data Network is a population-based data source with combined anonymous electronic healthcare data from different primary and secondary healthcare settings in the Netherlands.¹⁰

The different data sources, including data from general practitioners, in- and out-patient pharmacies, clinical laboratories, hospitals, the cancer registry, pathology registry and perinatal registry, are linked on a patient level through validated algorithms. The data are collected, processed, linked and anonymised by STIZON, an ISO/IEC 27001 and NEN 7510 certified foundation, compliant to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). STIZON acts as a Trusted Third Party (TTP) between the data sources and users of the anonymized data, which can request proportional study-specific datasets, in accordance with the GDPR.

The longitudinal nature of the PHARMO Data Network system enables to follow-up more than 10 million persons of a well-defined population in the Netherlands for an average of twelve years. Currently, the PHARMO Data Network covers over 7 million active persons out of 17 million inhabitants of the Netherlands. Data collection period, catchment area and overlap between data sources differ. All electronic patient records in the PHARMO Data Network include information on age, sex, socioeconomic status and mortality. Other information available is dependent on the data source.

The GP data comprise electronic patient records registered by GPs. The records include information on diagnoses and symptoms, laboratory test results, referrals to specialists and healthcare product/drug prescriptions. The prescription records include information on type of product, prescription date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity and route of administration. Drug prescriptions are coded according to the WHO ATC Classification System. Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC), which can be mapped to ICD codes, but can also be entered as free text. GP data cover a catchment area representing 3.2 million residents (~20% of the Dutch population).

The out-patient pharmacy data comprise general practitioner or specialist-prescribed healthcare products dispensed by out-patient pharmacies including community pharmacies as well as hospital-based out-patient pharmacies. The dispensing records include information on the type of product, date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity, route of administration, prescriber specialty and costs. Drug dispensing is coded according to the WHO ATC Classification System. Out-patient pharmacy data cover a catchment area representing 4.2 million residents (~25% of the Dutch population).

The hospital data comprise datasets containing data on hospital admissions, ambulatory consultations and high-cost medicines. Hospital data are collected and maintained by the Dutch Hospital Data Foundation and comprise records from nearly all hospitals in the Netherlands. With permission from each hospital the data are linked for research purposes with the PHARMO Data Network via the TTP. The following hospital data was used.

Hospital admissions: This dataset comprises hospital admissions for more than 24 hours and admissions for less than 24 hours for which a bed is required (i.e. in-patient records). The records include information on hospital admission and discharge dates, discharge diagnoses and procedures. Diagnoses are coded according to the WHO International Classification of Diseases and procedures are coded according to the Dutch Hospital Data Foundation registration system for procedures which links to the Dutch Healthcare Authority (NZa) declaration codes and the Dutch Classification of Procedures. Currently, PHARMO has access to data from 1998 onwards and of over 80% of the hospitals.

Ambulatory consultations: This dataset comprises all ambulatory consultations (i.e. out-patient records). The records include information on each contact, including date, diagnoses and procedures. Diagnoses are coded according to the WHO International Classification of Diseases and procedures are coded according to the Dutch Hospital Data Foundation registration system for procedures which links to the Dutch Healthcare Authority (NZa) declaration codes and the Dutch Classification of Procedures. Currently, PHARMO has access to data from 2016 onwards and of over 80% of the hospitals.

The Netherlands Perinatal Registry is maintained by Perined and comprises data on pregnancies, births and neonatal outcomes of births in the Netherlands, voluntarily collected by perinatal caregivers, mainly for benchmarking. For research purposes the data are linked with the PHARMO Data Network via the TTP, resulting in the PHARMO Perinatal Research Network (PPRN). Records include information on mothers (e.g. maternal age, obstetric history, parity), pregnancy (e.g. mode of delivery) and children (e.g. birth weight, gestational age, Apgar score). Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the Perinatal Registry code lists. For the current study permission has been obtained from PHARMO as well as Perined to use these linked data.

2.1.6 FISABIO (RDRU FISABIO [ES])

The RDRU_FISABIO provides the pertinent information of the population of the Valencian Region (one of the Spanish regions) that amounts around 5 million inhabitants and an annual birth cohort of 48000 newborns, representing 10.7% of the Spanish population and around 1% of the European population. The core data that RDRU_FISABIO has access to are Prescription and dispensations dataset, using ATC codes; Hospital discharge records, including diagnosis and procedures encoded with ICD9-CM up to 2015 and ICD10-ES 2016 onwards (the Spanish version of ICD10 which is more specific). Also uses Population-based Registries providing the relations between the women and their pregnancy outcomes being Birth registry; Perinatal Mortality registry using ICD-10 codes and Congenital anomalies registry (including live births, stillbirths and terminations of pregnancy due to a congenital anomalies) using ICD10-BPA codes. Moreover, the Mortality registry using ICD-10 codes and the Cancer registry using ICO3 codes are used. All databases are public and accessible through a request to the regional health authorities.

2.1.7 SIDIAP (IDIAPJGoI [ES])

The Information System for Research in Primary Care (Sistema d'Informació per al Desenvolupament de la Investigació en Atenció Primària (SIDIAP; <https://www.sidiap.org/index.php/ca/>) in Catalonia, Spain, is a primary care database set up by the Institute of Research in Primary Care (Institut Universitari d'Investigació en Atenció Primària Jordi Gol [IDIAP Jordi Gol]) and Catalan Institute of Health (Institut Català de la Salut).¹¹ The database collects information from 328 primary health care centers and includes more than 5.8 million patients covered by the Catalan Institute of Health (approximately 75% of the Catalan population) and is highly representative of the Catalan population.

SIDIAP data comprise the clinical and referral events registered by primary care health professionals (i.e. GPs, pediatricians, and nurses) and administrative staff in electronic medical records, comprehensive demographic information, community pharmacy invoicing data, specialist referrals, and primary care laboratory test results. SIDIAP can also be linked to other data sources, such as the hospital discharge database, on a project-by-project basis. Health professionals gather this information using International Classification of Diseases, 10th

Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) codes, Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) codes, and structured forms designed for the collection of variables relevant to primary care clinical management, such as country of origin, sex, age, height, weight, body mass index, tobacco and alcohol use, blood pressure measurements, and blood urine test results. Concerning vaccines, information on all routine childhood and adult immunizations is included in addition to the antigen and the number of administered doses.

SIDIAP is listed under the HMA-EMA Catalogues of real-world data sources (<https://catalogues.ema.europa.eu/node/1019/administrative-details>). The protocol must be evaluated by the SIDIAP Scientific Committee and by the IDIAPJGol Ethics Committee, the approval can take 6-8 weeks. The timeframe for data availability after the approval by the two local Committees is 1-2 months. An algorithm to identify pregnancies has been previously used within SIDIAP.¹² The algorithm uses diagnosis codes recorded in primary healthcare records during pregnancy and information recorded in the sexual and reproductive healthcare registries, including LMP, gestational week, expected date of delivery, actual date of delivery or termination, and pregnancy outcomes. Approximately 50% to 60% of pregnant women in Catalonia are attended in the sexual and reproductive healthcare centers that contribute data to SIDIAP. Approximately 80% of infant records can be linked to maternal records and used for research.¹³

2.1.8 FERR (Emilia-Romagna [IT])

The FERR database is a comprehensive healthcare registry operating in the Emilia-Romagna region of Italy. Emilia-Romagna database records data related to healthcare services. The main type of data included in the database are: birth certificate, electronic discharge records, drug prescription for inpatient and outpatient use, admission to emergency care, records of exemptions from copayment, diagnostic tests and procedures, causes of death, mental health services registry, The Emilia-Romagna database also include the regional IMER congenital anomalies registry, established in 1978, associated member of EUROCAT and International Clearinghouse for Birth Defects Surveillance and Research (<http://web.unife.it/progetti/imer/imernew/rengeng.htm>). This population-based program covers approximately 95% of all births in the Emilia-Romagna region.

2.1.9 CNR IFC (CNR [IT])

The National Research Council (CNR) Institute of Clinical Physiology (IFC) is Italy's largest public research institution dedicated to multidisciplinary studies with a primary focus on cardiovascular diseases and their interconnected systems, such as lungs, metabolism, neuroendocrine, and cancer (<https://www.cnr.it/en/institute/035/description>). Since its establishment in 1968, IFC has been at the forefront of combining experimental research, clinical studies, epidemiology, and advanced technologies to drive evidence-based medicine. IFC's mission is rooted in four key research areas: preclinical biology and disease mechanisms, clinical physiopathology and health risk factors, bio-techno-science and modelling, and epidemiology and health promotion. IFC is actively involved in 22 international (19 EU) and 37 national projects, reflecting its strong collaboration with global research institutions. It has an extensive database integrating clinical imaging, genetic, and bio humoral data for cardiovascular research and has coordinated numerous pharmacological and medical trials. In 2007, the institute's clinical operations were transferred to the Fondazione Toscana Gabriele Monasterio (FTGM), allowing IFC to concentrate exclusively on research while maintaining close ties to clinical practice. This collaboration has enabled IFC to explore innovative areas such as molecular imaging, systemic medicine, nanomaterials, and e-health technologies. IFC's ongoing initiatives emphasize personalized healthcare, leveraging cutting-edge diagnostics, patient-specific modelling, and simulation systems to optimize care and improve quality of life. With its multidisciplinary expertise, institutional collaborations, and patient-centred focus, the CNR Institute of Clinical Physiology continues to lead advancements in cardiovascular research and translational medicine.

For this report, CNR was unable to provide real data and performed all WP7 activities such as ETL and DQAs using dummy data. Due to limited sample size, results are not shown in this report.

2.1.10 Tuscany Health Registries (ARS [IT])

Tuscany is an Italian region, with around 3.6 million inhabitants. The Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana (ARS) is a research institute of the Tuscany Region. ARS' database comprises all the tables that are collected by the Tuscany Region to account for the healthcare delivered to its inhabitants. Moreover, ARS collects tables from regional initiatives. All the tables in the ARS' data source can be linked with each other at the individual level, through a pseudo-anonymous identifier. ARS' database routinely collects primary care and secondary care prescriptions of drugs for outpatient use and is able to link them at the individual level with hospital admissions, admissions to emergency care, records of exemptions from copayment, diagnostic tests and procedures, causes of death, mental health services registry, birth registry, spontaneous abortion registry, induced terminations registry. A pathology registry is available, mostly recorded in free text, but with morphology and topographic SNOMED codes. Mother-child linkage is possible through the birth registry.

2.1.11 Finnish Health Registries (THL[FI])

Universal health insurance is accessible for all citizens and permanent residents in Finland. Wellbeing services counties (n=22) are responsible for arranging health care funded by state. Health services are divided into primary health care and specialised medical care. The data that THL provides access to is most healthcare registries covering the whole population of Finland (around 5.6 million inhabitants). The core data of the Drugs and Pregnancy project (<https://thl.fi/en/research-and-development/research-and-projects/drugs-and-pregnancy>) includes data from Medical Birth Register, Register of Congenital Malformations and Register of Induced Abortions from 1996 onwards. Drugs and Pregnancy Database also includes following registries maintained by the Social Insurance Institution of Finland, Kela: Special reimbursement codes and diagnoses three months before pregnancy to three months following delivery or abortion and reimbursed drug refills three months before pregnancy to three months following delivery or abortion also 1994 onwards. Drugs and Pregnancy Database currently includes all pregnancies ending in delivery or induced abortion in 1996-2022 the total amount being around 1.7 million pregnancies.

Additional data sources maintained or accessed by THL and mapped to Conception CDM are Care Register for Health Care (HILMO), Register of Primary Health Care visits (Avohilmo), Cause of Death Registry for infant and maternal deaths. These data sources have been extensively used in registry-based research.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Data collection is mandatory by law and does not require informed consent from the recorded subjects. Data is stored on an individual level and can be linked by the personal identification number assigned to all citizens and permanent residents in Finland at birth or upon immigration. The results were reviewed against the subject knowledge from the source tables and good agreement obtained for included pregnancy periods with green and yellow quality.

2.1.12 SAIL (USWAN)

Wales is a constituent nation of the UK, home to ~3.1m people. Much of Wales is a former EU Convergence area. The Secure Anonymized Information Linkage (SAIL) Databank sources, accesses, links and analyses prospectively collected routine health, social care, education and population data, within a governed infrastructure that is safe and secure. All datasets are anonymized and encrypted by a third party and returned to SAIL for linkage. Data has been held on 5,400,000 people, since 1998 and can be made available within 3 months of events.

The NHS in Wales is funded by the Welsh Government from the block grant received from the Westminster government. NHS medical services, including all prescribed medicines, are free at the point of delivery. There is relatively little private medicine, and almost no non-surgical private pediatrics. Almost everyone living in

Wales is registered with a general practitioner (GP). GPs are responsible for all prescribing in the community, including regimens initiated in secondary care. Data on medicines administered only in hospitals is not generally available. SAIL can link datasets as needed, to allow exploration of any associations between prescribed medicines (ATC codes), diagnoses and maternal and infant outcomes, including preterm birth, SGA, congenital anomalies, infant feeding, hospitalizations, educational attainment, social care, and developmental delay.

SAIL holds linkable, anonymized national datasets, including:

- Accident and emergency care (from 2009),
- Critical care (from 2016),
- Congenital Anomaly Register and Information Service for Wales (CARIS), (with EUROCAT codes) from 1998
- In-patient and out-patient PEDW records (ICD10 codes),
- Maternity dataset (from 2015 for additional data on childbirth),
- National Community Child Health Database (NCCHD, includes gestation (ultrasound), birth centiles, childbirth, infant feeding, developmental screening and vaccinations),
- National Pupil Database Wales, (education attainment to 16, and special educational needs provision)
- ONS births and deaths (compulsory registration),
- Primary care data (including all prescriptions (from ~2000) and diagnoses as Read codes, mapped to ATC) from ~85% of Welsh GP practices. GPs are not remunerated for participation, and there are no thresholds. GPs' data form the basis of their reimbursement.
- Screening services (e.g. breast cancer screening),
- Substance misuse referrals
- Welsh Cancer Intelligence Surveillance Unit (WCISU, the cancer registry),
- Welsh Demographic Service,
- Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation (includes access to services and environmental exposure, other socio-economic status measures available),
- Welsh Results Reports service (radiology, pathology, including laboratory tests from 2007-17, in 5/ 7 UHBs).
- Children receiving Care and Support dataset / Children in Need census

Table 1 Participating data sources in the ConCePTION data characterization study

DAP	Data source and country	Data provenances available for CDM instance	Years with complete data
UOSL	Norwegian registries (NO)	Primary care records (KUHR), outpatient specialist diagnosis (KUHR/NPR), emergency room visits (KUHR), hospital discharge diagnosis (NPR), outpatient pharmacy dispensing (LMR), pregnancy registry (MBRN)	2008-2021
CHUT	EFEMERIS (FR)	Available instance restricted to pregnant women who terminated pregnancy or gave birth or and their children. Hospital discharge diagnosis, outpatient pharmacy dispensing, and child health records, no ICU, no primary care.	2005-2021
CHUT	POMME 10 (FR)	Available instance restricted to children born between 1 July 2010 to 30 June 2011.	2010-2011
CHUT	POMME 15 (FR)	Available instance restricted to children born between 1 July 2015 to 30 June 2016.	2015-2020
BPE	SNDS (FR)	Outpatient claims from French health care insurance schemes (DCIR database), hospital-discharge summaries from French public and private hospitals (PMSI database), and the national death registry. Primary care records, specialist referrals, ICU admission, hospital discharge diagnosis, pregnancy register, child health records, pharmacy dispensing.	2017-2020
PHARMO	PHARMO (NL)	Primary care (GP) records, hospital discharge diagnosis, ambulatory visit diagnosis, hospital inpatient and ambulatory procedures, out-patient pharmacy dispensing, ICU admissions, birth registry (perined).	2009-2019
RDRU_FISABIO	RDRU-FISABIO (ES, Valencian Region)	Hospital discharge diagnosis and procedures, ICU admission, outpatient pharmacy and healthcare centres prescribing and dispensing. Several population-based registries or information systems such as Birth Registry, Perinatal mortality Registry, congenital anomalies Registry, Mortality Registry and Cancer Registry etc.	2004-2021
IDIAPJGoI	SIDIAP (ES, Catalonia)	Primary care records, specialist referrals, ICU admission, hospital discharge diagnosis, pregnancy register, child health records, pharmacy dispensing.	2010-2021
FERR	FERR (IT, Emilia-Romagna region)	Primary care records, outpatient records, lab tests, emergency room visits, hospital admissions and procedures, ICU admission, outpatient pharmacy dispensing.	1995-2020
CNR	CNR (IT)	Disease-specific registry	2010-2021
ARS	ARS (IT)	Primary care diagnoses, prescriptions, lab tests, hospital admissions and procedures (HES APC, A&E, OP), pregnancy data, living situation, child health records.	1995-2020
THL	Finnish registries (FI)	Available instance restricted to pregnant women who gave birth or terminated pregnancy and their children. Primary care record, ICU, emergency room, hospital discharge diagnosis, pregnancy registry, congenital anomaly register, outpatient pharmacy dispensing.	1996-2018
USWAN	SAIL (WA)	Instance comprises available SAIL data, births and deaths register, hospital admission, primary care data.	1995-2021

2.2 Data Management

In this section, we provide a high-level description of the data management processes required for the study and of the datasets created at different stages from the extraction of raw data to the creation of a dataset for analysis. The ConcePTION pipeline follows a distributed (i.e., federated) network approach with a common protocol, a common data model and common analytics, that is —individual patient data remain local, while analytical scripts developed centrally are sent to be run by DAPs locally.

The ConcePTION pipeline is divided into four datasets (D) and three transformation steps (T). For this report, most analyses were conducted on the dataset converted to ConcePTION CDM (**D2**, Figure 1) prior to creation of study variables (**T2**, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Steps of the ConcePTION Pipeline from original data (D1) to analytical datasets (D4)

2.2.1 Original Data

2.2.2 Extraction and transformation of local data (T1)

Participating DAPs were asked to extract all available local data of relevance for the ConcePTION project, that is — WP1 and WP7 deliverables and convert these local data into the ConcePTION CDM v2.2 using their preferred programming/statistical software, a process also known as Extract-Transform-Load (ETL). An example can be found in [Figure 2](#).

DAPs documented their ETL design (i.e., origin table to target CDM table) in the ETL specification template (available [here](#)). For each data source, this documentation was reviewed by WP7 in collaboration with DAPs. The result of this process was a syntactically harmonized data instance including all data elements required for this study on which data characterization analytical scripts were run.

Figure 2 Example using the CPRD (Clinical Practice Research Datalink) data model of how a local data structure can be converted into the Conception CDM. Data characterization will take place with the second arrow on the data in the CDM.

2.2.3 Structure of the ConcePTION CDM

The ConcePTION CDM v.2.2 comprises 16 tables, hereafter referred to as CDM tables (Figure 3). Each CDM table is constituted by several standard variables. By convention, the ConcePTION CDM defines tables and variables mandatory and non-mandatory based on the minimal requirements to carry on studies, however some tables might become mandatory if the study requires it. Mandatory tables include: CDM_SOURCE, PERSONS, OBSERVATION_PERIODS, MEDICINES, VACCINES, EVENTS, PROCEDURES, MEDICAL_OBSERVATIONS, PERSON_RELATIONSHIPS and PRODUCTS. Each table has been described in detail elsewhere.²

Figure 3. ConcePTION CDM structure. Grey tables are known as *metadata* tables; Green tables are known as *routine healthcare data* tables; light blue tables are known as *curated* tables and blue tables are *surveillance* tables. Solid black lines refer to the linkage across records of the same person; dotted lines refer to linkage across items extracted from the same record; solid grey lines refer to linkage from items referring to a medicinal product to the product itself.

The figure above provides a high-level description of each CDM table. Detailed CDM specifications, such as the name of the variables per CDM table can be accessed online using this link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hc-TBOfEzRBthGP78ZWla13C0RdhU7bK/view?usp=sharing>.

With the purpose of data characterization, we requested the following list of events (Box 1), medicines (Box 2) and lifestyle characteristic (Box 3) to be extracted and loaded to the EVENTS and MEDICINES CDM tables, respectively (hereafter called data instance).

Box 1. List of events to be extracted

- Anxiety
- Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)**
- Autism spectrum disorder
- Breast Cancer**
- Depression**
- Epilepsy
- Foetal growth restriction
- Gestational Diabetes**
- Induced terminations of pregnancy
- Low birth weight
- Major congenital anomalies
- Maternal death

Microcephaly
Migraine
 Multiple gestation
Multiple sclerosis
 Neonatal death
 Pain
Pre-eclampsia
 Preterm birth
 Rheumatoid arthritis
 Spontaneous abortion
 Stillbirth
Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)
 Termination of Pregnancy for Fetal Anomaly (TOPFA)

Conditions in bold represent maternal conditions of interest for the demonstration projects in WP1 of the ConcePTION project (Task 1.3 and 1.5).

Box 2. List of pharmacological or therapeutical subgroups of medicines to be extracted

Agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09)
 Analgesics (N02)
 Antibacterials for systemic use (J01)
 Antidepressants (N06A)
 Antiemetics and antinauseants (A04A)
 Antiepileptics (N03A)
 Antihypertensives (C02)
 Antineoplastic agents (L01)
 Anti-Parkinson drugs (N04)
 Antipsychotics (N05A)
 Antivirals for systemic use (J05)
 Betablockers (C07)
 Calcium blockers (C08)
 Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)
 Diuretics (C03)
 Drugs for obstructive airway diseases (R03)
 Drugs used in Diabetes (A10)
 Endocrine therapy (L02)
 Immunostimulants (L03)
 Immunosuppressants (L04)
 Muscle relaxants (M03)
 Other nervous system drugs (N07)

Box 3. List of measurements or covariates to be extracted

Folic acid use
 Smoking status
 Alcohol use
 Educational level
 Last menstrual period
 Breastfeeding status
 Breastfeeding exclusivity
 Breastfeeding duration
 BMI and/or its components
 Socio-economic status and/or proxies of SES

2.2.4 Codelists for data characterization

To proceed with characterizing data sources, a standardized set of codes (i.e., codelists) was necessary to identify the specific events or medicine of interest ([Box 1-2](#)). This process requires selecting appropriate coding systems for each DAP (e.g., International Classification of Diseases (ICD), Read Codes) and ensuring comprehensive coverage of the target concept (or study variable), thereby creating a clear framework for extracting and interpreting further analyses. For this study, developing the study codelists involved multiple cycles of input and review from medical experts alongside DAPs, resulting in an iterative refinement. This activity was also shared with members from VAC4EU. Codelists for the characterization of diagnoses and pregnancies can be found in Annex I.

DAPs were asked to extract variables or codes for pre-defined conditions ([Box 1-3](#)) and include them in the EVENTS, MEDICAL_OBSERVATIONS and SURVEY_OBSERVATIONS tables, as applicable.

2.2.5 Previous DQ frameworks

Several theoretical DQFs exist.^{4-6,8,9,18-24} The latest available, the DQF from EMA proposes five data quality dimensions: coherence, extensiveness, timeliness, relevance, and reliability.⁵ The aim of EMA DQF is to provide a coherent guideline that can support a consistent DQA during regulatory processes.

2.2.6 Application of the INSIGHT tool

The INSIGHT tool was created as part of this deliverable and is a set of R scripts designed to assess the quality and fit-for-purpose of EHR data sources standardized to the ConcePTION CDM.¹ INSIGHT uses a three-level approach which helps identifying inconsistencies and errors (**Level 1 and 2**, [Figure 4](#)), as well as detailed characterization of the data source (**Level 1b and 3**, [Figure 4](#)). The INSIGHT tool consists of over 588 configurable DQAs.

Figure 4 Hierarchy and dimensions of data quality assessment in INSIGHT

Level 1 DQAs provide insight on the completeness and compliance of the ETL process towards the ConcePTION CDM specifications, ensuring format, structural and relational coherence. In addition, the plausibility of the data and the uniqueness of records is addressed, maintaining data integrity and identifying duplication errors. The following quality indicators are assessed:

1. Conformance with formatting requirements in each CDM table (by table).
2. Completeness of the variables in each CDM table (by table).
3. Frequency tables for all categorical variables in each CDM table (by table).
4. Distributions for continuous variable and dates in each CDM table (by table).
5. Proportion of incomplete dates in each CDM table (by table).
6. Uniqueness of records in each CDM table (by table).

Level 1b DQAs provide a list of all extracted and loaded non-date variables across the ConcePTION CDM tables. This creates contingency tables for categorical variables within each CDM table and shows the distribution of one variable across the categories of other variables. This level aims to enhance the understanding of the data content, facilitating semantic harmonization in the study's analytical scripts.

Level 2 DQAs provide an overview of the logical relationship and integrity of values within and between variables and tables. Its purpose is to verify the temporal plausibility by examining records that occur outside the recorded person-time, identifying observations related to a person ID that is not present in the PERSONS table, among other similar Inconsistencies. The following quality indicators are assessed:

1. Proportion of records with dates before birth date for each person in each CDM table (by table).
2. Proportion of records with dates after death date for each person in each CDM table (by table).
3. Proportion of records with dates outside of observation dates for each person in each CDM table (by table).
4. Proportion of records with person id not in PERSONS table.
5. Proportion of records linked to a visit id with date prior to visit start date.
6. Proportion of records linked to a visit id with date after to visit end date.
7. Proportion of records linked to a visit and with a person id different from the person ID in VISIT OCCURRENCE
8. Proportion of parents younger than 12 years old.

Level 3 DQAs provide distributions of population, diagnoses, medicines, vaccines, lifestyle factors, pregnancy, and temporal trends through calculation of incidence rates over sex, calendar time, and meaning for each specific concept. Results are presented in seven specific reports depending on table availability:

1. Study and source population
2. Dates
3. Medicine use
4. Vaccine uptake
5. Diagnoses of interest
6. Pregnancy
7. Visits and lifestyle factors

2.2.7 Deployment

The R Scripts (or INSIGHT tool) were distributed for local deployment to DAPs through a dedicated private GitHub repository. Issues with the R-Scripts were notified through GitHub, and WP7 resolved them. Given that there are potential risks of sharing sensitive information through the issues, we have mirrored the code in the following public repositories:

- <https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/INSIGHT-Level1>
- <https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/INSIGHT-Level1b>
- <https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/INSIGHT-Level2>
- <https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/INSIGHT-Level3>

For all indicators with a cell count less than 5, counts were replaced with “<5” programmatically. Further information on the INSIGHT tool can be found elsewhere.¹ If access to the private GitHub repository is desired, please submit a request via our institutional GitHub <https://github.com/UMC-Utrecht-RWE/>

2.2.8 Review, central sharing and storage

The outputs from the R script of INSIGHT comprised HTML reports and CSV files. HTML reports display information on parameters such as the date when the script was run, and the results from each of the checks with the corresponding interactive graphs and source CSV file displayed as interactive table. The HTML were used to review the quality of the characterization process. For visualization of the HTML report, please see the peer-review publication of INSIGHT.¹

In addition, we developed an approval form for each level in the INSIGHT tool (template is available [here](#)). This form contains the minimal requirements, as well as any particularity of the data instance before the data are ready for analysis (T2, [Figure 2](#)). Following completion of level 1, 2 and 3 checks to the satisfaction of DAP and WP7, the data instances were considered ‘passed’. For this deliverable, DAPs’ approval forms are available upon request to lead contributors.

Later, we asked each DAP to upload the outputs of INSIGHT to DRE for pooled analysis and visualization. DRE is a cloud based, globally available, research environment where data are stored and organized securely in a dedicated workspace for the study and where researchers can collaborate (<https://www.andrea-consortium.org/azure-dre/>). This platform was (and is for the next 5 years after the study ends) accessible remotely by DAPs, WP1 and WP7 members using authentication.

2.3 Study design

The study design is a descriptive analysis of the ConcePTION CDM data instance. We asked DAPs to extract data on subjects aged 12-55 at any time during the study period of 01 January 1995 – last data availability but were also allowed to extract smaller subpopulations (women of childbearing age, pregnant women, or children only).

2.4 Source and Study Population

For the data characterization, the source population comprises all persons registered in any of the data sources at any time during the study period. From the source population, we extract a ConcePTION relevant study population of all persons 0-55 years of age, that is — men and women of child-bearing age (12-55) and children (0-18).

The study population was followed from the moment of registration in the data source or start of the study period (01-01-1995) until death, loss to follow up, or reaching the age of end of follow-up (56y). As mentioned previously, DAPs may apply specific inclusion or exclusion criteria for the data instance. This is described in each DAP’s ETL specifications, available upon request to lead contributors, when possible.

No inclusion or exclusion criteria were applied at the analysis stage for the level 1 and 2 checks as these related to the completeness, conformance to the CDM (ETL conformance), and plausibility of the data.

2.5 Analysis

We inspected the descriptive analyses displayed in the HTML reports from INSIGHT in collaboration with DAPs. For this deliverable, we provided all measures calculated by year, age bands, and sex. For population distribution, we divided age into intervals (or bands) of four years, such as 0, 1–4, 5–9, 10–14, etc. following the definitions proposed by the World Health Organization.²⁵ The age band for rates calculation are divided into intervals of 10 such as 0-11, 12-19, 20-29, and so on.

Within data sources, we aimed to elucidate population shifts such as differences in prescription, diagnostic, and coding patterns over time. In addition, we also aimed to compare participating data sources by calculating measures by year and compared across DAPs. We plotted some measures to facilitate visual assessment.

For level 1 and 2, we presented results using passed (+) and failed (-) based on the assessment on the proportion of records (i.e., rows) that failed the pre-defined quality indicators:

- (+) <5% of records failed the quality indicator
- (+/-) between 5-10% of records failed the quality indicator
- (-) >10% records failed the quality criterion

Through level 3 indicators, we also provide information on conditions of interest, medicines and vaccines time span availability, and information regarding medicines, vaccines and diagnoses on women of childbearing age. Pregnancy episodes were identified through diagnostic codes or the provenance of the record in the SURVEY ID table (i.e., variable named 'meaning'). The pregnancy episodes were divided in 4 groups based on the type of outcome:

- *end of pregnancy*: all codes or meanings that refer to live birth or still birth
- *ongoing pregnancy*: all codes or meanings that refer to ongoing pregnancy for example 20 weeks ultrasound
- *interruption pregnancy*: all codes or meanings that refer to spontaneous abortions, elective terminations, termination due to foetal anomaly
- *start of pregnancy*: all codes or meaning that refer to start of pregnancy for example last menstrual date

3. Results

3.1 Availability of ConcePTION CDM tables per data instance

In [Table 2](#), we show the availability of CDM tables, and therefore data, in the D2 instance for the various DAPs. Out of the 16 tables defined in the ConcePTION CDM, availability ranged from 11 completed CDM tables in EFEMERIS to 15 in SAIL. All data sources included the EVENTS and MEDICINES tables necessary for extracting information on conditions and medicines of interest (Box1-2). Data on pregnancy episodes are accessible through the EVENTS, SURVEY ID and SURVEY OBSERVATIONS tables for this study, and all three tables were present in all data sources. Furthermore, the CDM SOURCE and METADATA tables, which provide vital details on data sources timeliness and structure, were also available across all data sources. Non-mandatory CDM tables such as INSTANCE (EFEMERIS) and VACCINES (EFEMERIS, POMME 10, POMME 15, THL, PHARMO, FERR) were unavailable at the time of this study. Mandatory CDM tables such as PROCEDURES and MEDICAL OBSERVATION were missing in the data instance that was used by EFEMERIS, SIDIAP, UOSL, EFEMERIS, POMME10, POMME 15, BPE, RDRU_FISABIO, and THL respectively.

3.2. INSIGHT level 1: Conformance and completeness

As mentioned previously, level 1 DQAs provide information on the quality dimension ‘conformance’, also sometimes referred as ‘coherence’ in published literature.⁵ **Conformance** refers to the degree to which data adheres to established standards, formats, and predefined rules or conventions within a CDM. For example, conformance involves:

- **Structural coherence:** Verifying that data structures align with the CDM's specifications, including the presence of mandatory and/or non-mandatory tables, fields, vocabularies, and concepts (study variables).
- **Format Coherence:** Ensuring data entries conform to specified formats, such as date formats, and allowable values for vocabulary variables.

In addition, level 1 DQAs also provided information on ‘completeness’. **Completeness** assessed the extent to which all required data is present. In INSIGHT, completeness is assessed through missing data analysis, which detects missing values with respect to CDM variables in the standardized data instance (at record level), typically labelled as NULL, NA, or blanks.

The extent of missingness across variables is presented below in [Table 6](#). Furthermore, we performed frequency analysis of categorical variables and distribution of continuous variables and dates. Detailed information about this analysis can be requested to lead contributors.

3.2.1 Conformance to ConcePTION CDM

In [Table 2](#) and [3](#), we outline the conformance of the available data instances against several quality and structural indicators (i.e., conventions) critical for harmonization under the ConcePTION CDM. We have measured the following conventions (i.e. Indicators):

- Presence of CDM tables
- Correct number of fields for the CSV files in the working directory
- Presence of variables irrespective of empty field
- Variable names written in lower case

- Presence of mandatory variables
- Presence of non-mandatory variables and cross check with the METADATA table
- Presence of vocabularies
- Variable format and cross check with fixed vocabularies and METADATA information

All data sources had the correct number of fields in their CSV files (i.e. CDM table), reflecting consistent file formatting. Variables were uniformly present across all data sources, ensuring adherence to the expected schema even in cases of missing values (i.e., a variable needs to be created even if it is completely missing, ensuring uniform CDM table structure across all data sources, that is with empty field, if necessary). All DAPs have consistently used lower-case for variable names following the ConcePTION CDM naming conventions. Mandatory and non-mandatory variables are present across all participating data sources and non-mandatory variables have been cross-checked with the METADATA table, ensuring completeness and correctness of the metadata provided.

All data sources successfully met the requirement for the presence of vocabularies, which includes detailed information on all available values for vocabulary variable documented in the METADATA table.

Furthermore, fixed (or pre-defined) vocabularies and open vocabulary values were cross verified against the actual values present in the tables with fixed values for fixed vocabulary variables or the metadata information provided for the open vocabulary variables. For the list of fixed vocabularies, please visit the following link <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hc-TBOfEzRBthGP78ZWla13C0RdhU7bK/view?usp=sharing>. All data sources passed the above-mentioned checks.

While most data instances conformed to format and allowable values for date elements (YYYYMMDD), we observed non-compliance in FERR and ARS (i.e., date values with different number of characters than 8 (format check) and different values than the allowable values for year: before 1995-future years compared to running date of the assessment, month: 01-12 or day: 01-31).

Table 2. Presence of the ConcePTION CDM tables in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

CDM tables	Data Access Providers (DAPs)											
	UOSL	EFEMERIS	POMME 10	POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FI SABIO*	SIDIAP	FERR*	ARS	THL	USWAN
METADATA	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
CDM SOURCE	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
INSTANCE	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
PRODUCTS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
EVENTS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
MEDICINES	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
VACCINES	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
PROCEDURES	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
MEDICAL OBSERVATIONS	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
VISIT OCURRENCE	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
SURVEY ID	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
SURVEY OBSERVATIONS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
EUROCAT	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+
PERSONS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
OBSERVATION PERIODS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
PERSON RELATIONSHIPS	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+

In bold, CDM tables which are mandatory per ConcePTION CDM conventions. *DAPs described as EUROCAT-DAPs only METADATA, CDM SOURCE, PERSONS, EUROCAT tables are mandatory.

Table 3. Level 1: Conformance with the ConcePTION CDM conventions across data instances

Indicator	Data Access Provider (DAP)											
	UOSL	CHUT EFEMERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FISABIO	SIDIAP	FERR	ARS	THL	USWAN
Correct number of fields for the CSV files in the working directory	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Presence of variables irrespective of their content	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Variable names written in lower case	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Presence of mandatory variables	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Presence of non-mandatory variables and cross check with the METADATA table	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Presence of vocabularies	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Variable format and cross check with fixed vocabularies and METADATA information	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Correct format of date variables	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Allowable values for date variables elements: day, month, year	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+

3.2.2 Missing analysis

In [Table 4](#), we present the assessment of missingness within data instances. Missing data were observed in both mandatory and non-mandatory tables, as well as in mandatory and non-mandatory variables. For instance, the VACCINES table, a mandatory component, was absent in 7 out of the 13 DAPs included in this report. Similarly, the MEDICAL OBSERVATIONS table was missing in 8 out of 13 DAPs. Other missing mandatory tables included PROCEDURES in EFEMERIS and SIDIAP, as well as PRODUCTS in SIDIAP, ARS, and US-WAN.

Mandatory variables demonstrated no missingness across all DAPs such as *person_id* and essential date variables such as *start_date_record* and *visit_start_date*. Variables necessary for filtering information were also largely complete, including *event_code* in EVENTS (0% missing), *medicinal_product_atc_code* in MEDICINES (with exceptions: 3.6% missing in BPE and 0.7% and 0.3% missing in CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15, respectively), and *procedure_code* in PROCEDURES (2.6% missing in FERR).

Missingness was also identified in non-mandatory and 'mandatory on condition' variables (i.e., variables that are necessary when another variable is completely missing, for example *event_code* and *event_free_text* are dependent on each-other). For instance, from non-mandatory variables, *day_of_death* and *month_of_death* were missing in over 98% of records in UOSL and 100% in CHUT POMME datasets. Missingness of the variable *presc_quantity_per_day* ranged from 100% in CHUT EFEMERIS and CHUT POMME datasets and 58.6% in PHARMO. Vaccine-related variables, such as *vx_type* and *vx_dose*, were entirely missing in UOSL and several other DAPs but were complete in BPE and SIDIAP. The variable *op_end_date* for OBSERVATION PERIODS was missing in 98.3% of records in UOSL but was complete in other DAPs. Furthermore, *visit_occurrence_id* was 100% missing in CHUT datasets, although complete in others.

Non-mandatory variables showed a consistent pattern of missingness across DAPs. For example, PRODUCTS had significant missingness, while 'mandatory on condition' variables like *event_free_text* were missing in more than 70% of records across all DAPs. Similarly, *date_prescription* was entirely missing in 7 out of 13 DAPs.

Table 4. Percentage of records missing per CDM variable in included data instances

CDM table	Data Access Providers (DAPs)											
	UOSL (%)	CHUT EFEM-ERIS (%)	CHUT POMME 10 (%)	CHUT POMME 15 (%)	BPE (%)	PHARMO (%)	RDRU_FI SABIO (%)	SIDIAP (%)	FERR (%)	ARS (%)	THL (%)	USWAN (%)
<i>INSTANCE (N)</i>	278	N/A	178	178	81	48	275	40	47	277	197	45
source_table_name	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
source_column_name	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
included_in_instance	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	14.3	0	0	0
<i>date_when_data_last_updated</i>	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	4.8	0	0	0
<i>since_when_data_complete</i>	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	8.8	0	0	0
<i>up_to_when_data_complete</i>	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>restriction_in_values</i>	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
list_of_values	100		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
restriction_condition	68		100	100	100	97.9	100	100	92.5	93.9	100	100
PRODUCTS (N)	17002	8290	5411	4362	105532	30751401	4881	N/A	48098	N/A	2205931	N/A
medicinal_product_id	0	0	0.1	0	0	0.01	0		0		0	
medicinal_product_name	0	0	0	0	13	0.0002	0		0		0.02	
unit_of_presentation_type	100	0	100	100	100	100	100		100		100	
unit_of_presentation_num	100	100	100	100	0	0	100		100		100	
administration_dose_form	100	0	43.3	27.3	12.8	100	100		100		100	
administration_route	100	100	100	100	40	100	100		100		100	
medicinal_product_atc_code	0	0	0.7	0.3	23	0	0		0		0	
subst1_atc_code	100	100	100	100	39.3	100	100		100		100	
subst2_atc_code	100	100	100	100	92.4	100	100		100		100	
subst3_atc_code	100	100	100	100	99.4	100	100		100		100	
subst1_amount_per_form	100	100	100	100	15.2	100	100		100		100	
subst2_amount_per_form	100	100	100	100	87.9	100	100		100		100	
subst3_amount_per_form	100	100	100	100	97.8	100	100		100		100	
subst1_amount_unit	100	100	100	100	15.3	100	100		100		100	
subst2_amount_unit	100	100	100	100	87.9	100	100		100		100	
subst3_amount_unit	100	100	100	100	97.8	100	100		100		100	

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subst1_concentration	100	100	100	100	99.4	100	100	100	100	100
subst2_concentration	100	100	100	100	99.8	100	100	100	100	100
subst3_concentration	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
subst1_concentration_unit	100	100	100	100	99.4	100	100	100	100	100
subst2_concentration_unit	100	100	100	100	99.8	100	100	100	100	100
subst3_concentration_unit	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
concentration_total_content	100	100	100	100	53.8	100	100	100	100	100
concentration_total_content_unit	100	100	100	100	53.7	100	100	100	100	100
medicinal_product_manufacturer	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

EVENTS (N)	230219296	243643	18607	26036	142078436	8075124	4385404	1322054 55	19511328	21640908	102558570	79972926
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
start_date_record	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.02	0	0
end_date_record	100	0	0	0	0	80.9	0	25.2	14.1	11.1	0	0
event_code	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
event_record_vocabulary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
text_linked_to_event_code	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	93.6	100	100	100
event_free_text	100	100	71.4	77.8	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
present_on_admission	100	100	100	100	100	0	100	100	38.8	7.2	100	100
laterality_of_event	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98.8	100	100	100
meaning_of_event	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
origin_of_event	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
visit_occurrence_id	0	0	0	0	39.6	86.9	0	100	6.4	0	0	78.4

MEDICINES (N)	290784713	2175605	1184119	616974	952644479	66253406	38845064	6129049 65	11534270 6	263508042	2128218	190393435
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
medicinal_product_id	0.2	0	0.001	0	3.5	100	0	0	0	0	0	100
medicinal_product_atc_code	0	0	0.1	0.02	3.6	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0	1.4
date_dispensing	0	0	0	0	0	53.6	0	0	0	0.0006	0	100
date_prescription	100	100	11.1	25.3	2.3	46.4	99.5	100	14.9	100	100	0
disp_number_medicinal_product	0.2	41.6	10.8	0	0	46.7	0.5	0	0	0	0	100
presc_quantity_per_day	9.7	100	100	100	100	58.6	0.5	100	100	100	100	100

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presc_quantity_unit	0.2	100	100	100	100	100	0	0	100	100	100	100
presc_duration_days	9.9	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
product_lot_number	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
indication_code	58.9	100	100	100	100	81.5	100	100	100	100	91.6	100
indication_code_vocabulary	48.9	100	100	100	100	46.4	100	100	100	100	100	100
meaning_of_drug_record	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.05	0	0
origin_of_drug_record	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
prescriber_speciality	59.9	0	0.004	0	3.4	0	0	100	100	100	58.9	0
prescriber_speciality_vocabulary	0.2	0	0	0	0	53.6	0	100	100	100	100	100
visit_occurrence_id	100	100	100	100	97.7	62.7	0	100	100	0	100	100

VACCINES (N)	45529071	N/A	N/A	N/A	14908490	N/A	N/A	30770288	N/A	8853239	N/A	874049
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person_id	0				0			0		0		0
<i>vx_record_date</i>	100				0			100		0		100
<i>vx_admin_date</i>	0				100			0		0		0
<i>vx_atc</i>	0				0			34.8		0		0
<i>vx_type</i>	100				100			0		100		100
<i>vx_text</i>	0				100			100		100		100
medicinal_product_id	100				0			0		0		100
<i>vx_dose</i>	100				100			0		0		100
<i>vx_manufacturer</i>	87.2				100			57.8		0		100
<i>vx_lot_num</i>	100				100			100		0		100
meaning_of_vx_record	0				0			0		0		0
origin_of_vx_record	0				0			0		0		0
visit_occurrence_id	100				100			100		100		100

PROCEDURES (N)	1819177	N/A	287048	116723	943808039	9737444	4153839	N/A	13314387	544731078	49753140	114388765
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person_id	0		0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
procedure_date	0		0	0	0	0	0		6.3	0.1	0	0
procedure_code	0		0	0	0	0	0		2.6	0.0004	0	0
procedure_code_vocabulary	0		0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
meaning_of_procedure	0		0	0	0	0	0		0	97.7	0	0

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origin_of_procedure	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0	0	
visit_occurrence_id	100	0	0	82.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	91.4	
MEDICAL OBSERVATIONS (N)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	10578	N/A	83950926	22563	9396530	N/A	214035835
person_id						0		0	0	0		0
mo_date						0		0	0	0		0
mo_code						0		100	100	59.7		0
mo_record_vocabulary						0		0	100	59.7		0
mo_source_table						0		100	100	0		0
mo_source_column						0		100	0	40.3		0
mo_source_value						0		0	0	40.3		23.1
mo_unit						100		71.7	0	93.7		100
mo_meaning						0		0	0	0		0
mo_origin						0		0	0	0		0
visit_occurrence_id						82.4		100	0	0		100
VISIT OCCURRENCE (N)	199109491	51025	7913	8546	876445501	552207	40935944	365040569	5178159	69251251	75745884	30864876
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
visit_occurrence_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00004	0	0
visit_start_date	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00004	0	0	0
visit_end_date	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00004	92.3	0	0.0003
specialty_of_visit	4.1	100	100	100	3.3	0.4	97.2	100	0	15.4	0	18.3
specialty_of_visit_vocabulary	0	100	100	100	2.1	0	0	100	0	15.4	52.9	18.3
status_at_discharge	100	100	100	100	98	100	97.2	100	90.8	92.3	70.9	0.2
status_at_discharge_vocabulary	100	100	100	100	97.9	100	0	100	98.8	92.3	0	0
meaning_of_visit	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
origin_of_visit	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SURVEY_ID (N)	3021581	438616	27482	29472	1332786	224744	1008772	238217	483547	1285779	3155381	3723161
person_id	1.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
survey_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
survey_date	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.002	0	0
survey_meaning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

survey_origin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SURVEY OBSERVATIONS (N)	50647214	10329880	699981	822481	3335023	5250800	8885195	714734	15402721	65759509	73169403	62087035
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.1
so_date	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	51.1	0	0
so_source_table	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
so_source_column	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
so_source_value	0	0	0	0	0.03	0.3	0.03	0	34.5	21.8	0.0002	23.2
so_unit	91.9	90.2	90.3	92.1	65.7	100	76.6	100	95.2	91.7	86.5	100
so_meaning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
so_origin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
survey_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PERSONS (N)	3515280	254664	16594	20757	8491153	706314	988055	7203481	4563259	3644644	2074656	1973454
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
day_of_birth	0.02	41.8	49.6	49.6	100	84.6	0.2	0	0	0	0	0.6
month_of_birth	0.02	41.8	49.6	49.6	100	84.6	0.2	0	0	0	0	0.6
year_of_birth	0.02	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0	0	0	0	0.002
day_of_death	98.3	99.9	99.9	100	96.8	100	99.5	93.9	98.4	0	99.6	99.1
month_of_death	98.3	99.9	99.9	100	96.8	100	99.5	93.9	98.4	98.3	99.6	99.1
year_of_death	98.3	99.9	99.9	100	96.8	99.6	99.5	93.9	98.4	98.3	99.6	99.1
sex_at_instance_creation	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0	0	0	98.3	0	0
race	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
country_of_birth	100	36.1	53.2	51.8	100	100	0	26.3	100	100	0	100
quality	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
OBSERVATION PERIODS (N)	3515280	244398	16596	20757	8491153	1898585	1959637	15822052	4625145	8262333	2074656	770391
person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
op_start_date	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
op_end_date	98.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
op_meaning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
op_origin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PERSON RELATIONSHIPS (N)	2015880	253225	8932	11107	558687	112372	982738	N/A	211140	543465	132128	1201974

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person_id	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1
related_id	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
meaning_of_relationship	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
origin_of_relationship	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
method of linkage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

N – total number of records per table. Percentage is calculated by dividing the number of empty/blank cells with the total number of records per table (N) multiplied by 100 and rounded to one decimal digit.

In bold, mandatory tables and variables

In italic, mandatory on condition variables per CDM conventions.

N/A - Not Available.

USWAN holds data on medicines prescribed in primary care for ~85% of the population, including ATC code, tablet strength, formulation, route of administration and brand name.

3.3 INSIGHT Level 2: Temporal Characterization

Level 2 DQAs evaluate the quality dimension often referred to as temporal plausibility. **Temporal Plausibility** refers to the consistency and logical sequence of time-related data within a dataset. It ensures that recorded observations (e.g., events and medicines) occur in a biologically or clinically meaningful or plausible order. For example, birth dates must precede medical encounters or prescriptions. For details on checks for level 2, please see section 2.2.6.

In [Table 5](#), we show an overall evaluation of temporal plausibility across the participating DAPs. We observed most DAPs complied with Level 2 quality indicators, although some discrepancies were noted in specific data sources. All DAPs, except PHARMO (49.3% in the SURVEY ID table), ensured that events did not occur before the recorded birth date of subjects. Similarly, all participating DAPs passed the check for events not occurring after a subject's recorded death date. However, compliance with the quality indicator ensuring that events occur within observation periods of the D2 instance varied across data sources. By observation periods we mean the period between start and end of observation for each subject as defined in the OBSERVATION PERIODS table by the variables *op_start_date* and *op_end_date*, respectively. UOSL, EFEMERIS, POMME 10, POMME 15, SIDIAP, and THL adhered to this requirement, while BPE, PHARMO, RDRU_FISABIO, ARS, and USWAN did not. FERR demonstrated partial compliance as defined by the threshold 5-10%, for two indicators: dates of events outside observation periods and subjects observed in a CDM table of interest without a corresponding record in the PERSONS table.

Most DAPs satisfied the requirement of having the entries in the PERSONS table for observed subjects, though FERR exhibited partial compliance (7.3% of records coming from the provenance birth_registry_child for both SURVEY ID and SURVEY OBSERVATIONS tables failed this check). Observations occurring before the *visit_start_date* or after the *visit_end_date* associated with *visit_occurrence_id* were highly compliant across datasets, though FERR and ARS did not meet this criterion (>10% issues), 13.2% in MEDICAL OBSERVATIONS and 48% in PROCEDURES, respectively. Alignment between the *person_id* in all CDM tables (when available) and the VISIT_OCCURRENCE table was ensured by most data sources, though PHARMO demonstrated partial compliance (5-10% issues, 6.5% in PROCEDURES) and ARS failed (>10% issues, 100% in PROCEDURES).

Finally, all data sources adhered to the logical constraint that a parent's birth date must precede their child's birth date by at least 12 years. SIDIAP was unable to perform checks involving the VISIT_OCCURRENCE and PERSONS_RELATIONSHIPS tables due to the unavailability of these tables in the data instance for this deliverable (see Table 2).

To be noted, [Table 5](#) provides a general assessment of the compliance to quality indicators, but Level 2 runs per CDM table. Further detailed information is available upon request to lead contributors.

Table 5. Temporal plausibility across DAPs and data sources in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

Indicator	Data Access Provider (DAP)											
	UOSL	CHUT EFEMERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_F ISABIO	SIDIAP	FERR	ARS	THL	USWAN
Dates of events before birth	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
Dates of events after death	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Dates of events outside obser- vation periods	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+/-	-	+	-
Subjects observed in a CDM ta- ble of interest without a corre- sponding record in the PER- SONS table	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	-	+	+
Observations associated with a visit_occurrence_id which occur before the visit_start_date	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	N/A	-	-	+	+
Observations associated with a visit_occurrence_id which occur after the visit_end_date	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	+	N/A	-	+	+	+
Observations associated with a visit_occurrence_id for which the associated person_id differs from that in the VISIT_OCCUR- RENCE table	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	N/A	-	-	+	+
Subjects indicated in PER- SON_RELATIONSHIPS as the parent of a child whose birth date is less than 12 years prior to the recorded birth date of the linkage child	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	N/A	+	+	-	+

N/A: Not Available.

VISIT OCURRENCE table is missing in the data instance, therefore *visit_occurrence_id* is unavailable.

3.4 INSIGHT Level 3: Data Characterization

The fitness for purpose of the data sources depends on the study question. INSIGHT level 3 produces many indicators that can be used for a detailed fitness for purpose assessment based on pre-defined study requirements for the research question. Below we describe several parameters such as source and study populations, follow-up, events of interest, medicines of interest, independent of a study question.

3.4.1 Source population and study population

In [Table 6](#), we show the distribution of the source and study population for the D2 instances included in the data characterization. We showed that the source population in the data instances were subsets from the source data. The demographic composition of the source and study populations varied across data sources, based on the ETL decisions that were made and approvals obtained (as per protocol data sources should ETL all children, and women of childbearing age). The study populations comprised a higher proportion of females in most data sources such as UOSL, CHUT data sources, PHARMO and RDRU_FISABIO. Most individuals present in the source population were born after 1 January 1995.

We observed that age distributions at the start of observation varied highly. Younger age groups (0 years) constituted large portions of the populations in data sources like THL (63.5%, N = 1,316,839) and USWAN (56.2%, N = 10,819), while older age groups (55+ years) were prominent in data sources like BPE (11.9%, N = 854,161) and SIDIAP (9.1%, N = 587,223). The level 3 checks show how the population was selected. This aligns with ETL instructions of including all subjects followed up from birth, if available.

At the start of follow-up, female individuals represent most of the study population in most data sources. For example, UOSL had 69.2% females (N = 2,404,605), and CHUT EFEMERIS exclusively included females (N = 146,108). We found male individuals in datasets such as BPE (47.7%, N = 3,059,924), SIDIAP (51%, N = 2,928,045), FERR (50.7%, N = 2,158,156), and ARS (49.9%, N = 1,663,231) providing a more balanced gender distribution.

As requested, women of childbearing age (12–55 years) represent a significant portion of the study population across the participating data sources. Proportion ranges from 87% in PHARMO to 7.1% in RDRU_FISABIO. THL, FERR, SIDIAP and BPE showed similar values, with women of childbearing age comprising 73.8%, 70.6%, 67.7% and 66.5%, respectively. For some data sources, such as EFEMERIS, POMME 10 and POMME 15, we were not able to calculate specific figures for women of childbearing age within the study population due to their data source structure based on pregnancy cohort. Restrictions also apply to THL, as only women of childbearing age who became pregnant during follow up were included in the data instance. Unfortunately, ARS did not provide this information. Due to the nature of the data (dummy data) in CNR-IT, results of this analysis are not included in table 6.

In [Figure 5](#), we provide information by sex and birth status (non-born yet) and by age bands in [Figure 6](#).

Table 6. Distribution of source population and study population in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

		Data Access Providers (DAPs)											
		UOSL	CHUT EFEMERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FIS ABIO	SIDIAP ^s	FERR	ARS	THL	USWAN*
Source population at start study^a (1-01-1995)													
Born before start study data	Female (N, %)	163985 (46.8%)	143361 (50.1%)	8225 (49.6%)	10075 (48.5%)	3074599 (42.8%)	473903 (67.1%)	364493 (37.1%)	2726470 (42.7%)	1694681 (37.8%)	1346879 (37.3%)	756895 (36.5%)	N/A
Born after 1 January 1995	Male (N, %)	553782 (15.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2535328 (35.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2625504 (41.1%)	1737122 (38.8%)	1309760 (36.2%)	0 (0%)	N/A
	(N, %)	130811 (37.4%)	142666 (49.9%)	8372 (50.4%)	10685 (51.5%)	1568457 (21.9%)	231894 (32.9%)	617940 (62.9%)	1031806 (16.2%)	1048855 (23.4%)	957118 (26.5%)	1316839 (63.5%)	N/A
Source population by age band at start follow up													
0		103545 (29.6%)	139885 (48.9%)	8367 (50.4%)	10459 (50.4%)	648303 (9%)	196352 (27.8%)	522662 (53.2%)	877864 (13.8%)	982972 (21.9%)	620684 (17.2%)	1316839 (63.5%)	10819 (56.2%)
1-4		77468 (2.2%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	701422 (9.8%)	40473 (5.7%)	83499 (8.5%)	300280 (4.7%)	167618 (3.7%)	194935 (5.4%)	38893 (1.876%)	194278 (10.1%)
5-14		379058 (10.8%)	62 (0.03%)	3 (0.02%)	3 (0.02%)	875684 (12.2%)	117268 (16.6%)	12801 (1.3%)	599882 (9.4%)	418443 (9.3%)	493972 (13.7%)	215657 (10.4%)	244232 (12.66%)
15-24		501228 (14.3%)	24556 (8.6%)	1426 (8.6%)	1522 (7.3%)	935068 (13%)	116770 (16.5%)	95784 (9.7%)	841196 (13.2%)	778409 (17.4%)	505670 (14%)	259375 (12.508%)	176240 (9.1%)
25-34		692201 (19.8%)	98141 (34.3%)	5608 (33.8%)	7140 (34.4%)	1178955 (16.4%)	130892 (18.5%)	205015 (20.9%)	1364115 (21.4%)	1159842 (25.9%)	765901 (21.1%)	196085 (9.456%)	175568 (9.11%)
35-44		455217 (13%)	23189 (8.1%)	1185 (7.14%)	1627 (7.8%)	1032515 (14.4%)	93242 (13.3%)	52192 (5.4%)	1050206 (16.5%)	795216 (17.7%)	570039 (15.8%)	40747 (1.965%)	49862 (2.59%)
45-54		337851 (9.6%)	182 (0.06%)	8 (0.04%)	6 (0.06%)	952506 (13.3%)	10238 (1.5%)	9058 (0.9%)	763014 (11.9%)	136679 (3.2%)	324735 (9%)	6113 (0.294%)	4019 (0.21%)
55+		23278 (0.7%)	12 (0.01%)	0 (0%)	3 (0.02%)	854161 (11.9%)	564 (0.1%)	1422 (0.1%)	587223 (9.1%)	41479 (0.9%)	137641 (3.8%)	25 (0.001%)	441 (0.03%)
Study population at start follow up													
Female (N, %)		240460 (69.2%)	146108 (100%)	12347 (74.4%)	15427 (74.3%)	3350126 (52.3%)	648611 (92%)	667898 (68.1%)	2808753 (49%)	2100237 (49.3%)	1668128 (50.1%)	1403764 (67.7%)	1205044 (63.4%)
Male (N, %)		107261 (30.8%)	0 (0%)	4248 (25.6%)	5330 (25.7%)	3059924 (47.7%)	56102 (8%)	312402 (31.9%)	2928045 (51%)	2158156 (50.7%)	1663231 (49.9%)	669960 (32.3%)	696932 (36.6%)
Females of childbearing age													
Female (N, %)		138940 (57.8%)	N/A	N/A	N/A	2228239 (66.5%)	564082 (87%)	47644 (7.1%)	1901393 (67.7%)	1482714 (70.6%)	N/A	1036569 (73.8%)	693766 (57.6%)

* The information about source population by sex at start study date was unavailable due to privacy restrictions. In USWAN, governance approvals for this study were sought for a restricted population of "women of childbearing age and their children".

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*** The study population size calculation was performed after applying the time exclusion criteria, such as start study date (1 January 1995), 1 year of lookback (original start of follow up date + 365.25 days), 1 day of follow up in the study period (start study date until last data availability date).*

**** Denominator is total number of women in the study population.*

^ Source population size is calculated at a fixed time point (1 January 1995 – start study date). All subjects that enter the data source after this time point are not present in this calculation and are shown as 'Not born yet' in the stratification by age band

Figure 5. Comparison of study population and source population by sex and birth status by DAPs. For USWAN only data about the study population is available. *Not born yet* stands for individuals born after the start of the study date (01-01-1995)

Figure 6. Size of source population by age band across data sources.

3.4.2 Follow-up

We show in [Table 7](#) the distribution of follow-up across data sources. The included data sources demonstrate wide variability in calendar years covered and follow-up durations.

Calendar year coverage varies significantly across data sources. Older data sources, such as SIDIAP, THL, and USWAN, included data from 1995–1997 in their instance, resulting in higher total follow-up times due to their long observation durations. In contrast, data sources, such as CHUT EFEMERIS (2004–2019) and RDRU_FISABIO (2010–2021), included less historic data and had shorter follow-up times, particularly in cohorts established after 2010. CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15 have notably limited follow-up durations (80585 and 35838 PY, respectively), reflecting their narrower calendar coverage (2009–2020 and 2014–2018). Larger data sources (i.e. availability through the years) like ARS and THL show significantly extended follow-up times (42215324 and 33758264 PY, respectively) due to their broader time spans and extensive population bases. Meanwhile, data sources with more recent calendar coverage, such as CHUT POMME 15 (2014–2018), generally show shorter overall follow-up lengths (35838 PY).

In [Figure 8](#), we provide information of follow-up by age groups. The analysis revealed distinct distributions across data sources. Data sources such as UOSL, SIDIAP, FERR, and USWAN demonstrate substantial person-years in the 30–39 and 40–49 age ranges (e.g., UOSL: 20.8% and 18.3%, SIDIAP: 22.2% and 23.6%, FERR: 22.7% and 23.6%, USWAN: 21.9% and 24.7%). These age groups accounted for a significant portion of the follow-up in many data sources. Follow-up in the 50–59 age range is relatively low across most sources (e.g., UOSL: 9.6%, SIDIAP: 13.1%, FERR: 11.4%, USWAN: 13.2%). In some data sources (e.g., CHUT EFEMERIS, CHUT POMME 10 and 15), follow-up in these older age groups is negligible or absent. The 1–9 age band shows evenly distributed follow-up between age bands in UOSL (18%) and SIDIAP (12.6%) but is missing in CHUT EFEMERIS (due to the nature of the data source comprising only pregnant women). The 10–19 and 20–29 age bands are moderately covered, particularly in UOSL (14.6% and 16.3%) and SIDIAP (13.3% and 16%). UOSL and SIDIAP generally show broad follow-up across all age groups, though older ages have less proportional coverage. CHUT datasets (EFEMERIS, POMME 10 and POMME 15) have limited data for older ages (due to the data source specifics comprising only pregnant women or pregnant women and their off springs) and, in some cases, negligible coverage for younger age groups (particularly in CHUT EFEMERIS since minimum included age band is 10-19, reflecting women of childbearing age).

Table 7. Distribution of follow up in the study population in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

Indicator	Data Experts and Access Providers											
	UOSL	CHUT EFEMERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FISA BIO*	SIDIAP	FERR	ARS	THL	USWAN
Calendar years covered	2004 - 2021	2004 - 2019	2009 - 2020	2014 - 2018	2017 - 2020	1997 - 2019	2010 - 2021	2006 - 2021	1995 - 2020	1995 - 2021	1996 - 2019	1995 - 2021
Total follow up time (PY)	42885407	137474	80585	35838	18684055	10969960	4748307	61036045	66287101	42215324	33758264	32955797
Follow up time (person years)												
0	1013024 (2.4%)	0 (0%)	8366 (10.4%)	10468 (29.2%)	520203 (2.8%)	117016 (1.1%)	470713 (9.9%)	762473 (1.2%)	930087 (1.4%)	418917 (1%)	1311617 (3.9%)	1030234 (3.1%)
1-9	7703861 (18%)	0 (0%)	64196 (79.7%)	15323 (42.8%)	4074486 (21.8%)	1114252 (10.2%)	3532247 (74.4%)	7683691 (12.6%)	8022944 (12.1%)	4494770 (10.6%)	10022986 (29.7%)	9002661 (27.3%)
10-19	6260070 (14.6%)	2808 (2%)	148 (0.2%)	149 (0.4%)	2635768 (14.1%)	2048099 (18.7%)	745347 (15.7%)	8119035 (13.3%)	8458019 (12.8%)	5361205 (12.7%)	7510607 (22.2%)	8410594 (25.5%)
20-29	6973827 (16.3%)	63728 (46.4%)	3873 (4.8%)	4489 (12.5%)	2955558 (15.8%)	2261300 (20.6%)		9225586 (15.1%)	10600850 (16%)	6708429 (15.9%)	5278532 (15.6%)	6166094 (18.7%)
30-39	8933904 (20.8%)	67117 (48.8%)	3801 (4.7%)	5116 (14.27%)	3554419 (19%)	2360055 (21.5%)	0 (0%)	13545677 (22.2%)	15047262 (22.7%)	9258905 (21.9%)	5333258 (15.8%)	4258084 (12.9%)
40-49	7858868 (18.3%)	3788 (2.78%)	201 (0.2%)	284 (0.8%)	2973161 (15.9%)	2179350 (19.9%)	0 (0%)	1376104 (22.5%)	15645796 (23.6%)	10416334 (24.7%)	3342124 (9.9%)	2955081 (9.1%)
50-59	4141853 (9.6%)	33 (0.02%)	0 (0%)	9 (0.03%)	1970460 (10.6%)	889888 (8%)	0 (0%)	7938540 (13.1%)	7582143 (11.4%)	5556764 (13.2%)	959140 (2.9%)	1133049 (3.4%)

*The age bands 10-19 and 20-29 were concatenated into 10-29.

Figure 7. Total follow-up time per data source

Figure 8. Total follow-up by age band across data sources

3.4.3 Start and End follow up Distribution

In [Table 8](#), we highlight the temporal distribution and concentration of data records across DAPs, emphasizing their variability in start and end follow-up periods and the prominence of specific years and months within each data source.

Across the DAPs, the years with the highest percentage of records varied for both the start and end of follow-up periods. For UOSL, the start of follow-up was most prominent in 2004 (46.5%), with January being the most significant month (29.6%). The end of follow-up peaked in 2021 (98.8%), with December contributing to 99.9% of records. Similarly, CHUT EFEMERIS showed 2014 as the most notable year for start follow-up (8.5%), with October being the most prominent month. However, multiple years (2010, 2014, 2015) shared the highest end follow-up records at 8.4%, with September and October frequently contributing high percentages.

CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15 exhibited concentrated data during their shorter intervals. For POMME 10, 2010 accounted for 51.1% of start follow-up records, and July stood out as the main month. The end follow-up year 2020 dominated with 41%, with June contributing entirely (100%). POMME 15 showed similar trends, with 2015 being the dominant year for start follow-up (50.8%) and 2018 for end follow-up (48.2%).

BPE, SIDIAP, and RDRU_FISABIO demonstrated strong year-end patterns, with 2020, 2021, and 2021 being the respective prominent end follow-up years. Notably, December consistently emerged as the key month for these data sources. PHARMO, THL, and USWAN presented substantial data records for earlier periods, such as 1998 (PHARMO, 56.3%), 1996 (THL, 39.7%), and 1995 (USWAN, 45%), where January was the most prominent month with records varying from 93.3%(THL) to 98% (PHARMO).

For ARS, records spanned 1950–2021, with 2006 contributing 8% of start follow-up records, and December being prominent. FERR showcased 1995 and 2020 as the most prominent years for start and end follow-up, respectively, with January and December as the main months. Across most DAPs, December emerged as the dominant month for end follow-up records, reflecting seasonal or administrative closures.

Table 8. Temporal distribution and concentration of data records in start and end follow-up periods in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

Metric	Most prominent year	Total records	Most prominent month	Total records for most prominent year
UOSL				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2004-2020 Mean records across years: 5.9% 	2004 (46.5%)	3477220	January (29.6%)	1615224
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2004-2022 Mean records across years: 5.3% 	2021 (98.8%)	3477221	December (99.9%)	3435648
CHUT EFEMERIS				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2014-2019 Mean records across years: 6.2% 	2014 (8.5%)	146108	October (9.3%)	12394
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2005-2019 Mean records across years: 6.2% 	2010 (8.4%), 2014 (8.4%), 2015 (8.4%)	146113	October (9.1%) September (9.6%) September (9.1%)	12267 12280 12286
CHUT POMME 10				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2009-2011 Mean records across years: 33.3% 	2010 (51.1%)	16595	July (11.5%)	8473
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2010-2020 Mean records across years: 9.1% 	2020 (41%)	16612	June (100%)	6816
CHUT POMME 15				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2014-2016 Mean records across years: 33.3% 	2015 (50.8%)	20757	July (11.6%)	10552
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2015-2018 Mean records across years: 25% 	2018 (48.2%)	20760	June (100%)	10016
BPE				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2015-2020 Mean records across years: 16.7% 	2015 (90.2%)	6593012	January (97.1%)	5944507
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2015-2018 Mean records across years: 16.7% 	2020 (99.7%)	6593012	December (99.9%)	6573566
PHARMO				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 1997-2019 Mean records across years: 4.3% 	1998 (56.3%)	704733	January (98%)	396690

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2004-2021 Mean records across years: 5.9% 	2019 (30.6%)	704726	December (92.6%)	215533
RDRU FISABIO				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2010-2020 Mean records across years: 9.1% 	2010 (57.1%)	980300	January (91.7%)	559708
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2010-2021 Mean records across years: 8.3% 	2021 (94.1%)	980300	December (99.2%)	922157
SIDIAP				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 2006-2021 Mean records across years: 6.3% 	2006 (65.1%)	5736798	January (95.9%)	3733036
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 2014-2021 Mean records across years: 12.5% 	2021 (88.8%)	5736798	December (98.1%)	5094355
FERR				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 1995-2020 Mean records across years: 3.8% 	1995 (42.8%)	4258393	January (95.9%)	1821682
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 1995-2020 Mean records across years: 3.8% 	2020 (86.3%)	4258393	December (98.6%)	3673040
ARS				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 1950-2021 Mean records across years: 1.4% 	2006 (8%)	3331443	December (79.5%)	264920
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 1995-2023* Mean records across years: 3.4% 	2023 (76.9%)	3331375	December (98.8%)	2560852
THL				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 1996-2018 Mean records across years: 4.4% 	1996 (39.7%)	2073724	January (93.3%)	823197
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 1996-2019 Mean records across years: 4.1% 	2019 (99.6%)	2073724	December (100%)	2065699
USWAN				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start of follow up Interval: 1995-2021 Mean records across years: 3.7% 	1995 (45%)	1901976	January (95.5%)	855480
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End of follow up Interval: 1995-2024** Mean records across years: 3.3% 	2022 (79.5%)	1899699	July (99.5%)	1510167

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N/A -Not available

Mean records calculated as sum of percentages across all years present divided by the total number of years available.

**Script ran in 2022; presence of future years (2023) shows continuation of follow-up.*

***Script ran in 2023; presence of future years (2024) shows continuation of follow-up.*

3.4.4 Registration in the data source

In [Table 9](#), we show the analysis of registration time point after birth across DAPs, which reveals distinct patterns in the registration timing. UOSL exhibits the most prominent registration time point at week 0, accounting for 28.8% of records. The registration interval spans 0 to 2847 weeks after birth, with other intervals contributing between 0.1% and 0.3%. Similarly, BPE and PHARMO also show a peak at week 0, with 12.4% and 26.2% of records, respectively. The registration intervals for BPE and PHARMO range from 0 to 2900 weeks and 0 to 2691 weeks after birth, with other intervals contributing between 1.3% and 2.9% for BPE and 0.1% and 1.9% for PHARMO.

FERR also has a notable concentration at week 0 after birth, comprising 19% of records, with a registration range of 0 to 1641 weeks and other intervals contributing between 0.1% and 1.6%. In contrast, SIDIAP shows the most prominent time point at week 3, accounting for 2.9% of records. Its registration spans 0 to 2917 weeks after birth, with other intervals contributing between 0.1% and 2.8%. For USWAN, week 0 is the most prominent time point, representing 54% of records, within a shorter registration interval of 0 to 356 weeks after birth, with other intervals contributing 0.1%.

In summary, for most DAPs, except for SIDIAP, where registration time points are more evenly distributed across the time interval, newborns are predominantly registered within the first week of life in the data source. This concentration at the earliest time point reflects a common practice in many data sources, where the initial registration aligns with birth or early postnatal care.

For other DAPs such as CHUT EFEMERIS, CHUT POMME 10, and CHUT POMME 15, data related to registration time points is not generated due to the specific structure of these data sources, where follow-up periods are based on pregnancy episodes, often involving multiple periods per subject. Additionally, no relevant data was available for RDRU_FISABIO, CNR, ARS, and THL. Notably, SIDIAP had the highest percentages recorded in the 0 to 6 weeks category, ranging from 0.4% to 2.9%. Due to the nature of the data (dummy data) in CNR-IT, results of this analysis are not included in table 9.

Table 9. Registration in data source after birth in the data instance for ConcePTION

DAP	Most prominent time point (weeks, %)	Registration time interval in weeks after birth	Percentage interval (excluding prominent time point, %)
UOSL	0 (28.8)	0 - 2847	0.1 – 0.3
CHUT EFEMERIS*	N/A	N/A	N/A
CHUT POMME 10*	N/A	N/A	N/A
CHUT POMME 15*	N/A	N/A	N/A
BPE	0 (12.4)	0 - 2900	1.3 – 2.9
PHARMO	0 (26.2)	0 - 2691	0.1 – 1.9
RDRU_FISABIO	N/A	N/A	N/A
SIDIAP**	3 (2.9)	0 - 2917	0.1 – 2.8
FERR	0 (19)	0 - 1641	0.1 -1.6
ARS	N/A	N/A	N/A
THL	N/A	N/A	N/A
USWAN	0 (54)	0 - 356	0.1

N/A- Not available

*Due to the data source structure this data is not created (follow up periods are created based on pregnancy episodes, with the same subjects having multiple periods).

**The highest percentages in the categories 0 to 6 weeks (0.4% - 2.9%).

USWAN governance restrictions restriction recording to week of birth. By law, all births must be registered within 6 weeks.

3.4.5 Availability of conditions of interest

In [Table 10](#), we show the temporal coverage and provenance of health care data across data sources reflecting the diverse capabilities and focuses using the ‘meaning’ variable in CDM tables. ARS provides extensive coverage across multiple data streams, including access to mental health services (1996–2021), birth registries (2002–2020), and emergency room diagnoses (2010–2021). UOSL also offers broad temporal data, with cancer registries (2005–2020) and hospitalization records (2008–2021). EFEMERIS focuses on hospitalization data, covering 2004–2019 for associated diagnoses and 2005–2019 for primary care. POMME 10 (2010–2011) and POMME 15 (2015–2016) provide narrower coverage, emphasizing hospitalization records. BPE includes data estimated from death registries (2017) and hospitalization records (2017–2020). PHARMO captures primary care events (2009–2019) and hospital diagnoses (2012–2019), while RDRU_FISABIO spans 2010–2021 for all their data banks such as perinatal death registries, anomalies registries, and hospitalization data for the data instance in the ConcePTION project.

SIDIAP offers comprehensive healthcare coverage (2014–2021), including ICU and primary care diagnoses, emergency events, and specialist diagnoses. FERR provides long-term mental health service data for children and teenagers (1995–2020). THL captures a broad range of healthcare data from 1996–2019, including primary care and hospitalization records, anomaly registry, and birth registry. USWAN provides prolonged data coverage for primary diagnosis (pd), secondary diagnosis (sd), spanning from 1995–2021, EUROCAT from 1998, and education and child development.

In [Table 11](#), we summarize the presence of various conditions of interest that were predefined for the data characterization ([Box 1](#)), based on different code lists applied in different data sources. The Level 3 checks provide a good opportunity to inspect if these conditions were extracted and whether there were temporal patterns. The diagnostic data availability, vocabulary usage, and temporal coverage varied significantly across the DAPs. Data sources such as ARS, THL, and USWAN, exhibited extensive temporal coverage starting from 1995–1996 and extending until 2021. In contrast, POMME 10 (2010–2011) and POMME 15 (2015–2016), had narrower time spans, confirming limited follow-up.

Conditions such as anxiety/depression, epilepsy, gestational diabetes, migraine, multiple sclerosis and pre-eclampsia were consistently available across DAPs except ARS, with temporal spans ranging from mid-1990s to 2021 in data sources like THL and USWAN. Vocabularies predominantly included ICD-10 and its derivatives (e.g., ICD10ES, ICD10CM). However, certain conditions exhibited significant gaps (zero counts). Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), autism spectrum disorder, elective termination, multiple gestation and low birth weight were unavailable in CHUT datasets (due to the data model of the data source where records coming from the birth registries are saved under the child id and not mother id, making it not possible to capture with the current scripts), while Termination of Pregnancy for Fetal Anomaly (TOPFA) was confined to BPE, SIDIAP and USWAN. Breast cancer and systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) were widely documented across DAPs with large temporal spans, while stillbirth and neonatal death had more sporadic representation such as in PHARMO and SIDIAP. The CHUT datasets and ARS showed notable limitations in the availability of conditions such as preterm birth, spontaneous abortion, and rheumatoid arthritis. BPE, although with limited time span (2017–2020) showed a high coverage of the conditions of interest, missing only low birth weight and pain. Due to the nature of the data (dummy data) in CNR-IT, results of this analysis are not included in table 10 and table 11. Conditions availability is reflective of the codelists used. See annex 1 for codelists used. In figure 9, we provide comparative graphs showing the availability of conditions of interest per year across DAPs.

Rates of the conditions of interest over years are provided in annex II.

Table 10. Diagnostic data time span by data bank in data instance for the ConcePTION project

DAP	Provenance
ARS	access_to_mental_health_service_primary (1996-2021), exemption (1996-2021), birth_registry_child(2002-2020), hospitalisation_primary (2003-2021), hospitalisation_secondary (2003-2021), death_registry (2010), emergency room_diagnosis (2010-2021), access_to_mental_health_ser- vice_comorbidity (2012-2021)
UOSL	cancer_registry (2005-2020), hospitalisation_primary (2008-2021), hospitalisation_secondary (2008-2021), primary_care_diagnosis (2008-2021)
EFEMERIS	hospitalisation_associated (2004-2019), hospitalisation_primary (2005-2019), hospitalisation_linked (2016)
POMME 10	hospitalisation_associated (2010-2011), hospitalisation_primary (2010-2011)
POMME 15	hospitalisation_associated (2015-2016), hospitalisation_primary (2015-2016)
BPE	estimated_from_death_registry_and_inpatient (2017), hospitalisation_primary (2017-2020), hospitalisation_secondary (2017-2020)
PHARMO	hospital_diagnosis (2012-2019), primary_care_event (2009-2019)
RDRU_FISABIO	perinatal_death_registry_child (2010-2019), perinatal_death_registry_mother (2011-2019), anomalies_mother_registry (2011-2019), death_registry (2011-2019), cancer_registry (2011-2019), hospitalisation_secondary (2016-2021), hospitalisation_primary (2016-2021)
SIDIAP	hospital_diagnosis (2014-2021), hospitalisation_ICU_primary (2019-2021), hospitalisation_ICU_secondary (2018-2021), hospitalisation_primary (2014- 2021), hospitalisation_secondary (2014-2021), primary_care_emer- gency_event (2014-2021), primary_care_event (2014-2021), specialist_diagnosis (2014-2021)
FERR	access_to_mental_health_service_primary_baby and teenager (1995-2020)
THL	primary_care_diagnosis (1996-2019), hospitalisation_primary (1996-2019), hospitalisation_secondary (1996-2019), anomaly_registry (1996-2018), birth_registry (1996-2018)
USWAN	pd (1995-2021), sd (1995-2021)

Table 11. Presence of events of interest and temporal patterns in the EVENT table of the data instance for ConcePTION

	Data Access Providers											
	UOSL	CHUT EFEM- ERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FIS ABIO	SIDIAP	FERR*	ARS	THL [§]	USWAN [^]
Overall diagnostic data time span	2005-2020, 2008-2021	2004-2019, 2005-2019	2010-2011	2015-2016	2017-2020	2009-2019, 2012-2019	2010-2019, 2011-2019, 2016-2021	2014-2021, 2019-2021	1995-2020	1996-2021, 2002-2020, 2003-2021, 2010-2021, 2012-2021	1996-2019	1995-2021
Anxiety/Depression												
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021	2005-2019	2010-2011	2015-2016	2017-2020	2012**, 2013-2019	2011-2015**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	1996, 1999-2020		1996**, 1997-2019	1996-2021
Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10			ICD10CM		ICD9, ICD10	N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021				2017-2020			2014-2021		1996-1997**, 2000-2002**, 2003-2021	1997-2019	1996-2021
Autism spectrum disorder												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10			ICD10CM		ICD10	N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021				2017-2020			2014-2021		2010**	1998-2019	1996-2021
Breast cancer												

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Availability	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10			ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10	ICD9	N/A	ICD10
Years	2005- 2021	2012- 2013** 2016** 2019**			2017** 2018- 2020	2009- 2019	2011-2021	2014-2021	2005**, 2007- 2018**	1996- 1997**,199 8-2021	1996**, 1997- 2019	1996-2021

Elective termination

Availability	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	
Years	2008- 2021				2018- 2020	2009- 2019	2016-2021	2014-2021	2019**		1996- 2019	

Epilepsy

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008- 2021	2005- 2019	2010, 2011* *	2015- 2016	2017- 2020	2009- 2019	2011-2021	2014-2021	1995- 2020		1996- 2019	1996-2021

Foetal growth restriction (FGR)

Availability	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
Vocabularies						ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM		ICD9		
Years						2012**, 2013- 2019	2011-2021	2014-2021		2002**, 2004**, 2016**, 2017- 2018, 2020*		

Gestational Diabetes

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008- 2021	2005- 2019	2010- 2011	2015- 2016	2018- 2020	2009- 2019	2011-2021	2014-2021	2019**		1996- 2019	1996-2021

Low birth weight

Availability	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Vocabularies						ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES		ICD10			
Years						2012- 2019	2010-2021		1995- 2020			

Major congenital anomalies

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10			ICD10CM			N/A	ICD10
Years	2008- 2021	2005- 2019	2010- 2011	2015- 2016	2017- 2020			2014-2021			1996- 2019	1998-2021

Microcephaly

Availability	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies					ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years					2017- 2020	2012- 2019	2010- 2014**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	1995- 1998**, 1999- 2020		1996- 2019	1995-2021

Migraine

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008- 2021	2005**, 2009- 2011**, 2012- 2019	2010*, *	2015, 2016**	2017**, 2018- 2020	2009- 2019	2012- 2014**, 2015-2021	2014-2021	2005- 2006**, 2007- 2020		1997- 2019	1996-2021

Multiple gestation

Availability	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008- 2021				2017- 2020	2012- 2019	2011- 2013**, 2014-2021	2014-2021	2018- 2020**		1996- 2019	1996-2021

Multiple sclerosis

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
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Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021	2006-2019	2010-2011*	2015, 2016**	2018-2020	2009-2019	2012-2015**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020**		1996**, 1997-2019	1996-2021
Neonatal death												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10			ICD10CM			N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021				2017-2020			2014-2021			1997-1999**, 2000-2019	1999, 2001-2005**, 2015**
Pain												
Availability	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
Vocabularies						ICD10	ICD10ES		ICD10			
Years						2013-2019	2016-2021		2020**			
Pre-eclampsia												
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021	2005-2019	2010-2011	2015-2016	2018-2020	2009-2019	2011-2021	2014-2021	2018**		1996-2019	1996-2021
Preterm birth												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM			N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021				2017-2020	2012-2019	2011-2021	2014-2021			1996-2019	1995-2021
Rheumatoid arthritis												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10		N/A	ICD10
Years	2008-2021				2018-2020	2009-2019	2011**, 2014**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	2019**		1997-2019	1996-2021

Spontaneous abortion												
Availability	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Vocabularies	ICD10				ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10	N/A		
Years	2008-2021				2018-2020	2009-2019	2015**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	2019**	1996-2019		
Stillbirth												
Availability	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
Vocabularies					ICD10	ICD10, ICPC	ICD10ES	ICD10CM	N/A			
Years					2017, 2018-2020**	2009-2019	2016-2021	2014-2021	1996**, 1997-2018, 2019**			
Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)												
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Vocabularies	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10	ICD10, ICD10ES	ICD10CM	ICD10	N/A		ICD10
Years	2008-2021	2004**, 2005-2019	2010, 2011*	2015-2016	2017-2020	2012**, 2013-2019	2012-2015**, 2016-2021	2014-2021	2020**	1997-2019	1996-2021	
Termination of Pregnancy for Foetal Anomaly (TOPFA)												
Availability	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-
Vocabularies					ICD10				ICD10CM	N/A		
Years					2017-2020				2014-2021	1996**, 1997-2019		

Gap years or deviations from start or end of the overall time span (depending on data bank) means no records for the condition of interest was found.

** Less than 5 records

*ICD9 codes also available, but due to missingness of this vocabulary in the codelist (presence of ICD9CM instead), diagnoses recorded under ICD9 were not captured.

§Due to privacy concerns the information on code counts by diagnostic vocabulary was not provided. The vocabularies present are ICD10 and ICPC2.

^Primary care READ codes from the phenotype library codes were also available, but due to misalignment with the code list used (RCD instead of READ) these codes were not extracted. USWAN data on pregnancy loss (outside EUROCAT) are redacted by regulators; regulators considered these data unduly sensitive.

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Figure 9. Presence of conditions of interest over study timespan by year across DAPs

3.4.6 Completeness of diagnostic data

In [Table 12](#), we show the completeness of event codes across DAPs, which revealed minimal data gaps in most sources. Notably, UOSL, CHUT EFEMERIS, CHUT POMME 10, CHUT POMME 15, PHARMO, RDRU_FISABIO, SIDIAP, FERR, THL, and USWAN demonstrated no missing event codes (0%). These datasets collectively represented substantial total record counts, ranging from 12530 records in CHUT POMME 10 to over 306 billion records in USWAN, highlighting their extensive coverage.

In contrast, BPE exhibited only 26 missing event codes, accounting for a negligible proportion (0.0001%) of its 25,594,954 total records. However, ARS presented a notable exception, with 2,238,016 missing event codes, comprising 13.7% of its 16,374,741 total records.

The total record counts reflect data after the application of stringent exclusion criteria, including the removal of records with missing dates, meanings or vocabularies, subjects not in the study population, records outside individual observation periods, or vocabularies not part of predefined code lists. Additionally, records with unknown or other sex classifications were also excluded.

Table 12. Missing diagnostic event codes in the data instance for the ConcePTION project

DAP	Missing event codes (N, %)	Total number of records*
UOSL	0 (0)	103743911
CHUT EFEMERIS	0 (0)	244179
CHUT POMME 10	0 (0)	12530
CHUT POMME 15	0 (0)	20259
BPE	26 (0.0001)	25594954
PHARMO	0 (0)	7268843
RDRU_FISABIO	0 (0)	2267408
SIDIAP	0 (0)	69105457
FERR	0 (0)	847092
ARS	2238016 (13.7)	16374741
THL	0 (0)	76502679
USWAN	0 (0)	306268659343

**Total number of records in the tables of interest after application of exclusion criteria such as missing dates, meaning and vocabulary data; subjects not part of the study population; records outside the observation period for each subject; vocabularies not part of the code list used to filter the data; sex as unknown or other*

3.4.7 Medication use and vaccine uptake

In [Table 13](#), we show the medication and vaccine provenance using the variable ‘meaning’ from the CDM table. The dispensing data across DAPs demonstrates a wide variation in provenance and time span, reflecting the diversity of the data sources. ARS offers comprehensive data on dispensing in community pharmacies (2002–2020), Regional Health Service-associated dispensing (2008–2021), hospital pharmacy dispensing for inpatient and outpatient use (2004–2021) and unspecified vaccine administration (1995–2021). Similarly, UOSL provides dispensing data from community pharmacies and vaccination records covering a substantial period from 2004 to 2021, while EFEMERIS includes similar data spanning 2004–2019 for medicines. Shorter time spans are evident in data sources like POMME 10 (2009–2020) and POMME 15 (2014–2018), focused exclusively on community pharmacy dispensing.

BPE presents medicinal products data through community pharmacy dispensing and unspecified hospital pharmacy dispensing, both spanning 2015–2020 for medicinal products as well as vaccines. PHARMO captures prescription data from general practitioners (GPs) and dispensings from outpatient pharmacies from 2009 to 2019, while RDRU_FISABIO manages outpatient pharmacy data from 2013 to 2021. SIDIAP provides dispensing data from community pharmacies for the years 2014–2021 and vaccines data coming from primary care records (2014–2021). FERR covers both community pharmacies and hospital pharmacies for home use during 2009–2020.

THL offers one of the most extensive data sources, covering community pharmacy dispensing from 1996 to March 2019, while USWAN provides primary care prescription data (including specialist-initiated prescriptions) and vaccine data, both spanning from 1995–2021. Prescription data is available in CHUT POMME 10 and 25, BPE, PHARMO and FERR.

Table 13. Medicinal products data time span by data bank in the data instance for ConcepTION

DAP	Provenance
ARS	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2002-2020), dispensing_in_community_pharmacy_on_behalf_of_RHS (2008-2021), dispensing_in_hospital_pharmacy_for_inpatient_use (2004-2021), dispensing_in_hospital_pharmacy_for_outpatient_use (2004-2021), administration_of_vaccine_unspecified (1995-2021)*
UOSL	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2004-2021), vaccination_record (2004-2021)*
EFEMERIS	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2004-2019)
POMME 10	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2009-2020)
POMME 15	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2014-2018)
BPE	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2015-2020)^, dispensing_in_hospital_pharmacy_unspecified (2015-2020), dispensing_in_hospital_pharmacy_unspecified (2017-2020)*
PHARMO	community_gp_dispensing (2009-2019), outpatient_pharmacy_dispensing (2009-2019)
RDRU_FISABIO	outpatient_pharmacy_management (2013-2021)
SIDIAP	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2014-2021), primary_care_medical_record (2014-2021)*
FERR	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (2009-2020), dispensing_in_hospital_pharmacy_for_home_use (2009-2020)
THL	dispensing_in_community_pharmacy (1996-2019)
USWAN	gp (1995-2021), administration_at_general_practitioner (1995-2021)*

*Data retrieved from the VACCINES table

^Same data for both the MEDICINES and VACCINES tables

We present in [Table 14](#), the availability of medicinal products of interest across data sources, grouped by therapeutic class. The medicinal product data across DAPs reveals comprehensive yet varied coverage across therapeutic classes and time spans. Overall, data availability spans from 1995 to 2021, with USWAN demonstrating the most extensive coverage and data sources like POMME 15 (2014–2018) and BPE (2015–2020) offer shorter durations. Therapeutic classes such as antiemetics and antinauseants (A04A), antiepileptics (N03A), antipsychotics (N05A), antidepressants (N06A), and drugs used in diabetes (A10) are consistently available across most DAPs. However, drugs such as antihypertensives (C02) are missing in all DAPs and are present only in USWAN.

Cardiovascular-related therapeutic classes, including diuretics (C03), betablockers (C07), calcium blockers (C08), and agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09), are broadly represented, with the latter showing complete coverage across all DAPs. Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02) and antibacterials for systemic use (J01) exhibit comprehensive inclusion, while antivirals (J05) and endocrine therapy (L02) show slight variability.

Muscle relaxants (M03), immunosuppressants (L04), and drugs for obstructive airway diseases (R03) display high representation across data sources, while other nervous system drugs (N07) and anti-Parkinson drugs (N04) have less consistent availability, as seen in CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15. Temporal coverage within DAPs highlights intermittent or specialized availability for some therapeutic classes, such as antineoplastic agents (L01) and endocrine therapy (L02) in CHUT data sources. THL and USWAN primarily provide count data for the anatomical main group of medicinal products shown in table 15. While USWAN offers information on the availability of the medicinal products listed in [Table 15](#), it does not specify the time span of availability. Both datasets demonstrate extensive coverage, spanning 1995–2019 for THL and 1996–2020 for USWAN. USWAN includes data for all medicinal product groups of interest, whereas THL lacks data on drugs used in the respiratory system.

Data on vaccines was available only for UOSL, BPE, SIDIAP, ARS, and USWAN. ARS and USWAN showed the most extensive coverage on vaccine data spanning from 1995 to 2021. Similar availability was provided from BPE (2015–2020) and SIDIAP (2014–2021).

Table 14. Presence of medicinal products of interest in the MEDICINES and VACCINES tables by therapeutic class of the data instance and temporal patterns

	Data Access Providers										
	UOSL	CHUT EFEM- ERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARM O	RDRU_FI SABIO	SIDIAP	FERR	ARS	USWAN ^s
Overall medicinal products data time span	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2002-2020, 2004-2021, 2008-2021	1995-2021
Antiemetics and antinauseants (A04A)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Antiepileptics (N03A)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2002-2021	
Antipsychotics (N05A)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2011, 2012-2013**, 2014-2020	2014-2017	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Antidepressants (N06A)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2017, 2018**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Drugs used in Diabetes (A10)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Antihypertensives (C02)											
Availability	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
Diuretics (C03)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2018, 2019**	2014**, 2015-2016, 2017**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Betablockers (C07)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2017, 2018**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Calcium blockers (C08)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009**, 2010-2015, 2016-2018, 2019**	2014-2016	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system (C09)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2007, 2008**, 2009-2019	2009-2012, 2013**, 2014, 2015**, 2016-2020	2014-2015, 2016**, 2017	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2002**, 2003-2021	
Corticosteroids for systemic use (H02)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Antibacterials for systemic use (J01)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2002**, 2003-2021	
Antivirals for systemic use (J05)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Vaccines (J07)											
Availability	+	N/A	N/A	N/A	+	N/A	N/A	+	N/A	+	+
Years	2004-2021				2015-2020			2014-2021		1995-1996**, 1997-2021	
Antineoplastic agents (L01)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004**, 2005-1010, 2011**, 2012-2017, 2019**	2009-2020	2014-2018**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Endocrine therapy (L02)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004**, 2005-2021	2004-2007, 2008**, 2009-2019	2009-2010, 2017-2018**, 2019-2020	2014-2015, 2018**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	
Immunostimulants (L03)											
Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Years	2004-2021	2004-2006, 2007-2008**, 2009-2017, 2018**, 2019	2009**, 2010, 2011**, 2013**	2014**, 2015	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2020	2009-2020	2003-2021
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Immunosuppressants (L04)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004**, 2005-2019	2009-2020	2014-2016, 2017**, 2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	

Muscle relaxants (M03)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2017, 2018-2019**	2009-2011, 2013**, 2015**	2014-2015, 2016-2017**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	

Analgesics (N02)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004-2021	2004-2019	2009-2020	2014-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	

Anti-Parkinson drugs (N04)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
Years	2005-2021	2004-2018, 2019**	2009-2010, 2013**	2014**, 2015-2018	2015-2020	2009-2019		2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	

Other nervous system drugs (N07)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004**, 2005-2021	2004-2019	2009-2011, 2013-2014**, 2017-2018**, 2019	2014-2016, 2017**	2015-2020	2009-2019	2013-2021	2014-2021	2009-2020	2003-2021	

2019,
2020**

Drugs for obstructive airway diseases (R03)

Availability	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Years	2004- 2021	2004- 2019	2009- 2020	2014- 2018	2015- 2020		2013- 2021	2014- 2021	2009- 2020	2003- 2021	

Table 15. Presence of medicinal products of interest in the MEDICINES and VACCINES tables by the main anatomical group of the data instance and temporal patterns

	Data Access Providers	
	THL	USWAN
Overall medicinal products data time span	1996-2019	1995-2021
Alimentary tract and metabolism (A)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996-2019	1995-2021
Cardiovascular system (C)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996-2019	1995-2021
Systemic hormonal preparations excluding sex hormones and insulins (H)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996**, 1997-2019	1995-2021
Ant infectives for systemic use (J)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996-2019	1995-2021
Antineoplastic and immunomodulating agents (L)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996**, 1997-2019	1996-2021
Musco-skeletal system (M)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996-2019	1995-2021
Nervous system (N)		
Availability	+	+
Years	1996-2019	1995-2021
Respiratory system (R)		
Availability	-	+
Years	N/A	1995-2021

N/A not available

3.4.8 Completeness of medicinal products and vaccine data

We provide in [Table 16](#) the assessment of missing data in medication and vaccine records across DAPs. For MEDICINES, missing indication codes when indication vocabulary was present were observed only in PHARMO (20,906,955 records, 35.4%) and THL (2,059,423 records, 100%), while other UOSL showed no missing data for this variable. Due to complete missingness of indication code vocabulary in CHUT data sources, RDRU_FISABIO, SIDIAP, FERR, ARS and USWAN this indicator cannot be calculated.

Missing prescriber specialty was most prominent in UOSL, with 59.4% of its 128,809,527 records missing this information. Other DAPs with missing data for this indicator included CHUT EFEMERIS (0.08%) and CHUT POMME 10 (0.004%). In contrast, THL and USWAN showed complete missingness (100%) for this variable. Records with missing numbers of dispensed medicinal products were prevalent in CHUT EFEMERIS (41.6%) and PHARMO (46.6%), whereas most other DAPs such as UOSL, CHUT POMME 15, BPE, SIDIAP, FERR, ARS, and THL had no missing data.

Missing data regarding the number of prescribed medicinal products per day was a pervasive issue, with complete missingness (100%) reported for BPE, FERR, ARS, THL, and USWAN, among others. Similarly, PHARMO exhibited a high level of missing data (58.9%). The missingness of prescribed units when prescribed medicinal

products per day was observed only in PHARMO (41.1%), while for most data sources this assessment could not be performed due to complete missingness of the number of prescribed medicinal products per day.

For VACCINES, missing vaccine types were observed universally across UOSL, BPE, ARS, and USWAN, all reporting 100% missingness. Missing vaccine doses mirrored this pattern, with the same DAPs showing complete missingness for this indicator. Regarding vaccine manufacturers, UOSL and USWAN reported 100% missingness, while SIDIAP exhibited 8.3% missing data for this variable.

Table 16. Completeness of medication and vaccine data

Indicator	Data Access Providers												
	UOSL	CHUT EFEM-ERIS	CHUT POMME 10	CHUT POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FI SABIO	SIDIAP	FERR	ARS	CNR	THL	USWAN
MEDICINES													
Missing indication code when indication vocabulary is present													
Number of records (N, %)	0 (0%)	-	-	-	-	20906955 (35.4%)	-	-	-	-	-	2059423 (100%)	-
Missing prescriber specialty when prescriber specialty vocabulary is present													
Number of records (N, %)	128809527 (59.4%)	1670 (0.08%)	50 (0.004%)	0 (0%)	13072950 (3.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	-	-	-	-	2059423 (100%)	17259519 (3 (100%))
Records with missing number of dispensed medications													
Number of records (N, %)	0 (0%)	906238 (41.6%)	128105 (10.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	27543854 (46.6%)	195619 (0.54%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	295 (100%)	0 (0%)	17259519 (3 (100%))
Records with missing number of prescribed medications per day													
Number of records (N, %)	22839412 (10.5%)	2177849 (100%)	1184027 (100%)	611904 (100%)	351887590 (100%)	34832113 (58.9%)	195619 (0.54%)	14194726 (100%)	75106857 (100%)	146376909 (100%)	295 (100%)	2059423 (100%)	17259519 (3 (100%))
Missing prescribed unit when prescribed medication per day is present													
Number of records (N, %)	0 (0%)	-	-	-	-	24302404 (41.1%)	0 (0%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
VACCINES													
Missing vaccine type													
Number of records (N, %)	41277385 (100%)	N/A	N/A	N/A	8561617 (100%)	N/A	N/A	0 (0%)	N/A	5079508 (100%)	24 (100%)	N/A	832130 (100%)
Missing vaccine dose													
Number of records (N, %)	41277385 (100%)	N/A	N/A	N/A	8561617 (100%)	N/A	N/A	0 (0%)	N/A	0 (0%)	24 (100%)	N/A	832130 (100%)
Records vaccine manufacturer													
Number of records (N, %)	41277385 (100%)	N/A	N/A	N/A	8561617 (100%)	N/A	N/A	1370976 (8.3%)	N/A	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	N/A	832130 (100%)

3.4.9 Pregnancy data availability

In [Table 17](#) we present pregnancy-related information across various data sources. All data sources provided information on females of childbearing age (12–55 years old). For EFEMERIS, POMME 10, and POMME 15, the presence of this subpopulation was inferred from population size and follow-up data stratified by age bands, as specific counts were unavailable. Pregnancy episodes were identified in most DAPs, except for POMME 10 and POMME 15 (due to the nature of the data source which comprises only children), and no data was available for FERR and ARS. Medicines use in females of childbearing age was consistently available across all DAPs except for USWAN, while vaccine uptake data were present in UOSL, BPE (only vaccine dispensing in community pharmacies), SIDIAP, ARS, and unavailable in others such as CHUT data sources, PHARMO, and RDRU_FISABIO, among others. The most prominent medicines group in UOSL was drugs used in the nervous system (ATC code group N) for all years from 2005 to 2021, while in EFEMERIS it was drugs used in the alimentary tract and metabolism (ATC code group A).

Diagnostic information for females of childbearing age was widely reported, with data available for all DAPs except for THL and USWAN. These diagnoses were identified through rates of conditions of interest stratified by sex and age bands. Conditions such as breast cancer, epilepsy, and migraine were identified in BPE and PHARMO.

For detailed information on specified medicines, vaccine uptake or conditions of interest in females of childbearing age contact lead contributors.

Table 17. Pregnancy information across data sources

Indicator	Data Expert and Access Provider (DAP)												
	UOSL	EFEM-ERIS	POMME 10	POMME 15	BPE	PHARMO	RDRU_FIS ABIO	SIDIAP	FERR	CNR ^{\$}	ARS	THL	USWAN
Females of childbearing age (12 – 55 years old)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	N/A	+	+	+
Pregnancy episodes	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	N/A	N/A	N/A	+	+
Medication use in females of childbearing age**	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	N/A
Vaccine uptake in females of childbearing age**	+	N/A	N/A	N/A	+	N/A	N/A	+	N/A	-	+	N/A	N/A
Diagnostic information for females of childbearing age [^]	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	N/A	N/A

N/A - Not available

* No data on number of women of childbearing age was provided, but the presence of this subpopulation was confirmed from the distribution of population size and follow up stratified over age band.

**Identified through counts of medicinal products use and vaccine administration stratified by anatomical main group in females of childbearing age.

[^]Identified through rates of conditions of interest stratified over sex and age band.

^{\$}Age band 0-11 was the only age band present in the data.

3.4.10 Type of pregnancy records

In [Table 18](#), we show the presence of pregnancy code types and the presence of one type of pregnancy code or more than one type of pregnancy code in the study population.

In UOSL, 30.5% of women had one type of pregnancy code (423,666), and 11.1% (154,644) had more than one type. Pregnancy records primarily included end of pregnancy codes (72.2%) and interruption of pregnancy codes (27.7%). Similarly, CHUT EFEMERIS reported pregnancy codes predominantly for end of pregnancy (94%) and interruption pregnancy (6%), though counts of women with one or more types of codes were not available. For BPE, 11.5% of women had one type (255,318) and 2.7% (61,259) had more than one type, with 83.6% of records reflecting end of pregnancy and 16.4% interruption of pregnancy.

In PHARMO, 10.4% of women (58,501) had one type and 9.8% (55,116) had more than one. Pregnancy records spanned multiple types, including start of pregnancy (58.7%), interruption pregnancy (5.6%), ongoing pregnancy (12.7%), and end of pregnancy (23%). RDRU_FISABIO reported limited counts, with 0.5% of women (245) having one type and 0.1% (37) having more than one. Most records reflected ongoing pregnancy (75.6%) and end of pregnancy (24.4%).

SIDIAP showed 7.1% (134,173) of women with one type of pregnancy code and 12.1% (229,312) with more than one. Pregnancy records included start of pregnancy (17.8%), interruption pregnancy (7.5%), ongoing pregnancy (47.4%), and end of pregnancy (27.3%). THL had higher percentages, with 45.4% (470,864) having one type and 23.4% (242,163) having more than one. Records were for end of pregnancy (70.5%) and interruption pregnancy (29.5%).

Lastly, USWAN reported the highest proportion of women with one type of pregnancy code (63.8%, 442,441) and 5.9% (41,213) with more than one type. Most records reflected end of pregnancy (84.5%) and interruption pregnancy (5.4%).

For FERR, and ARS the data on pregnancy code presence and types were not available. CHUT POMME 10 and CHUT POMME 15 comprise only children, so no pregnancy codes are present.

Table 18. Details on pregnancy codes

DAP	Pregnancy code counts			
	One type of pregnancy code (N, %) *	More than one type of pregnancy code (N, %) *	Pregnancy code types**	Specific code by meaning (N, %)
UOSL	423666 (30.5)	154644 (11.1)	end of pregnancy interruption pregnancy	849120 (72.2) 326241 (27.7)
CHUT EFEMERIS	N/A	N/A	end of pregnancy interruption pregnancy	85160 (94) 5427 (6)
CHUT POMME 10	N/A	N/A	NA	
CHUT POMME 15	N/A	N/A	NA	
BPE	255318 (11.5)	61259 (2.7)	end of pregnancy interruption pregnancy	339306 (83.6) 66718 (16.4)
PHARMO	58501 (10.4)	55116 (9.8)	start of pregnancy interruption pregnancy ongoing pregnancy end of pregnancy	156850 (58.7) 14940 (5.6) 34063 (12.7) 61513 (23)
RDRU_FISABIO	245 (0.5)	37 (0.1%)	ongoing pregnancy end of pregnancy	241 (75.6) 78 (24.4)
SIDIAP	134173 (7.1)	229312 (12.1)	start of pregnancy interruption pregnancy ongoing pregnancy end of pregnancy	177194 (17.8) 74860 (7.5) 471602 (47.4) 270794 (27.3)
FERR	N/A	N/A	N/A	
CNR	N/A	N/A	N/A	
ARS	N/A	N/A	N/A	
THL	470864 (45.4)	242163 (23.4)	interruption pregnancy end of pregnancy	498339 (29.5) 1192839 (70.5)
USWAN	442441 (63.8)	41213 (5.9)	interruption pregnancy end of pregnancy	50064 (5.4) 860563 (84.5)

N/A – Not available NA – Not applicable

*The unit of observation is women. Denominator is total women in the study population.

**The unit of observation is pregnancy records. Denominator is total number of pregnancy records

4. Discussion

4.1 Principal findings

This deliverable describes the characterization of data sources that were made accessible by different DAPs for the ConcePTION project. DAPs converted their data in the ConcePTION CDM and ran the INSIGHT quality checks.¹ We provide evidence about the availability, conformance, and temporal plausibility of data across diverse data sources under the ConcePTION CDM, along with temporal patterns observed in the representation of conditions of interest, medications, vaccines and pregnancy-related information. Based on the output of 588 parameters we characterized the data that will support the fit for purpose assessment for drug utilization and safety studies in pregnancy.

The availability of CDM tables across DAPs demonstrated a high range of completeness (69-94%), with USWAN having the highest number of tables. The presence of essential tables such as EVENTS and MEDICINES which are critical for extracting information on conditions (i.e. events) and medicines, underscores the capabilities of all these data sources for drug utilization and safety studies.

Level 1 showed strong adherence to structural coherence across all DAPs, providing a solid foundation for multi-database studies as researchers can align and integrate data sources more easily, reducing preprocessing efforts and preventing errors. Mandatory variables, such as *person_id* and key date variables (e.g., *start_date_record*), were consistently present with *person_id* missing only in USWAN SURVEY OBSERVATIONS (4.1%) and PERSON RELATIONSHIPS (0.1%), which are particularly important for longitudinal studies that require tracking individuals over time and across healthcare encounters. Variables such as *presc_quantity_per_day* and *presc_duration_days* in MEDICINES exhibited complete missingness across most DAPs with exception for UOSL, PHARMO and RDRU_FISABIO limiting their use in drug utilization studies by preventing accurate estimation of daily medication use or hinder the calculation of defined-daily-dose (DDD) used in studies to compare medication use across populations.

Source populations represented in the data instances were subsets of the broader local source data. For instance, approximately 3.5 million subjects were included in the UOSL data instance compared to the 5.6 million individuals in the Norwegian population. Similarly, only 7.1 million of France's 67 million population were represented in the BPE data instance.²⁶ This disparity can be attributed to local data minimization requirements and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which mandate the collection and processing of data strictly limited to what is necessary for specific, explicit, and legitimate research purposes.

Level 3 revealed significant variability in demographic distributions, follow-up durations, and temporal coverage across the participating DAPs. While most data sources demonstrated extensive demographic and age coverage, certain datasets exhibited notable gaps. For instance, CHUT data sources lacked representation in specific age categories, such as 1–4 years, and limited availability in age bands like 5–14 and 55+. However, CHUT data instance is a cohort of pregnant women and their infants to study medication use and impact during pregnancy and short-term infant outcomes, thus underscoring the importance of aligning data instance characteristics with research objectives, process also known as fit-for-purpose assessment.³

Follow-up durations also varied substantially among the DAPs. ARS (initiated 01/01/1995), THL (initiated 01/01/1996), and USWAN (initiated 01/01/1996), provided extended temporal coverage spanning over two decades on their data instances., thus better suited for longitudinal studies and trend analyses, offering a robust foundation for investigating chronic conditions, long-term treatment outcomes, and temporal shifts in healthcare

patterns. Conversely, BPE (initiated 01/01/2015) and CHUT POMME data instances (initiated 01/06/2010) offered shorter follow-up durations. As mentioned previously, differences on follow-up durations might be as well as consequence of data minimization requirements or specific research requirements interpretation.²⁷

Most of the medicines of interest are available across DAPs with a few exceptions such as anti-Parkinson drugs (N04) in RDRU_FISABIO and drugs used in the respiratory system (R) in THL due to data minimization. Antihypertensive drugs (C02) are notably absent in most DAPs, except for USWAN. This limitation may significantly restrict the utility of these data sources for studies focusing on hypertension management, cardiovascular risk mitigation, and related health outcomes. Addressing temporal gaps and ensuring uniform representation across all therapeutic classes can support robust pharmacovigilance and drug safety assessments.

Information on females of childbearing age (12–55 years old) was available in most data instances. Moreover, medication use among females of childbearing age was mostly available, offering comprehensive insights into drug exposure during critical reproductive periods. This data is consistently available across DAPs, while USWAN did not provide this information due to privacy restrictions.

UOSL and THL stand out with high proportions of "end of pregnancy" codes (72.2% and 70.5%, respectively), while BPE offers detailed data on "interruption pregnancy" codes (16.4%). These datasets enable detailed evaluations of pregnancy outcomes, including live births, stillbirths, and terminations, as well as broader trends and complications. This richness in data fosters nuanced analyses and supports public health initiatives targeting maternal health. Nevertheless, variability in the proportion of women with pregnancy codes across DAPs introduces challenges in generalizability. For instance, RDRU_FISABIO and BPE report low proportions of women with pregnancy codes (0.5% and 11.5%, respectively) compared to USWAN (63.8%). This may be attributed to the characteristics of these data sources, where BPE includes data from the general population with no sex restrictions, while USWAN has a high proportion of females of childbearing age. In RDRU_FISABIO, the low capture of records can be due to missing vocabulary (ICD10ES) in the codelists, affecting data retrieval, as well as the data structure where most of the pregnancies come from the birth registry and are not captured through diagnostic codes.

4.2 Strengths and Limitations

The INSIGHT tool has been successfully implemented in various studies, both within the ConcePTION project (EUPAS43385, EUPAS43416, EUPAS43420, EUPAS43409, EUPAS43393) and elsewhere (EUPAS31095, EUPAS31001, EUPAS37273, EUPAS39226, EUPAS39438, EUPAS40317, EUPAS40404, EUPAS42504, EUPAS108847, EUPAS47708, EUPAS50117, EUPAS50123, EUPAS43593, EUPAS44424, EUPAS41725, EUPAS45461). It has also been adopted by several other EU based RWD research networks, including SIGMA, VAC4EU, and EU PE&PV.

Given the standardization to the ConcePTION CDM, there was no need for data instance reformatting, and more time was invested in analytical tasks which required a thorough documentation of the ETL design by DEAPs either by using single templates or FAIR catalogues. The presence of mandatory variables, even when completely missing, ensures that missing data can be appropriately documented and addressed in analyses. However, the missing analysis is currently unable to distinguish between missing at local data sources (never collected) and missing at extract-transform-load process. Future versions of INSIGHT should include a distinction between true error and issue from local source, making interpretation of results easier.

One major limitation observed was the misalignment of coding systems between filtering codelists and the data instances. This mismatch directly impacted the ability to generate an accurate characterization of conditions of interest. For example, ARS employed ICD9, while the filtering codelists used ICD9CM, leading to significant gaps in condition identification. Another example was USWAN where 'READ' codes were specified in the data instance and 'RCD' in the filtering codelists. Similarly, certain conditions, such as TOPFA or microcephaly, might not be captured appropriately by diagnostic codes alone, instead they are usually recorded (and validated) using birth registries and phenotyping algorithms. To be noted, rates on condition of interest should be interpreted with caution.

The consistent unavailability of the PRODUCTS table across DAPS might reflect issues with populating this table with available source data. Addressing knowledge gaps in less commonly populated tables such as PRODUCTS, INSTANCE, and PROCEDURES tables can improve data comprehensiveness as well as facilitate the construction of analytical pipelines. Clear guidelines and data validation processes should be emphasized to ensure logical consistency in future INSIGHT versions.

4.3 Implications and Recommendations for researchers

The following implications and recommendations are based on the data instance used for the ConCePTION project and may not necessarily reflect ongoing improvements in data quality and completeness of the data sources.

Data sources characteristics

The inclusion of data sources with regional (RDRU_FISABIO, SIDIAP, ARS, FERR) and national coverages (UOSL, THL, BPE, PHARMO), as well as the inclusion of different data banks (i.e., GP, pharmacy, registries) is likely to enhance the generalizability of findings. Most data instances have adequate follow-up time for younger and middle age groups, particularly between 30 to 49 years, ensuring power for analyses focused on these age bands. Given the restriction of THL and CHUT data instances to certain populations (i.e., pregnant women), their ability to conduct studies is therefore restricted to this population. SIDIAP, THL, and USWAN, provide long-term follow-up spanning decades, enabling the study of trends over time and the evaluation of long-term outcomes.

Availability of conditions of interest across instances showed considerable differences. The code lists applied by DAPs such as PHARMO, RDRU_FISABIO, FERR, THL, and USWAN included conditions such as anxiety, epilepsy, gestational diabetes, migraine, multiple sclerosis, and preeclampsia. However, UOSL, CHUT data sources, BPE, SIDIAP, and ARS used a broader code list that also included conditions like ADHD, autism, major congenital anomalies, neonatal death, and TOPFA. This discrepancy highlights the need for standardized filtering code lists to enable comparisons.

The lack of mandatory tables such as PROCEDURES (CHUT EFEMERIS and SIDIAP) and MEDICAL OBSERVATIONS in multiple instances (UOSL, CHUT data sources, BPE, RDRU_FISABIO and, THL) may impact studies requiring detailed procedural or observational data such laboratory test results, physiological measurements and lifestyle factors for general population (i.e., smoking, body mass index, and socio-economic status). Likewise, DAPs who hold a birth registry have information regarding lifestyle factor for pregnant women in the SURVEY_OBSERVATION table. Nonetheless, DAPs most likely have improved their data instance in response to further studies using the ConCePTION CDM.

Missing indication codes when indication vocabulary is complete, as seen in PHARMO (35.4%) and THL (100%) may lead to data gaps in research requiring precise medication usage context. Similar issues were identified for other critical variables, including prescriber specialty and dispensed medicinal products.

We recommend researchers using these data instances to apply the Structured Process to Identify Fit-For-Purpose Data (SPIFD) which can provide a systematic approach to assess whether data are fit for research question.³

ETL misspecifications

Although most DAPs adhered to temporal plausibility of events some exceptions were noted, particularly where events occurred outside the defined observation periods. For instance, 50% of records in the SURVEY ID table for PHARMO were recorded outside the respective observation periods. The reason of misspecification might lay during the ETL process wherein observation periods are constructed from different data banks each with different observation periods per subject, lack of linkage

between data banks, or using visit occurrence to construct observation periods. Consequently, valuable data points are missed in EVENTS or MEDICINES, leading to the underestimation of incidence rates, inaccurate exposure and outcome analyses.

An additional ETL misspecification is the “Parent less than 12 years old” check for THL, where 94.1% of records failed. This issue arose due to the incorrect assignment of identification variables, person ID and related ID. Rather than assigning the related ID to the mother’s ID, it was mistakenly linked to the child’s ID. Similarly, the person ID, which should have corresponded to the child, was instead assigned to the mother. This misalignment resulted in erroneous parent-child relationships, leading to the high failure rate in this check. We observed similar ETL misspecification when pregnancy-related conditions such as gestational diabetes was linked to children ID. This is rather an issue than an error, given that the record is prompt by the birth of the children rather than the pregnancy.

Non-compliance with date format standards in FERR and ARS can lead to errors during data import and analysis such as parsing errors in data pipelines when the number of characters rule is not followed (8 characters) or disruption of temporal analyses in case of invalid day, month or year values. Non-compliance impairs the ability to perform checks for logical and clinical consistency (Level 2), such as: ensuring events occur within observation periods or validating that birth dates precede all other records for a subject. Date-based calculations, such as age at condition of interest date, follow-up duration, or rate calculations, become unreliable without consistent date formats.

5. Conclusion

From appropriate CDM conversion to data source characterization, INSIGHT allowed for a standardized description of the several data sources participating in IMI-ConcePTION, particularly WP1 and WP7. Regarding data sources, they demonstrate high conformance to the ConcePTION CDM, particularly in schema structure, variable presence, and formatting. Essential CDM tables such as EVENTS and MEDICINES complied with minimal requirements to carry on studies on drug utilization and safety. However, the consistent absence of the MEDICAL OBSERVATION table restricted the availability of covariates such as body mass index or folic acid use. We observed several ETL misspecification such date format, creation of observation periods, and ID relation between children and mothers which need to be overcome during analytical stages if studies are carried out using these data instances. Given the inconsistent capture of diagnostic codes and the lack of phenotyping algorithms for complex diseases such as TOPFA, rates for conditions of interest should be interpreted with caution.

6. References

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As of the submission of this report, ARS Toscana has not yet completed its review of the document.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used GTP-3.5 to improve readability and language. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content.

7. Annex I Codelists for data characterization

Codelist used by FERR, RDRU_FISABIO, THL, PHARMO, UOSL and USWAN

event_definition	coding_system	codes
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICD10	M061, M050, M064, M06, M058, M068, M053, M069, M062, M051, M063, M052, M060, M05, M059
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICD10CM	M061, M0610, M0611, M0612, M0613, M0614, M0615, M0616, M0617, M0618, M0619, M050, M0500, M0501, M0502, M0503, M0504, M0505, M0506, M0507, M0508, M0509, M064, M0640, M0641, M0642, M0643, M0644, M0645, M0646, M0647, M0648, M0649, M06, M0587, M0582, M0584, M0585, M0586, M0581, M0583, M0589, M058A, M0580, M058, M0588, M068, M0680, M0681, M0682, M0683, M0684, M0685, M0686, M0687, M0688, M0689, M068A, M0567, M0562, M0564, M0565, M0566, M0561, M0563, M0569, M0560, M053, M0530, M0531, M0532, M0533, M0534, M0535, M0536, M0537, M0538, M0539, M05, M0577, M0572, M0574, M0575, M0576, M0571, M0573, M0579, M057A, M0570, M059, M0607, M0602, M0604, M0605, M0606, M0601, M0603, M0609, M060A, M0600, M0608, M069, M0690, M0691, M0692, M0693, M0694, M0695, M0696, M0697, M0698, M0699, M062, M0620, M0621, M0622, M0623, M0624, M0625, M0626, M0627, M0628, M0629, M051, M0510, M0511, M0512, M0513, M0514, M0515, M0516, M0517, M0518, M0519, M0547, M0542, M0544, M0545, M0546, M0541, M0543, M0549, M0540, M063, M0630, M0631, M0632, M0633, M0634, M0635, M0636, M0637, M0638, M0639, M0557, M0552, M0554, M0555, M0556, M0551, M0553, M0559, M0550, M052, M0520, M0521, M0522, M0523, M0524, M0525, M0526, M0527, M0528, M0529, M060, M0590, M0591, M0592, M0593, M0594, M0595, M0596, M0597, M0598, M0599
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICD10DA	M050, M068, M058, M06, M064, M063, M069, M051A, M051F, M051C, M053, M051E, M051B, M051D, M051, M062, M052, M060, M05, M059, M061
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICD9CM	7144, 7141, 7143, 71433, 7142, 7148, 71489, 71432, 71431, 71430, 7140, 714, 71481, 7149
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICPC	L88, L8801
Arthritis rheumatoid	ICPC2	L8804
Arthritis rheumatoid	MEDCODEID	1932121000006116, 125937016, 8187291000006113, 8187311000006112, 14011041000006114, 13709511000006115, 13709571000006112, 13709541000006116, 14177941000006118, 14177971000006114, 2530001000006117, 7282111000006119, 7276071000006116, 3527061011, 3527712017, 3527731011, 3527737010, 371261000000111, 11929781000006114, 2839291014, 3514955016, 1785221000006119, 311496011, 309816012, 251794010, 309829012, 309833017, 359310019, 309836013, 2472447010, 755441000006119, 309828016, 309824019, 309827014, 297641010, 13790221000006116, 123542016, 3709251000006117, 297544012, 12626381000006115, 12734381000006119, 3636541000006112, 889751000006116, 989331000006117, 889801000006111, 889781000006112, 989301000006113, 889771000006114, 989311000006111, 889761000006119, 989321000006115, 889821000006118, 889741000006118, 889811000006114, 889791000006110, 989291000006112, 168661000006110, 891581000006117, 891631000006119, 891611000006113, 891601000006110, 891591000006119, 891651000006114, 891641000006112, 891621000006117, 12717421000006111, 401537011, 12717431000006114, 891571000006115, 891661000006111, 2640821000000117, 116082011, 5721481000006110, 5721451000006119, 426510015, 889731000006111, 168751000006115, 2196791000000119, 8045661000006112, 257899015, 4596611000006113, 219021000000114, 8440041000006115, 8440051000006118, 8440071000006111, 1875561000006119, 2275501000000119, 8440031000006113, 8459501000006119, 1875591000006110, 2275671000000111, 1875601000006119, 2275711000000112, 1875611000006116, 2275751000000111, 1875571000006114, 2275831000000110, 1875581000006112, 2275791000000115, 168761000006118, 309791014, 309802019, 13709581000006110, 309787016, 162041000006117, 162051000006115, 4809101000006114, 309792019, 4809221000006114, 7099641000006113, 309798015, 162081000006111, 13605001000006117, 309800010, 13687681000006113, 3528264013, 8447181000006111, 12114051000006110, 13687691000006111, 162101000006115, 162111000006117, 5721431000006114, 309805017, 162131000006111, 13687701000006111, 3528262012, 3528266010, 8447281000006115, 12114061000006112, 13687711000006114, 162141000006118, 309789018, 309788014, 309790010, 309803012, 309804018, 7078501000006113, 162191000006110, 309794018, 2159844013, 1880371000006117, 16911000006114, 3514958019, 162231000006117, 8102191000006119, 359292012, 13677531000006119, 451461014, 149911000006117, 9357441000006116, 3901751000006115, 909191000006119, 312523013, 312518013, 312520011, 424981000006114, 312534011
Arthritis rheumatoid	RCD	N040, Xa3gP, XE1DU
Arthritis rheumatoid	RCD2	N040
Arthritis rheumatoid	SCTSPA	203746006, 69896004, 239791005, 156481008, 287010008, 267887009

Arthritis rheumatoid	SNOMEDCT_US	156471009, 69896004, 156481008, 287010008, 267887009, 201763001, 239791005, 201811002, 203746006
Breast cancer	ICD10	Z901, C506, C509, D05, D059, C501, D051, D050, C503, C505, C50, C500, D057, C508, C502, C504
Breast cancer	ICD10CM	Z9013, Z9012, Z9011, Z9010, D05, D051, D0512, D0511, D0510, D050, D0502, D0501, D0500, C506, C5061, C5062, C50612, C50622, C50611, C50621, C50619, C50629, C50, C509, C5091, C5092, C501, C5011, C5012, C50112, C50122, C50111, C50121, C50119, C50129, C503, C5031, C5032, C50312, C50322, C50311, C50321, C50319, C50329, C505, C5051, C5052, C50512, C50522, C50511, C50521, C50519, C50529, C500, C5001, C50012, C50022, C5002, C50011, C50021, C50019, C50029, C508, C5081, C5082, C50812, C50822, C50811, C50821, C50819, C50829, C50912, C50922, C50911, C50921, C50919, C50929, C502, C5021, C5022, C50212, C50222, C50211, C50221, C50219, C50229, C504, C5041, C5042, C50412, C50422, C50411, C50421, C50419, C50429, D058, D0582, D0581, D0580, C7981, D059, D0592, D0591, D0590
Breast cancer	ICD9CM	8548, 8544, 8546, 8542, 8535, 2330, 8524, 4022, 8525, 852, 8520, 8521, 1746, 1749, 1741, 174, 1743, 1745, 1740, 1748, 1742, 1744, 8536, 8534, 8522, 19881, 8523, 8547, 8543, 8545, 8541, 8533
Breast cancer	ICPC	X7601, X76
Breast cancer	ICPC2P	X76001
Breast cancer	MTHICD9	8542, 8547, 8521, 1725, 1748, 1749, 8543, 8545, 8534, 8541
Breast cancer	RCD2	B58y0, 71308, B830, 71312, 71361, B8301, B8300, B346, B341, B34, B34z, B343, B345, B340z, B340, B342, B344, 71300, 71302, 71309, 71311, 71310, 71305, 71306, 71304, 7130z, 7130, BB9G, BB90, ZV6G1, Byu6
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Breast cancer	SNOMEDCT_US	<p>865954003, 287800000, 172045004, 27865001, 12246641000119104, 71222002, 49355000, 81240005, 23500003, 359889000, 22246009, 154521006, 269595005, 254841008, 286896005, 92540005, 92541009, 92543007, 154636004, 189336000, 92562005, 92578007, 92579004, 92593006, 353591000119105, 92646008, 92647004, 92652009, 92665000, 92666004, 353631000119105, 92714001, 92777004, 92778009, 255068000, 254838004, 286897001, 286894008, 286893002, 286895009, 708921005, 447782002, 372096000, 716593008, 265054005, 274025005, 449106004, 311774002, 10371000132109, 773129000, 89367004, 438614004, 439499006, 1202019006, 440062005, 447107001, 440147006, 287456008, 443959005, 11377005, 737169005, 1201909000, 713502002, 274974008, 1149128008, 1149127003, 447310001, 447751001, 442830000, 446024004, 7231000179103, 7221000179100, 236901008, 28939002, 446017000, 445976006, 446735004, 235181002, 180050005, 62006009, 67579003, 89005003, 12986006, 6189002, 12708000, 29105006, 174334007, 174332006, 237394008, 6274000, 63429000, 67424009, 32256004, 300025007, 736465001, 118445002, 7151000179104, 447862008, 444182002, 442836006, 410555001, 63348002, 51994001, 125862001, 870629001, 14714006, 726491007, 41214003, 4539004, 27480002, 3326006, 446114009, 233401008, 81398000, 66361005, 300016001, 309695008, 447173003, 303840006, 230960003, 239348002, 428297005, 120231006, 75503001, 31075001, 230811007, 41180005, 42349006, 176481007, 447752008, 41393008, 432086003, 6535008, 252053007, 448460005, 336863008, 401107009, 432775006, 444230006, 443791002, 86033002, 387741004, 125863006, 230986008, 817000, 71579005, 447984009, 307857006, 265011000, 446510008, 700074001, 830035005, 830034009, 235253004, 770108008, 708884000, 446427003, 232567000, 239333008, 84736001, 239334002, 392033004, 20287004, 1179137002, 700072002, 447650007, 449095008, 1179139004, 713160003, 1179140002, 1179136006, 447966007, 449291005, 69990006, 390849007, 70163005, 448901001, 178099003, 178098006, 302459006, 178097001, 11227005, 178095009, 359892001, 79023002, 709116003, 448132001, 448133006, 67085004, 238364004, 238365003, 300030006, 57668004, 309723003, 708854008, 713168005, 86127008, 43426004, 66169000, 17056008, 81751006, 87055003, 230907002, 274069003, 10236001, 708639004, 236832005, 32783004, 172106007, 59687004, 233026009, 172111009, 72432009, 20486005, 23183008, 274068006, 446068002, 446802003, 438811009, 450668002, 450667007, 307616002, 301794000, 67418003, 234310009, 35968005, 39559009, 5621009, 85095002, 370611004, 439249005, 301889008, 46116005, 33507007, 307796007, 446106003, 450664000, 446872002, 63109005, 2407009, 177281002, 447362004, 446868001, 238299003, 302345000, 450804001, 236326007, 306966000,</p>

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Demyelination multiple sclerosis	Free_text	MSnarrow, MSbroad
Demyelination multiple sclerosis	ICD10	G35

Demyelination multiple sclerosis	ICD10CM	G35
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Demyelination multiple sclerosis	ICD9CM	340
Demyelination multiple sclerosis	ICPC	N86
Demyelination multiple sclerosis	ICPC2P	N86001, N86002
Demyelination multiple sclerosis	MEDCODEID	5006891000006112, 641211000000118, 5006901000006111, 7510741000006111, 297180018, 297179016, 2894411000006110, 641301000000114, 41398015, 5006911000006114, 7092351000006112, 7058051000006116, 7045281000006112, 983291000006110, 983311000006114, 983301000006111, 297181019, 695191000006119, 4769281000006110, 297177019, 2692565012, 7861151000006116, 1682241000006111, 5006921000006118, 2674605012, 1858501000006114, 226293100000117, 905781000006118, 908811000006112
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Demyelination multiple sclerosis	SNOMEDCT_US	230372003, 438511000, 18353007, 230373008, 16092000, 192929006, 192928003, 439567002, 766246000, 155023009, 247000007, 230374002, 192930001, 192926004, 192927008, 733028000, 1186728004, 428700003, 816984002, 724778008, 426373005, 425500002
Elective termination	Free_text	ELECTTERMnarrow
Elective termination	ICD10	O0489, O0480, O0486, O0736, O086, O0484, O0734, O081, O071, O082, Z332, O07, O0739, O0730, O072, O073, O074, O045, O070, O04, O046, O047, O048, O049, O041, O042, O040, O043, O044, O0483, O0733, O085, O05, O056, O057, O055, O058, O059, O051, O052, O050, O053, O054, O076, O077, O075, O078, O079, O0485, O0735, O0482, O0732, O0487, O0737, O0481, O083, O0731, O06, O066, O067, O065, O068, O069, O061, O062, O060, O063, O064, O0488, O0738, Z3711
Elective termination	ICD10CM	O0489, O0480, O0486, O0736, O086, O0484, O0734, O081, O071, O082, Z332, O07, O0739, O0730, O074, O072, O073, O045, O070, O04, O046, O047, O048, O049, O041, O042, O040, O043, O044, O0483, O0733, O085, O05, O056, O057, O055, O058, O059, O051, O052, O050, O053, O054, O076, O077, O075, O078, O079, O0485, O0735, O0482, O0732, O0487, O0737, O0481, O083, O0731, O06, O066, O067, O065, O068, O069, O061, O062, O060, O063, O064, O0488, O0738, Z3711
Elective termination	ICD10DA	O019A
Elective termination	ICD9CM	6392, 6391, 6396, 638, 6382, 6381, 6386, 6380, 6384, 6383, 6385, 6387, 6388, 6389, 636, 6362, 6361, 6366, 6360, 6364, 6363, 6365, 6367, 6368, 6369, 63622, 63621, 63620, 63612, 63611, 63610, 63662, 63661, 63660, 63602, 63601, 63600, 63642, 63641, 63640, 63632, 63631, 63630, 63652, 63651, 63650, 63672, 63671, 63670, 63682, 63681, 63680, 63692, 63691, 63690, 6393, 635, 6352, 6351, 6356, 6350, 6354, 6353, 6355, 6357, 6358, 6359, 63522, 63521, 63520, 63512, 63511, 63510, 63562, 63561, 63560, 63502, 63501, 63500, 63542, 63541, 63540, 63532, 63531, 63530, 63552, 63551, 63550, 63572, 63571, 63570, 63582, 63581, 63580, 63592, 63591, 63590, 6394, 6398, 6395, 637, 6372, 6371, 6376, 6370, 6374, 63729999999999999999, 6373, 6375, 6377, 6378, 6379, 63722, 63721, 63720, 63712, 63711, 63710, 63762, 63761, 63760, 63702, 63701, 63700, 63741999999999999999, 63742, 63741, 63740, 63732, 63731, 63730, 63752, 63751, 63750, 63772, 63771, 63770, 63782, 63781, 63780, 63792, 63791, 63790
Elective termination	ICPC	W83
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Elective termination	MTHICD9	6393, 63700
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Elective termination	SCTSPA	156079001, 1220657009, 1220652003, 1220653008, 1220656000, 1220651005, 1220648003, 1220645000, 1220641009, 267194005, 49416000, 59919008, 90645002, 707207004, 1220632004, 1220631006, 1220626009, 1220625008, 1220586000, 1220564001, 16101000119107, 200483009, 70317007, 18391007, 275423001, 49632008, 198763005, 61752008, 26743002, 86891002, 8996006, 38784004, 18684002, 74978008, 198751000, 198767006, 198737000, 198740000, 198738005, 198733001, 198735008, 198734007, 198739002, 198736009, 198741001, 198742008, 7802000, 198731004, 52660002, 198729008, 198723009, 698636009, 198726001, 198720007, 198724003, 198719001, 198718009, 198721006, 198725002, 198722004, 198727005, 27169005, 57734001, 58071009, 4576001, 111431001, 3634007, 21280005, 48433002, 111432008, 59859005, 198710002, 198714006, 198706000, 198705001, 198708004, 198707009, 198712005, 198709007, 198715007, 198691008, 198697007, 198701005, 198698002, 198693006, 198692001, 198695004, 198694000, 198699005, 198696003, 198702003, 198703008, 34500003, 198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 53638009, 200485002, 60330007, 391896006, 18302006, 267297005, 46101000119101, 363681007, 156096000, 198880003, 237013006, 70186003, 785867009, 198815000, 198814001, 198817008, 67042008, 13943000, 26623000, 29421008, 7822001, 5939002, 198811009, 198812002, 198807003, 198806007, 198809000, 198808008, 198810005, 271954000, 198878009, 198816004, 285409006, 57797005, 609453002, 609447002, 609449004, 609450004, 609452007, 609485004, 39406005, 302375005, 288045002, 267195006, 149998006, 287955003, 69302000, 386641000, 10455003, 1204037006, 184005004, 714812005, 609446006, 1204036002
Elective termination	SNM	F31600, U000205, F31690, F31720, P1755, F31670, F31740, P1500
Elective termination	SNOMEDCT_US	386639001, 70317007, 156079001, 267297005, 391897002, 60330007, 198763005, 1220657009, 1220652003, 1220653008, 1220656000, 1220651005, 1220648003, 1220645000, 1220641009, 267194005, 698636009, 198726001, 198727005, 198725002, 198720007, 198719001, 198724003, 198718009, 198722004, 198721006, 198723009, 46101000119101, 198730003, 1204036002, 198690009, 18391007, 237013006, 70186003, 785867009, 275423001, 156078009, 198873000, 49416000, 198817008, 59919008, 198815000, 198808008, 198807003, 198812002, 198806007, 198810005, 198816004, 198814001, 198809000, 198811009, 90645002, 271954000, 7822001, 26623000, 13943000, 5939002, 29421008, 67042008, 198878009, 18302006, 86891002, 198731004, 49632008, 38784004, 26743002, 18684002, 8996006, 61752008, 74978008, 7802000, 156077004, 198767006, 198751000, 707207004, 1220632004, 1220631006, 1220626009, 1220625008, 1220586000, 1220564001, 16101000119107, 198714006, 198715007, 198712005, 198707009, 198706000, 198705001, 198709007, 198708004, 198710002, 156075007, 267295002, 714812005, 609447002, 609449004, 609450004, 609452007, 609485004, 39406005, 111431001, 57734001, 3634007, 4576001, 27169005, 111432008, 48433002, 59859005, 21280005, 34500003, 198729008, 285409006, 149995009, 302375005, 156070002, 200480007, 363681007, 156096000, 198880003, 198860004, 267195006, 10455003, 152229008, 184005004, 1204037006, 149997001, 57797005, 69302000, 149998006, 287955003, 609446006, 386641000, 53638009, 198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 198742008, 198740000, 198734007, 198733001, 198738005, 198736009, 198741001, 198739002, 198735008, 198737000, 198703008, 198701005, 198694000, 198693006, 198698002, 198692001, 198696003, 198702003, 198699005, 198695004, 198697007, 200485002, 200483009
Epilepsy	ICD10	G40, G409, G403, G406, G400, G402, G401, G408, G404, G407, G405
Epilepsy	ICD10CM	G40A, G40, G409, G4090, G40901, G40909, G405, G403, G40B, G400, G402, G401, G408, G404
Epilepsy	ICD9CM	3459, 34591, 34590
Epilepsy	ICPC	N07, N88
Epilepsy	ICPC2EENG	N88
Epilepsy	ICPC2P	N07001, N88006, N07002, N07003, N88003
Epilepsy	MEDCODEID	2159218018, 2159220015, 2159219014, 1932071000006116, 3862731000006112, 504161016, 5231901000006116, 5231871000006116, 5231911000006118, 362161000006110, 1013171000006112, 1013181000006110, 1013191000006113, 7289921000006116, 5231721000006112, 478024019, 405571000006113, 4948491000006116, 4948501000006112, 2466801000000118, 3182921000006118, 3182931000006115, 8053261000006111, 2872771000006114, 73622018, 5007121000006118, 13686271000006111, 13686241000006115, 13491221000006117, 5007101000006111, 4769541000006119, 5007171000006117, 13493091000006112, 13493111000006115, 5300371000006115, 6369851000006112, 3210951000006110, 3323851000006114, 7277091000006117, 2598971000006115, 2159274014, 2564351000006115, 8024981000006113, 8025041000006119, 2564321000006112, 345345010, 13622561000006113, 2014871000006119, 1175991000000119,

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Epilepsy	RCD	<p>XM03i, X75Z3, X75Z5, X75Z6, X75Z1, X75Z2, X75Z4, X75ZD, X75Z7, X75Z9, X75Z0, F25, XE15a, F2544, XaE1j, F2503, F2502, F2512, F2514, XaC34, XaDbE, X75YR, XaE12, XEOrw, X75Z8, F2542, X75ZC, XaEHz, F2552, X75ZA, XM03h, F2555, R003z, R003, R0030, R0031, R0032, R003y, XM1Dy, Fyu51, Fyu50</p>
Epilepsy	RCD2	<p>F25, F25H, R003z, R003, R0032</p>

Epilepsy	SCTSPA	<p>768555009, 83752007, 79631006, 246549008, 246551007, 246552000, 246546001, 246548000, 246550008, 230438007, 764453009, 766044005, 838351006, 444229001, 246537007, 41119002, 308742005, 361268000, 361267005, 788417006, 230391003, 438156004, 41510006, 230397004, 230454005, 720519003, 8291000119107, 42365007, 187931000119106, 23374007, 765216006, 61927004, 771448004, 733623005, 784377008, 698021005, 773498006, 770898002, 44145005, 717225001, 230384001, 434551000124106, 434541000124109, 770405003, 15523002, 715425000, 230382002, 770622009, 765756007, 192990004, 38281008, 230410004, 230411000, 230387008, 230388003, 770623004, 770624005, 771141002, 230383007, 59754009, 722386009, 58895005, 49776008, 50866000, 230386004, 443410001, 39745004, 230405003, 230396008, 6208003, 246536003, 702753003, 433083002, 246542004, 407675009, 74737003, 51075009, 4103001, 230460005, 782772000, 87476004, 438113009, 2665008, 771142009, 230419003, 230416005, 230415009, 778063003, 230427007, 193021002, 773230003, 230453004, 721088003, 782737003, 191714002, 230399001, 230441003, 29963001, 246535004, 230429005, 733082001, 770431001, 773548008, 771469002, 230450001, 15938005, 198990007, 198991006, 69909000, 237283007, 198992004, 303063000, 198993009, 10752641000119102, 426634003, 241006, 84757009, 442481002, 724988000, 724992007, 724991000, 724989008, 724787004, 724990004, 724549005, 860806007, 724789001, 860815000, 724786008, 724785007, 322112361000132104, 10750951000119106, 100941000119100, 733195008, 733032006, 230435005, 230439004, 230414008, 733031004, 422513000, 193004006, 73706008, 82381000119103, 723125008, 726702005, 313307000, 445095002, 192982004, 192981006, 192991000, 192993002, 68761002, 111498005, 230447004, 230432008, 764522009, 784342008, 784372002, 279953009, 783739005, 41497008, 725413002, 716706009, 276597004, 53521000119106, 765089003, 128612007, 449203004, 717276003, 230394006, 722762005, 89525009, 65120008, 19598007, 715629001, 699688008, 698760002, 192979009, 246545002, 4619009, 13973009, 52125007, 230407006, 763534009, 785726009, 308680003, 766932005, 73840001, 36803009, 230428002, 724274009, 715534008, 771223000, 770438007, 290871000119101, 773421009, 770755007, 68091000119102, 290741000119102, 84221000119101, 84231000119103, 84211000119108, 84201000119105, 119001000119108, 230433003, 307357004, 716278005, 230413002, 6204001, 109478007, 230425004, 230393000, 230418006, 230408001, 230381009, 278510009, 230390002, 230406002, 87185006, 784345005, 230444006, 770643005, 193003000, 723304001, 763802009, 267592003, 307356008, 19593003, 785303004, 773643006, 16873003, 230422001, 230421008, 192845009, 778047006, 230412007, 230426003, 37356005, 230443000, 770758009, 230445007, 230459000, 230457003, 230458008, 230401007, 1155717003, 442512002, 230404004, 87095001, 230400008, 230398009, 763827002, 722110003, 763861000, 230403005, 773497001, 193009001, 192999003, 84171000119106, 84181000119109, 84161000119100, 84191000119107, 14401000119109, 20121000119105, 21391000119102, 29753000, 246544003, 42440009, 13847000, 60338000, 60317006, 723926008, 724672003, 724728006, 724671005, 766815007, 7033004, 246532001, 95208000, 237612000, 773699009, 702344008, 698764006, 698767004, 75023009, 698763000, 246531008, 778001003, 47391000119107, 789063000, 230389006, 782825008, 442511009, 770678005, 267581004, 783064000, 783055005, 783062001, 783139000, 763349002, 702326000, 361123003, 193002005, 9112001, 768473009, 724576005, 734434007, 230191005, 7689009, 767254005, 116401000119105, 307200007, 440443001, 79745005, 10701000119109, 422873003, 445355009, 425237009, 3371000119106, 441678004, 710046001, 422527005, 290881000119103, 698761003, 422724001, 698762005, 425054007, 425349008, 40816002, 230392005, 765093009, 18191000, 20544001, 230440002, 437871001, 246538002, 724670006, 735235000, 724669005, 724727001, 724668002, 137991000119103, 277130004, 246539005, 721207002, 371115001, 372441001, 371114002, 371107004, 371022006, 230455006, 723676007, 230437002, 771303004, 432354000, 246541006, 49644006, 117891000119100, 61484000, 59457001, 246540007, 7454002, 33941008, 246529004, 246528007, 82401000, 246533006, 72103000, 79348005, 423086004, 981000119108, 703150000, 723126009, 723127000, 230431001, 765170001, 193008009, 34601006, 703524005, 763632004, 53482009, 230456007, 290671000119100, 290691000119104, 29071000119101, 290681000119102, 290721000119108, 290761000119103, 291311000119108, 19334007, 413101007, 230395007, 230420009, 230417001, 71831005, 230430000, 780827006, 768666006, 193000002, 71587006, 763622006, 66264000, 51887003, 352818000, 54200006, 230452009, 230423006, 49255002, 246530009, 2198002, 39194005, 193010006, 14521008, 28055006, 230448009, 717223008, 719810000, 725163002, 206735004, 206732001, 206738002, 32631004, 91175000, 155045005, 267593008, 128613002</p>
Epilepsy	SNOMEDCT_US	<p>155036009, 768555009, 83752007, 79631006, 246549008, 246551007, 246552000, 246546001, 246548000, 246550008, 230438007, 764453009, 766044005, 838351006, 444229001, 246537007, 41119002, 308742005, 361268000, 361267005, 788417006, 230391003, 438156004, 41510006, 230397004, 230454005, 720519003, 8291000119107, 42365007, 267698007, 187931000119106, 23374007, 765216006, 61927004, 771448004, 733623005, 784377008, 698021005, 773498006, 770898002, 44145005, 717225001, 230384001, 434551000124106, 434541000124109, 770405003, 15523002, 715425000, 230382002, 770622009, 765756007, 192990004, 38281008, 230410004, 230411000, 230387008, 230388003, 770623004, 770624005, 771141002, 230383007, 59754009, 722386009, 58895005, 49776008, 50866000, 230386004, 443410001, 39745004, 230405003, 230396008, 6208003, 246536003, 702753003, 433083002, 246542004, 407675009, 74737003, 51075009, 4103001, 230460005, 782772000, 32631004, 87476004, 438113009, 2665008, 771142009, 230419003, 230416005, 230415009, 778063003, 230427007, 193021002, 773230003, 230453004, 721088003, 782737003, 191714002, 230399001, 230441003, 29963001, 246535004, 246545002, 230429005, 733082001, 770431001, 773548008, 771469002, 230450001, 15938005, 198990007, 198991006, 69909000, 237283007, 198992004, 303063000, 198993009, 10752641000119102, 426634003, 241006, 84757009, 155045005, 193026007, 267593008, 442481002, 724988000, 724992007, 724991000, 724989008,</p>

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Fetal growth restriction	Free_text	FGRnarrow, FGRbroad
Fetal growth restriction	ICD10	O3651, O3659, O365, O410, O4101, O4102, O4103, O4100
Fetal growth restriction	ICD10CM	O3651, O3659, O365, O410, O4101, O4102, O4103, O4100, O4100X1, O4100X2, O4100X3, O4100X4, O4100X5, O4100X0, O4100X9, O43891, O43892, O43893, O43899, O4389
Fetal growth restriction	ICD9CM	6580, 65803, 65800, 6565, 65653, 65650
Fetal growth restriction	MDR	10069150, 10077582, 10010163, 10070532, 10054746, 10016497, 10016498, 10016499, 10016500, 10016502, 10016504, 10016505, 10016507, 10053700, 10016862, 10016521, 10070531, 10016857, 10055695, 10055696, 10055697, 10055698, 10055700, 10055702, 10055703, 10055705, 10016865, 10048488, 10048489, 10022819, 10071034, 10030289, 10030293, 10036150, 10036153, 10055708, 10055706, 10041042
Fetal growth restriction	MTHICD9	6565, 65800, 65650
Fetal growth restriction	RCD	Xa09R, Xa09P, X70Er, XE1eV, Q102, Q101, Q100, Xa09Q, L514, L280, L280z, L2800, L2802, XE1eU, Xa09S
Fetal growth restriction	RCD2	Q10z, L514, L280, L280z, L2800, Q10
Fetal growth restriction	SCTSPA	91849001, 276606009, 722835006, 724853001, 840448004, 470751005, 470750006, 431265009, 206164002, 268245001, 64177003, 189445003, 713192002, 199654008, 54213000, 267258002, 763717004, 276607000, 722525006, 473420003, 276608005, 276604007, 200474004, 3554000, 397949005, 18471004, 237292005, 398276003, 59566000, 199652007, 199656005, 268815007, 22033007
Fetal growth restriction	SNM	F33710, M29440
Fetal growth restriction	SNOMEDCT_US	91849001, 276606009, 722835006, 724853001, 840448004, 470751005, 470750006, 276604007, 22033007, 206166000, 268815007, 431265009, 206164002, 268245001, 156185006, 267337006,

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Gestational diabetes	Free_text	GESTDIABnarrow, GESTDIABbroad
Gestational diabetes	ICD10	O244, O24, O249, O2441, O2491
Gestational diabetes	ICD10CM	O244, O24, O249, O2442, O24420, O24424, O24429, O2441, O24410, O24414, O24419, O2491, O24919
Gestational diabetes	ICD9CM	64883, 64880, 64803
Gestational diabetes	ICPC	W84
Gestational diabetes	ICPC2EENG	W85
Gestational diabetes	ICPC2P	W77004, W85001
Gestational diabetes	MDR	10000139, 10012598, 10012606, 10012624, 10018209, 10018210
Gestational diabetes	MTHICD9	64883, 64880, 64803
Gestational diabetes	RCD	L1808
Gestational diabetes	RCD2	L1808
Gestational diabetes	SCTSPA	11687002, 359964007, 10753491000119101, 75022004, 46894009, 40801000119106
Gestational diabetes	SNM	D2403, D2410
Gestational diabetes	SNOMEDCT_US	11687002, 199232003, 237629002, 393568003, 10753491000119101, 75022004, 359964007
Low Birth Weight	ICD10	P07, P072, P070, P071, P073, O60, P059
Low Birth Weight	ICD10CM	P0702, P0703, P0701, P0700, P071, P070, P0714, P0715, P0716, P0717, P0718, P0710, R636
Low Birth Weight	ICD9CM	7832, 6442, 64421, 64420, 76504, 76505, 76506, 76507, 76508, 76502, 76503, 76501, 7649, 76494, 76495, 76496, 76497, 76498, 76499, 76492, 76493, 76491, 76490, 7640, 76404, 76406, 76407, 76408, 76409, 76402, 76403, 76401, 76400, 76405, 78321, 7651, 76514, 76515, 76516, 76517, 76518, 76519, 76512, 76513, 76511, 76510, 78322
Low Birth Weight	ICPC2EENG	T10
Low Birth Weight	ICPC2P	T10013, W84015, A94012, T08006, T29022
Low Birth Weight	MTHICD9	64420, 76490, 7640, 7649, 76405, 76406, 76408, 76510
Low Birth Weight	RCD2	L142z, Q10z, L2651, R0348, Qyu10, Qyu11
Low Birth Weight	SCTSPA	401180009, 722959000, 722960005, 276606009, 722835006, 276609002, 268868001, 723918000, 723917005, 206161005, 38206000, 276658003, 276612004, 206164002, 276614003, 7293009, 276613009, 129599004, 64177003, 189445003, 276616001, 717931007, 717932000, 771507004, 771299009, 724489002, 724488005, 10761141000119107, 10761191000119104, 10761241000119104, 10761341000119105, 698716002, 698717006, 717933005, 276615002, 723920002, 723919008, 267258002, 199612005, 276607000, 722525006, 61294007, 735540007, 762492001, 762491008, 762490009, 276611006, 206620009, 206621008, 276610007, 248342006, 46703003, 12064008, 270496001, 199059002, 22601002, 260361001, 60861008, 282020008, 49550006, 310538001, 4886009, 268815007, 22033007, 276617005
Low Birth Weight	SNM	F01704, F33710, F35070, F31570
Low Birth Weight	SNOMEDCT_US	401180009, 722959000, 722960005, 276606009, 722835006, 147106008, 169873003, 310538001, 276609002, 268868001, 723918000, 723917005, 199056009, 206161005, 270496001, 199059002, 38206000, 60861008, 276658003, 206174004, 276612004, 22033007, 206166000, 268815007, 206164002, 276614003, 276617005, 7293009, 276613009, 12064008, 46703003, 276605008, 156185006, 267337006, 129599004, 22601002, 64177003, 189445003, 276616001, 206172000, 276610007, 717931007, 717932000, 771507004, 4886009, 282020008, 49550006, 771299009, 724489002, 724488005, 10761141000119107, 10761191000119104, 10761241000119104, 10761341000119105,

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Maternal death	Free_text	MATERNALDEATHnarrow
Maternal death	ICD10	O96, O97, P016, O95
Maternal death	ICD10CM	O96, O97, P016, O95
Maternal death	ICD9CM	7616
Maternal death	RCD2	13M8, Q016, 22JZ
Maternal death	SCTSPA	200578004, 268799007, 53035006, 200155004, 160962004, 59283008, 237358009, 200156003
Maternal death	SNOMEDCT_US	200155004, 200156003, 138279005, 160962004, 237358009, 268799007, 53035006, 206051001, 59283008, 237359001, 200157007, 200578004
Microcephaly	Free_text	MICROCEPHALYnarrow, MICROCEPHALYbroad
Microcephaly	ICD10	Q000, Q999, Q049, Q751, Q750, Q91, Q02, Q917, F842, Q916
Microcephaly	ICD10CM	Q870, Q000, Q9351, Q999, Q8719, Q049, Q751, Q750, E744, Q91, Q02, Q917, F842, Q872, E7872, Q916
Microcephaly	ICD9CM	75555, 7400, 758, 7589, 7421, 7581
Microcephaly	ICPC2P	A90002, N85001, N85006, N85007
Microcephaly	MDR	10000590, 10083189, 10002317, 10002318, 10002320, 10049004, 10002943, 10048409, 10052634, 10008810, 10008814, 10008815, 10008824, 10009835, 10010270, 10010389, 10075892, 10077707, 10066946, 10049889, 10066950, 10067477, 10056354, 10052652, 10084106, 10084114, 10027532, 10027533, 10027534, 10068320, 10083972, 10067857, 10034115, 10048907, 10084109, 10077709, 10039000, 10039281, 10078573, 10044686
Microcephaly	MEDCODEID	129569012, 4161018, 4159010, 312877018, 2527721000006110
Microcephaly	MTHICD9	75555, 7429, 7560, 7581, 2701, 7421
Microcephaly	RCD	PKy63, PF552, XE1Lu, PF550, X004C, PKy60, P00z, P00, PKyz5, Xa0Zb, X40WK, PJ, PJz, PJzz, PKy61, P2y0, XE1Lz, PG04, PG01, P210, P211, P21z, P21, X20Ie, X78Ep, PJ1, X78Eo, XM00P, X40Tw, X005S, PKy73, X788u, PKy64, XM01S
Microcephaly	RCD2	PF552, PF550, PG01, F1306, PKy60, P00, P00z, PJ, PJz, PJzz, PKy61, P2y0, PG04, PKyz5, P210, P211, P21, P21z, PJ1, PJ1z, C3150, PKy73, PKy64, PKy63, PJ12, Eu842
Microcephaly	SCTSPA	205622008, 48069004, 268262006, 63661009, 205258009, 89369001, 203926007, 57148006, 204094009, 157023005, 205724000, 271611007, 1667003, 719819004, 109418001, 46683007, 124160001, 124593001, 74345006, 205729005, 78071008, 68528007, 204030002, 271572004, 234638009, 1829003, 204031003, 230312006, 76880004, 21634003, 21086008, 28861008, 40354009, 703535000, 254267009, 45582004, 57917004, 43929004, 57219006, 238049009, 21111006, 702431004, 409709004, 68618008, 737540008, 254268004
Microcephaly	SNM	M22560, M21510, D5182, U000360, N0CODE, D5500, D5632, D2013, M22650, D5012, D5187, M70150, M70290, M75100, D1650, M21300, M20230, D5023, D5027, D5047
Microcephaly	SNOMEDCT_US	205257004, 268262006, 63661009, 205258009, 48069004, 192836008, 230312006, 89369001, 203926007, 156887001, 268306009, 156885009, 76880004, 21634003, 156883002, 268305008, 238049009, 157018005, 157023005, 205724000, 409709004, 21086008, 205832003, 21111006, 205729005, 57148006, 204094009, 74345006, 205411004, 205414007, 57219006, 28861008, 40354009, 124593001, 124160001, 1667003, 702431004, 205413001, 205415008, 204029007, 78071008, 68528007, 204030002, 271572004, 1829003, 204031003, 156893009, 234638009, 703535000, 205621001, 254268004, 157021007, 268357008, 156995003, 205622008, 254267009, 268344000, 193045003, 46683007, 190761008, 192583003, 68618008, 157032007, 45582004, 109418001, 57917004, 271611007, 43929004, 737540008, 719819004
Migraine	ICD10	G440, G433, G43, G431, G430, G439, G438, G432
Migraine	ICD10CM	G43D, G43D1, G43D0, G4402, G44021, G44029, G437, G4371, G43711, G43719, G4370, G43701, G43709, G4404, G44041, G44049, G4400, G44001, G44009, R1115, G43A, G43A1, G43A0, G434, G4341, G43411, G43419, G4340, G43401, G43409, G4383, G43831, G43839, G4382, G43821, G43829, G43, G431, G4311, G43111, G43119, G4310, G43101, G43109, G430, G4301, G43011, G43019, G4300, G43001, G43009, G439, G4391, G43911, G43919, G4390, G43901, G43909, G43B, G43B1, G43B0, G438, G4381, G43811, G43819, G4380, G43801, G43809, G43C, G43C1, G43C0, G436, G4361, G43611, G43619, G4360, G43601, G43609, G435, G4351, G43511, G43519, G4350, G43501, G43509, G4483, G4453
Migraine	ICD9CM	33902, 3467, 34673, 34671, 34672, 34670, 33904, 33900, 3463, 34633, 34631, 34632, 34630, 3464, 34643, 34641, 34642, 34640, 346, 3460, 34603, 34601, 34602, 34600, 3461, 34613, 34611, 34612, 34610, 3469, 34693, 34691, 34692, 34690, 3468, 34683, 34681, 34682, 34680, 3466, 34663, 34661, 34662, 34660, 3465, 34653, 34651, 34652, 34650, 33983, 33943, 3462, 34623, 34621, 34622, 34620

Migraine	ICPC	N90, N89
Migraine	ICPC2P	N90001, N89001, N89002, N89003, N89004, N89005, N89006, N89010, N89007
Migraine	MTHICD9	33900, 3460, 3461, 5362, 3462, 3465
Migraine	RCD2	F2610, F2623, F2627, F260, F2620, F261, F261z, F26y3, J1620, F26y0, F26, F26z, F262z, F262, F2624, F26y1, F26y, F26yz, F2611, F26y2, Fyu53, Fyu5F
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Migraine	SNOMEDCT_US	95653008, 471661000124108, 145611000119107, 230466004, 230476001, 193027003, 83351003, 771304005, 232285008, 230473009, 230475002, 230474003, 124171000119105, 431601000124105, 437931000124100, 95657009, 95654002, 193947008, 55865003, 193031009, 193032002, 193034001, 155048007, 267699004, 193029000, 124001000119104, 193039006, 95658004, 154923002, 268772005, 196747007, 18773000, 230472004, 294031000119103, 95661003, 95656000, 443095000, 59292006, 95659007, 294001000119105, 425936006, 26150009, 23186000, 124081000119107, 155046006, 37796009, 198407008, 193041007, 230465000, 711545001, 193036004, 445322004, 193030005, 424699007, 4473006, 155047002, 230468003, 699314009, 230463007, 230462002, 56097005, 425007008, 232284007, 230464001, 95655001, 193033007, 49605003, 193037008, 193040008, 122731000119104, 191970005, 423894005, 425365009, 423683008, 423279000, 79267007, 193028008, 230467008, 193038003, 724429004, 711407000, 95660002, 427419006, 128187005, 194493009
Multifoetal pregnancy	ICD10	P505, P015, O30, O309, O301, O300, Z372
Multifoetal pregnancy	ICD10CM	O30, O308, O309, O3090, P015, O301, O3010, O300, O3003, O30031, O3000, O30009, Z372
Multifoetal pregnancy	ICD9CM	651, 7615, 6516, 65163, 65161, 65160, V272, 6511, 65111, 65110, 6510, 65100, 6519, 65190
Multifoetal pregnancy	ICPC2P	W84002, W84007
Multifoetal pregnancy	MTHICD9	7720, V272, 65111, 65110, 65100, 65190
Multifoetal pregnancy	RCD2	Q4101, Q015, Q015z, Q0150, Q0151, L2282, L2281, L228z, L2280, L228, L21, L21z, L21z0, L211, L2111, L211z, L2110, L210, L210z, L2100, 6333
Multifoetal pregnancy	SCTSPA	315960005, 266906006, 429187001, 445866007, 446810002, 206046007, 206048008, 64254006, 199321001, 65147003, 199316004, 199319006, 459168005, 459169002, 199320000, 199323003, 156154002, 199337007, 199341006, 199338002, 16356006, 199379001, 199382006, 199378009, 199380003, 199381004, 428511009, 237236005, 442478007, 75291008, 18001006, 206047003, 206050000, 313415001, 169828005, 72957006, 2256007, 288259000, 237321009, 21987001, 249110003, 71119005, 450825001, 91271004, 87663001
Multifoetal pregnancy	SNM	F31110, F30650, F31213, F31212, F35680, F35670
Multifoetal pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US	157053003, 288259000, 442478007, 429187001, 21987001, 237321009, 72957006, 87663001, 266906006, 137799001, 160404006, 71119005, 18001006, 206046007, 206048008, 75291008, 206050000, 206047003, 147182007, 169949007, 313415001, 450825001, 459168005, 459169002, 2256007, 156150006, 16356006, 156154002, 199337007, 199341006, 199338002, 199378009, 199380003, 199382006, 199379001, 199381004, 428511009, 249110003, 91271004, 156152003, 64254006, 199321001, 199323003, 199320000, 156151005, 65147003, 199319006, 199316004, 147059007, 169828005, 445866007, 446810002, 237236005, 315960005
Pain	ICD10	R521, J312, M774, R522, G564, G530, M543, G500
Pain	ICD10CM	G893, R3982, G8921, G894, G892, J312, G8922, R6884, M774, M7742, M7741, M7740, M7912, M7911, M7918, M7910, M791, G8929, G8928, M2555, M25552, M25551, M25559, G5763, G5762, G5761, G5760, G576, M5481, B0221, M541, M5412, M5413, M5416, M5417, M5411, M5418, M5410, M5414, M5415, M543, M5432, M5431, M5430, G500
Pain	ICD9CM	6206, 3382, 33821, 3384, 4721, 33822, 78492, 33829, 33828, 6255, 5311, 7292, 7243, 3501
Pain	ICPC2P	L18018, L18002, L02010, L03012, L29004, A01005, N29022, N03002, X99012, R83010, N94009, N99014, S70002, L86009, N92001
Pain	RCD2	N33A, K536, F3721, H121z, N2412, N2401, N2402, K585, E278, 1964, J0464, R00zC, Ryu70, F344, F5016, B7Fy1, F3560, N242, N2420, N2423, A5315, N2422, F3010, F301z

Pain	SCTSPA	<p>788891004, 762596000, 762594002, 762595001, 282743009, 735935009, 10181000119102, 879973007, 315241008, 413742003, 444746004, 14150005, 102557007, 63866002, 416562001, 86345004, 12400141000119100, 15749801000119100, 16002671000119100, 16013431000119100, 15743681000119100, 1084561000119100, 12400181000119100, 203508001, 69186005, 789494008, 111985007, 195798007, 51881000119109, 736428003, 134407002, 631000119102, 762602002, 11892641000119100, 431237007, 35074008, 736464002, 124171000119105, 274665008, 278860009, 762599007, 95657009, 762452003, 762598004, 762597009, 1121000119107, 674051000119103, 735936005, 735644008, 3061000119102, 235841007, 762454002, 431481001, 12400221000119100, 12400261000119100, 12400301000119100, 12400341000119100, 762451005, 129511000119105, 432615008, 133731000119108, 1162829009, 16002911000119100, 15743561000119100, 16002871000119100, 15743521000119100, 373621006, 193184006, 230575000, 95654002, 237067000, 279032003, 232406009, 133171000119105, 699694000, 98611000119104, 230477005, 109771000119103, 762590006, 762592003, 762591005, 762593008, 762589002, 1197734000, 426135001, 441711008, 129501000119107, 782661001, 762604001, 762605000, 136791000119103, 90979004, 232405008, 16580691000119100, 426628005, 737306007, 762601009, 762600005, 203509009, 128200000, 734987002, 734989004, 734988007, 734986006, 712537009, 734947007, 293951000119107, 293921000119104, 293931000119101, 293941000119105, 293961000119109, 293971000119103, 161977000, 571000119103, 294031000119103, 722982003, 24078009, 102481003, 443095000, 63491006, 792845002, 12236951000119100, 12237071000119100, 12237191000119100, 712826000, 314642004, 279048002, 29930001000004100, 43922008, 10085004, 726531007, 279041008, 113611000119100, 279030006, 41321000119101, 279036000, 303081002, 121021000119105, 301773003, 774135008, 774134007, 298731003, 710230000, 285339000, 39402007, 762354003, 785723001, 279047007, 240271006, 239166000, 195779005, 195780008, 714252004, 737305006, 371806006, 439469002, 271858001, 371810009, 371812001, 371808007, 371809004, 371811008, 38654001, 12336008, 1089561000119100, 1092171000119100, 449313005, 297217002, 20793008, 233819005, 16754391000119100, 704677002, 427419006, 95443002, 89638008, 89874002, 206796000, 207621000, 115491000119105, 82423001, 275488008, 12584003, 140004, 195783005, 274669002, 203102006, 156760009, 230648001, 307176005, 129612002, 112102006, 778003000, 16206741000119100, 16638401000119100, 16638321000119100, 15633361000119100, 76691009, 27830001, 11049006, 35635000, 762603007, 307177001, 193947008, 230539002, 291781000119103, 291761000119107, 291791000119100, 291771000119101, 408749000, 408750000, 23096007, 247387008, 1086061000119109, 4151000119102, 35496009, 247395007, 43763009, 424941009, 279059006, 230537000, 247392005, 247393000, 247389006, 713839007, 230597003, 247385000, 15968741000119100, 16839401000119100, 202794004, 46960006, 16864831000119100, 62195001, 46578006, 16206941000119100, 292251000119105, 292241000119108, 31490007, 95670000, 713278001, 16057351000119100, 292491000119101, 292531000119101, 292521000119104, 16057391000119100, 292481000119104, 866043000, 422136003, 14090001000004100, 247386004, 762607008, 247391003, 25416002, 279981003, 129179000, 17974002, 713847007, 2177002, 17111003, 713829001, 713831005, 713837009, 427972000, 54314008, 713320007, 1145217005, 1145215002, 1145240009, 1145220002, 1145244000, 1145223000, 420658009, 162039006, 42561004, 246602002, 1362002, 23056005, 230538005, 712857000, 247388003, 61830005, 112103001, 95669001, 175004, 247396008, 202796002, 2169001, 31681005, 129613007, 75983009, 66056001, 247398009, 103014001, 103015000, 6617009, 408047005, 21954000, 30085007, 16269008, 123253007, 82116008, 71760005, 322769008, 193090007, 156750000, 268011004, 203114003, 203115002, 288236006, 288235005, 288234009, 288237002, 288233003, 288238007, 288239004, 288240002, 16224871000119100, 82473003, 123255000, 203117005, 408751001</p>
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Preeclampsia	Free_text	PREECLAMPnarrow
Preeclampsia	ICD10	O15, O1502, O1503, O1500, O150, O159, O14, O12, O120, O1221, O1222, O1223, O1220, O1201, O1202, O1203, O1200, O122, O121, O1211, O1212, O1213, O1210, O142, O1422, O1423, O1420, O1402, O1403, O1400, O140, O149, O141, O1412, O1413, O1410, O1492, O1493, O1490
Preeclampsia	ICD10CM	O15, O151, O150, O1502, O1503, O1500, O159, O131, O132, O133, O139, O12, O120, O122, O1221, O1222, O1223, O1220, O1201, O1202, O1203, O1200, O121, O1211, O1212, O1213, O1210, O142, O1422, O1423, O1420, O140, O1404, O1402, O1403, O1400, O14, O149, O141, O1414, O1412, O1413, O1410, O1492, O1493, O1490, O13
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Preeclampsia	ICPC	W81
Preeclampsia	ICPC2EENG	W81
Preeclampsia	ICPC2P	W81003, W81004, W81008
Preeclampsia	MDR	10014129, 10014131, 10014132, 10070538, 10049058, 10027620, 10027623, 10035033, 10036485, 10074050, 10036492, 10036493, 10036557, 10036563, 10056505, 10040444, 10040447, 10044382, 10045638, 10046135
Preeclampsia	MTHICD9	64260, 64263, 6423, 64240, 6424, 6425, 64250, 64623, 64620
Preeclampsia	RCD	L1263, L126, L126z, L1260, XE2sh, L123z, L1230, X30Q3, XE0vr, XE0xy, Xa41E, XE0vs, L124z, L1240, XaBE0, X40C0, L125, Xa40P, X40By, L125z, L1250, X40C3, X40Bx, XE0vv, L162z, L1620
Preeclampsia	RCD2	L126, L1263, L126z, L1260, L123z, L1230, L16C0, L12A, L1240, L124z, L129, L12B, L125, L125z, L1250, L1236, L162z, L1620
Preeclampsia	SCTSPA	198973001, 156109003, 198979002, 15938005, 198992004, 198996001, 198989003, 6758009, 267203000, 199085003, 199080008, 156112000, 267307002, 308551004, 48194001, 288250001, 198981000, 48552006, 30354006, 198971004, 198964009, 237279007, 398254007, 198982007, 198987001, 41114007, 267200002, 198980004, 237281009, 46764007, 288201007, 34165000, 95605009
Preeclampsia	SNM	D2503, D2504, D2502, F70720
Preeclampsia	SNOMEDCT_US	46764007, 6758009, 156111007, 15938005, 198988006, 198996001, 198992004, 198994003, 198989003, 30354006, 308551004, 156125008, 199140001, 34165000, 95605009, 198969004, 156112000, 267307002, 48552006, 267305005, 157038006, 288250001, 198972006, 267200002, 198980004, 198973001, 156108006, 198978005, 41114007, 199009006, 237281009, 198981000, 156106005, 267306006, 398254007, 156109003, 198979002, 288201007, 156105009, 48194001, 199011002, 198987001, 198982007, 156110008, 199010001, 156107001, 198963003, 198970003, 237279007, 198971004, 198964009, 199079005, 267203000, 199085003, 199080008
Preterm delivery	ICD10	O60, O603, O6012, O6013, O6014, O6010, O601
Preterm delivery	ICD10CM	O603, O6012, O6013, O6014, O6010, O601

Preterm delivery	ICD9CM	6442, 64421, 64420, 65811
Preterm delivery	ICPC2EENG	A93
Preterm delivery	ICPC2P	A93007
Preterm delivery	MTHICD9	65811
Preterm delivery	RCD2	L142z, L2811
Preterm delivery	SCTSPA	59403008, 4886009, 724489002, 724488005, 270496001, 199059002, 367494004, 65588006, 282020008, 49550006, 199658006, 698716002, 6383007, 10761241000119104, 10761141000119107, 10761191000119104
Preterm delivery	SNOMEDCT_US	199056009, 270496001, 199059002, 367494004, 65588006, 59403008, 4886009, 282020008, 6383007, 49550006, 199658006, 724489002, 724488005, 10761141000119107, 10761191000119104, 698716002, 10761241000119104
Spontaneous abortion	Free_text	SPONTABOnarrow, SPONTABObroad
Spontaneous abortion	ICD10	O0386, O0336, O0389, O039, O0384, O0334, O081, O037, O035, O0339, O0383, O0333, O021, O05, O056, O057, O055, O058, O059, O051, O052, O050, O053, O054, O033, O0385, O0335, O0382, O0332, O0387, O0337, O0381, O0331, O03, O036, O038, O031, O032, O030, O034, O06, O066, O067, O065, O068, O069, O061, O062, O060, O063, O064, O0380, O0330, O0388, O0338
Spontaneous abortion	ICD10CM	O031, O0386, O0336, O0389, O039, O0384, O0334, O081, O032, O030, O035, O0339, O034, O0383, O0333, O021, O05, O056, O057, O055, O058, O059, O051, O052, O050, O053, O054, O038, O033, O0385, O0335, O0382, O0332, O0387, O0337, O0381, O0331, O03, O036, O037, O06, O066, O067, O065, O068, O069, O061, O062, O060, O063, O064, O0380, O0330, O0388, O0338
Spontaneous abortion	ICD9CM	6391, 632, 6463, 64633, 64631, 64630, 634, 6342, 6341, 6346, 6340, 6344, 6343, 6345, 6347, 6348, 6349, 63422, 63421, 63420, 63412, 63411, 63410, 63462, 63461, 63460, 63402, 63401, 63400, 63442, 63441, 63440, 63432, 63431, 63430, 63452, 63451, 63450, 63472, 63471, 63470, 63482, 63481, 63480, 63492, 63491, 63490, 637, 6372, 6371, 6376, 6370, 6374, 6373, 6375, 6377, 6378, 6379, 63722, 63721, 63720, 63712, 63711, 63710, 63762, 63761, 63760, 63702, 63701, 63700, 63742, 63741, 63740, 63732, 63731, 63730, 63752, 63751, 63750, 63772, 63771, 63770, 63782, 63781, 63780, 63792, 63791, 63790
Spontaneous abortion	ICPC	W82
Spontaneous abortion	ICPC2EENG	W82
Spontaneous abortion	ICPC2P	W82002, W82008, W82001, W82004, W82007
Spontaneous abortion	MTHICD9	64633, 64631, 63700
Spontaneous abortion	RCD	XE0xe, L042x, L0426, L0423, L0425, L041, XE0vh, L041x, L0416, L0414, L041y, L041w, L0413, XaBDd, L04, XE0ve, X40As, L0, L0z, XM1PB, L040x, L040y, L040w, L04z, L040z, L040, L071, L07, L070z, L071z, X40Aw, Lyu02
Spontaneous abortion	RCD2	L042z, L042, L041, L071z, L071, Lyu02
Spontaneous abortion	SCTSPA	156079001, 198657009, 198656000, 198663000, 198655001, 198660002, 198659007, 198661003, 16607004, 21737000, 109894007, 699949009, 111453004, 109895008, 275425008, 1148755000, 44216000, 1148484005, 1148619000, 1148941002, 1148942009, 1148943004, 29171003, 200483009, 70317007, 307733001, 69124005, 17369002, 156073000, 198665007, 198667004, 34270000, 43306002, 2781009, 10697004, 58990004, 13384007, 34614007, 19169002, 85116003, 156072005, 16863000, 413338003, 198652003, 198650006, 198647008, 198651005, 198648003, 198653008, 267191002, 198641009, 198640005, 198642002, 198643007, 23793007, 156074006, 198689000, 198631006, 198781008, 198792009, 6176008, 198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 267297005, 28379004, 363681007, 237242009, 156096000, 198880003, 8095007, 371374003, 81002003, 371375002, 237245006
Spontaneous abortion	SNOMEDCT_US	386639001, 70317007, 156071003, 267294003, 156079001, 267297005, 156073000, 198657009, 198656000, 198663000, 198655001, 198660002, 198659007, 198661003, 69124005, 198667004, 198665007, 16863000, 156072005, 413338003, 198650006, 198648003, 198647008, 198654002, 267191002, 198652003, 198653008, 198651005, 198682009, 307733001, 17369002, 58990004, 2781009, 43306002, 13384007, 10697004, 34270000, 19169002, 85116003, 34614007, 23793007, 156087000, 198616002, 267187007, 16607004, 6176008, 237242009, 156070002, 200480007, 363681007, 156096000, 198880003, 21737000, 109894007, 699949009, 111453004, 109895008, 275425008, 371374003, 81002003, 1148755000, 44216000, 371375002, 1148484005, 1148619000, 1148941002, 1148942009, 1148943004, 156074006, 198689000, 198631006, 29171003, 198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 198781008, 198792009, 198643007, 198641009, 198640005, 198642002, 237245006, 200483009
Stillbirth	Free_text	STILLBIRTHnarrow, STILLBIRTHbroad

Stillbirth	ICD10	O364, O021, Z377, O310, O3101, O3102, O3103, O3100, Z371, Z374, Z373
Stillbirth	ICD10CM	O310, O364, O021, Z377, O3101, O3102, O3103, O3100, Z371, Z374, Z373
Stillbirth	ICD9CM	6631, 66313, 66311, 6564, 65643, 65641, 65640, 632, 6632, 66323, 66321, 6633, 66333, 66331, 6516, 65163, 65160, 66383, 66381, 6638, V277, V271, V274, V273, 6460, 64603, 64601, 64600, 663, 66303, 66301, 6515, 65153, 65151, 65150, 6634, 66343, 66341, 6514, 65143, 65141, 65140, 6513, 65133, 65131, 65130, 6639, 6635, 66353, 66351, 6636, 66363, 66361
Stillbirth	ICPC	W93, W91, A95
Stillbirth	ICPC2EENG	A95, W91
Stillbirth	ICPC2P	W82007, A95001
Stillbirth	MDR	10000230, 10016480, 10016481, 10078992, 10016539, 10079001, 10016873, 10022814, 10022815, 10022816, 10076687, 10076697, 10027704, 10032272, 10033741, 10033742, 10033745, 10060443, 10076720, 10037708, 10037709, 10037710, 10037723, 10042062, 10042063, 10053173, 10044674, 10044677, 10044678, 10044680, 10045189, 10045190, 10045191, 10055710
Stillbirth	MTHICD9	6564, 65643, 65641, 65640, V277, V271, V274, V273, 64603, 64600, 6514
Stillbirth	RCD	X40E0, X40E5, XE0ve, L160, L1601, L160z, L1600, X70EM, 6332, X40E3, ZV276, ZV271, XaC1G
Stillbirth	RCD2	Q486, L264, L264z, L2640, L2641, Q4z, L160, L1601, L160z, L1600, 6332, Q48D
Stillbirth	SCTSPA	237361005, 445868008, 445862009, 446035009, 206259008, 206258000, 67313008, 44174001, 1762004, 17766007, 237362003, 199605001, 199607009, 237363008, 199608004, 83121003, 75697004, 315959000, 315964001, 309759009, 316756005, 16607004, 740597009, 762612009, 414249001, 198901003, 45513003, 38651009, 76358005, 445548006, 72543004, 90127001, 199069008, 199068000, 199071008, 169829002, 169830007, 237364002, 408796008, 713202001, 70112005, 7860005, 68509000, 35608009, 237366000, 28996007, 77814006, 237365001, 276506001, 276507005, 84122000, 7428005, 14022007, 399363000, 199606000, 199609007, 276505002, 391181005, 10588007, 276503009, 22514005, 38257001, 52942000, 84382006, 30165006, 3798002, 54650005, 39213008, 77714001, 762613004, 762614005, 169832004, 169834003, 169833009, 169827000
Stillbirth	SNM	F31660, F33820, M28140, M28110, M28130, F35250, F35260
Stillbirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199605001, 76358005, 237361005, 713202001, 77714001, 445548006, 276507005, 84122000, 7428005, 445868008, 445862009, 446035009, 206259008, 206258000, 67313008, 206574009, 44174001, 1762004, 17766007, 14022007, 237362003, 414249001, 90127001, 45513003, 199607009, 199609007, 237363008, 199606000, 199608004, 156184005, 399363000, 198901003, 237366000, 156087000, 198616002, 267187007, 16607004, 38651009, 156131006, 267314000, 199069008, 199071008, 199068000, 276503009, 10588007, 157167009, 206602000, 268887007, 147058004, 169827000, 206581002, 237364002, 72543004, 7860005, 740597009, 315964001, 315959000, 206583004, 309759009
Systemic lupus erythematosus	ICD10	L930, M320, L93, M328, L932, L931, M32, M321, M329
Systemic lupus erythematosus	ICD10CM	L930, M320, M3211, M3214, M3213, L93, M328, L932, M3219, M3212, L931, M32, M321, M3210, M329, M3215
Systemic lupus erythematosus	ICD10DA	L930, M320, L93, L930A, L932A, L932C, L932B, L932, M328, L931, M32, M329, M321
Systemic lupus erythematosus	ICD9CM	6954, 7100
Systemic lupus erythematosus	ICPC2P	L99056, L99065
Systemic lupus erythematosus	MEDCODEID	6681821000006113, 7359931000006118, 512234017, 5128101000006110, 5128081000006119, 309383019, 4805631000006111, 308701011, 6681971000006115, 3789511000006117, 92209015, 309405011, 660871000006118, 2667371000006113, 5124671000006119, 301721015, 4805601000006115, 719321000006114, 5418211000006113, 5284821000006110, 2768671000006114, 2267461000000115, 2267501000000115, 257962019, 308697013, 308709013, 308700012, 308704015, 308705019, 25612013, 308706018, 308707010, 1224370019, 1792431000000117, 114310015, 5140881000006110, 502127019, 2739071000006115, 5141731000006114, 18298019, 297639014, 158372014, 677561000006119, 297542011, 177301000006114, 5140921000006119, 3400601000006117, 3678391000006114, 359447015, 5557071000006111, 92208011, 309408013, 158442019, 1728151000006118, 7511501000006112, 114251000006118, 453243010, 109961000006114, 286303015, 88991000006119, 89011000006116, 312579010
Systemic lupus erythematosus	RCD	M154, M154z, N000z, N000
Systemic lupus erythematosus	RCD2	M154, M154z, N000z, N000
Systemic lupus erythematosus	SCTSPA	201439005, 200936003, 55464009, 200944003

Systemic lupus erythematosus	SNOMEDCT_US	200936003, 200944003, 156450004, 201435004, 55464009, 201439005
anxiety	ICD10	F400, F419, F411, F412, F41, F413, F408, F418, F410, F409, F40, F401, F402
anxiety	ICD10CM	F40241, F4322, F400, F4001, F4002, F4000, F40290, F4021, F419, F418, F411, F40210, F4023, F40240, F40230, F40242, F40243, F40231, F40233, F40232, F40220, F40291, F4521, F4022, F40218, F41, F413, F40228, F408, F40248, F4029, F40298, F410, F409, F40, F4024, F4011, F4010, F401, F402
anxiety	ICD9CM	30924, 30021, 30022, 29384, 30002, 30029, 3002, 30023
anxiety	MTHICD9	308, 300, 30742, 3002
anxiety	RCD2	E2924, E200, E2004, E2002, E2020, Eu41z, Eu41, Eu413, Eu40y, Eu410, Eu40, Eu40z
anxiety	SCTSPA	403592009, 58963008, 192038005, 192037000, 192042008, 67195008, 192039002, 698693004, 70691001, 191722009, 61569007, 1380006, 82415003, 75007009, 82339009, 102929005, 35429005, 11458009, 36646009, 5874002, 225644006, 277838008, 277831002, 247825008, 89225005, 247808006, 702535006, 277822002, 277824001, 277827008, 277833004, 225636006, 277828003, 277821009, 277834005, 277818007, 277829006, 225637002, 431432003, 225643000, 225642005, 225638007, 277839000, 277825000, 277823007, 277826004, 225635005, 277820005, 277819004, 247805009, 300895004, 34938008, 51493001, 724722007, 22621000119103, 724723002, 12398201000119100, 724708007, 724654009, 55967005, 762331007, 737341006, 762515000, 52910006, 10743001000119100, 37868008, 53467004, 109006, 788866004, 69479009, 231506008, 207363009, 198288003, 102925004, 90790003, 64165008, 37872007, 24109003, 238976006, 192611004, 191708009, 313182004, 426174008, 19887002, 129869000, 38617005, 111487009, 54746005, 231508009, 280947008, 724451007, 724449008, 723115003, 723093008, 1144992001, 723087000, 102920009, 247866008, 247869001, 247868009, 723119009, 723112000, 726403001, 724450008, 724448000, 34563004, 247818001, 722843001, 722842006, 1186988005, 102931001, 723086009, 723121004, 723120003, 102932008, 102919003, 762349007, 723113005, 723118001, 723117006, 724824002, 723114004, 723092003, 724879005, 735688001, 247854002, 81350009, 21897009, 62351001, 102930000, 110358001, 102918006, 70997004, 16265951000119100, 231504006, 61387006, 16266831000119100, 231501003, 428687006, 370567003, 231503000, 102915009, 102927007, 10586006, 13438001, 79823003, 225624000, 371631005, 35607004, 89948007, 8185002, 59923000, 63909006, 5509004, 76868007, 87798009, 11941006, 111491004, 34116005, 31781004, 32388005, 22230001, 3158007, 111490003, 63701002, 49564006, 24781009, 50983008, 19766004, 4932002, 82738004, 64060000, 76812003, 83631006, 1816003, 30059008, 38328002, 74010007, 61212007, 56576003, 72861004, 65064003, 82494000, 53956006, 43150009, 198280005, 300894000, 279622009, 386810004, 403593004, 313387002, 1004004007, 102924000, 191709001, 16265061000119100, 16265301000119100, 16264621000119100, 16264901000119100, 16264821000119100, 271947006, 1004005008, 1686006, 126943008, 11806006, 85061001, 80583007, 16266991000119100, 54587008, 231502005, 25501002, 191724005, 191725006, 191726007, 192044009, 238966008, 102913002, 102923006, 102928002, 102922001, 102921008, 110357006, 238965007, 34652008, 54307006, 192399006, 268714001, 192397005, 192403004, 192405006, 192400001, 192398000, 192393009, 48694002, 702883002, 386808001, 52039009, 191721002, 65673007, 38237000, 47372000, 197480006, 16265701000119100, 268630000
anxiety	SNOMEDCT_US	52039009, 403592009, 58963008, 192038005, 192037000, 67195008, 192039002, 47372000, 698693004, 70691001, 191722009, 61569007, 1380006, 82415003, 75007009, 82339009, 102929005, 35429005, 11458009, 36646009, 5874002, 38237000, 48694002, 225644006, 277838008, 277831002, 247825008, 89225005, 247814004, 247808006, 702535006, 277822002, 277824001, 277827008, 277833004, 225636006, 277828003, 277821009, 277834005, 277818007, 277829006, 225637002, 431432003, 225643000, 225642005, 225638007, 277839000, 277825000, 277823007, 277826004, 225635005, 277820005, 277819004, 247805009, 300895004, 191703000, 197480006, 34938008, 51493001, 724722007, 22621000119103, 724723002, 12398201000119100, 724708007, 724654009, 55967005, 762331007, 737341006, 762515000, 52910006, 471971000124108, 10743001000119100, 37868008, 53467004, 109006, 788866004, 69479009, 231506008, 207363009, 198288003, 162192002, 139476005, 102925004, 90790003, 64165008, 37872007, 24109003, 238976006, 192611004, 191708009, 313182004, 426174008, 19887002, 129869000, 38617005, 111487009, 268627007, 54746005, 280947008, 724451007, 724449008, 723115003, 723093008, 1144992001, 723087000, 102920009, 247866008, 247869001, 247868009, 723119009, 723112000, 726403001, 724450008, 724448000, 34563004, 247818001, 722843001, 722842006, 1186988005, 102931001, 723086009, 723121004, 723120003, 102932008, 102919003, 762349007, 723113005, 723118001, 723117006, 724824002, 723114004, 723092003, 724879005, 735688001, 247854002, 81350009, 191706008, 192401002, 21897009, 62351001, 102930000, 110358001, 16265701000119100, 436001000124105, 270472006, 102918006, 70997004, 16265951000119100, 231504006, 61387006, 16266831000119100, 702883002, 231501003, 370567003, 231503000, 102915009, 102927007, 10586006, 17496003, 192192006, 50026000, 13438001, 79823003, 286544004, 225624000, 371631005, 191705007, 35607004, 89948007, 8185002, 59923000, 63909006, 5509004, 76868007, 87798009, 11941006, 111491004, 34116005, 31781004, 32388005, 22230001, 3158007, 111490003, 63701002, 49564006, 24781009, 50983008, 19766004, 4932002, 82738004, 64060000, 76812003, 83631006, 1816003, 30059008, 38328002, 74010007, 61212007, 56576003, 72861004, 65064003, 82494000, 53956006, 43150009, 198280005, 300894000, 401010000, 279622009, 386808001, 191721002, 191720001, 154884005, 386810004, 65673007, 191734001, 268630000, 403593004, 313387002, 58535001, 1004004007, 102924000, 191709001,

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Codelist used by BPE, ARS, SIDIAP, CNR and CHUT

event_definition	coding_system	codes
ADHD	ICD10	F90, F90.0, F90.1, F90.8, F90.9
ADHD	ICD10CM	F90, F90.0, F90.1, F90.2, F90.8, F90.9
ADHD	ICD9	314, 314.0, 314.1, 314.2, 314.8, 314.9
ADHD	ICD9CM	314, 314.0, 314.00, 314.01, 314.1, 314.2, 314.8, 314.9
ADHD	MTHICD9	314.0, 314.00, 314.01, 314.1, 314.2, 314.8, 314.9
ADHD	RCD2	1P00, E2E, E2E0, E2E00, E2E01, E2E0z, E2E1, E2E2, E2Ey, E2Ez, Eu900, Eu902, Eu90y, Eu90z
ADHD	SNOMED	154940006, 154951006, 154952004, 192126003, 192127007, 192129005, 192130000, 192131001, 192132008, 192133003, 192134009, 192592000, 192593005, 192594004, 192595003, 192596002, 229715008, 229717000, 280996003, 31177006, 35253001, 389990003, 392751009, 393706000, 406506008, 42584006, 444613000, 44548000, 7461003
ADHD	SNOMEDCT_US	154940006, 154951006, 154952004, 192126003, 192127007, 192129005, 192130000, 192131001, 192132008, 192133003, 192134009, 192592000, 192593005, 192594004, 192595003, 192596002, 229715008, 229717000, 280996003, 31177006, 35253001, 389990003, 392751009, 393706000, 406506008, 42584006, 444613000, 44548000, 7461003
Autism	ICD10	F84.0
Autism	ICD10CM	F84.0
Autism	ICD9CM	299.0, 299.00, 299.01
Autism	MTHICD9	299.0, 299.00, 299.01
Autism	RCD2	E140, E1400, E1401, E140z
Autism	SNOMED	154878007, 191688000, 191689008, 191690004, 191691000, 192581001, 271450003, 34883005, 38763009, 408856003, 408857007, 43614003
Autism	SNOMEDCT_US	154878007, 191688000, 191689008, 191690004, 191691000, 192581001, 271450003, 34883005, 38763009, 408856003, 408857007, 43614003
Breast cancer	ICD10	C50, C50.0, C50.1, C50.2, C50.3, C50.4, C50.5, C50.6, C50.7, C50.8, C50.9, D05, D05.1, D05.9, Z90.1
Breast cancer	ICD10CM	C50, C50.11, C50.31, C50.41, C50.51, C50.61, C79.81, D05, D05.0, D05.1, D05.9, Z90.10, Z90.11, Z90.12, Z90.13
Breast cancer	ICD9	174, 174.0, 174.1, 174.2, 174.3, 174.4, 174.5, 174.6, 174.8, 174.9, 233.0, 238.3, 239.3
Breast cancer	ICD9CM	174, 174.0, 174.1, 174.2, 174.3, 174.4, 174.5, 174.6, 174.8, 174.9, 198.81, 233.0, 40.22, 85.2, 85.20, 85.22, 85.23, 85.25, 85.33, 85.34, 85.35, 85.36, 85.41, 85.42, 85.43, 85.44, 85.45, 85.46, 85.47, 85.48
Breast cancer	ICPC	X76
Breast cancer	RCD2	7130, 71300, 71302, 71304, 71305, 71306, 71308, 71309, 7130z, 71310, 71311, 71312, 71361, B34, B340, B340z, B341, B342, B343, B344, B345, B346, B34z, B58y0, B830, B8300, B8301, BB90, BB9G, BB9J, Byu6, ZV6G1
Breast cancer	SNOMED	109888004, 109889007, 116221009, 150298000, 150299008, 150300000, 150301001, 150302008, 150303003, 150304009, 150306006, 150323002, 154521006, 154636004, 17056008, 172039007, 172043006, 172045004, 172047007, 172049005, 188146000, 188147009, 188150007, 188151006, 188152004, 188153009, 188154003, 188155002, 188156001, 188161004, 189336000, 189337009, 189338004, 189705006, 190121004, 22418005, 22964006, 237370008, 24268003, 254837009, 269595005, 278053004, 27865001, 287654001, 2985005, 316517001, 317230007, 359728003, 359738008, 359740003, 367502008, 372064008, 373176000, 384723003, 392021009, 392022002, 395701007, 406505007, 408643008, 456903003, 52314009, 5835009, 58477004, 60633004, 64368001, 64837009, 66398006, 70183006, 71222002, 72258006, 72577009, 73359007, 76468001, 8115005, 86616005, 88764002, 93685009, 93745008, 93776002, 93796005, 94297009
Breast cancer	SNOMEDCT_US	109888004, 109889007, 116221009, 150298000, 150299008, 150300000, 150301001, 150302008, 150303003, 150304009, 150306006, 150323002, 154521006, 154636004, 17056008, 172039007, 172043006, 172045004, 172047007, 172049005, 188146000, 188147009, 188150007, 188151006, 188152004, 188153009, 188154003, 188155002, 188156001, 188161004, 189336000, 189337009, 189338004, 189705006, 190121004, 22418005, 22964006, 237370008, 24268003, 254837009, 269595005, 278053004, 27865001, 287654001, 2985005, 316517001, 317230007, 359728003, 359738008, 359740003, 367502008, 372064008, 373176000, 384723003, 392021009, 392022002, 395701007, 406505007, 408643008, 456903003, 52314009, 5835009, 58477004, 60633004, 64368001, 64837009, 66398006,

		70183006, 71222002, 72258006, 72577009, 73359007, 76468001, 8115005, 86616005, 88764002, 93685009, 93745008, 93776002, 93796005, 94297009
Depression	ICD10	F30.0, F30.1, F30.2, F30.3, F30.4, F30.5, F30.6, F30.7, F30.8, F30.9, F31.0, F31.1, F31.2, F31.3, F31.4, F31.5, F31.6, F31.7, F31.8, F31.9, F32, F32.0, F32.1, F32.2, F32.3, F32.4, F32.5, F32.6, F32.7, F32.8, F32.9, F33, F33.0, F33.1, F33.2, F33.3, F33.4, F33.5, F33.6, F33.7, F33.8, F33.9, F34, F34.0, F34.1, F34.2, F34.3, F34.4, F34.5, F34.6, F34.7, F34.8, F34.9, F35.0, F35.1, F35.2, F35.3, F35.4, F35.5, F35.6, F35.7, F35.8, F35.9, F36.0, F36.1, F36.2, F36.3, F36.4, F36.5, F36.6, F36.7, F36.8, F36.9, F37.0, F37.1, F37.2, F37.3, F37.4, F37.5, F37.6, F37.7, F37.8, F37.9, F38.0, F38.1, F38.2, F38.3, F38.4, F38.5, F38.6, F38.7, F38.8, F38.9, F39, F39.0, F39.1, F39.2, F39.3, F39.4, F39.5, F39.6, F39.7, F39.8, F39.9, F41.2, F92.0
Depression	ICD10CM	F30, F31, F32, F32.0, F32.1, F32.2, F32.3, F32.8, F32.9, F33, F33.1, F33.2, F33.3, F33.41, F33.9, F34, F34.1, F34.9, F35, F36, F37, F38, F39, F41.8, F53
Depression	ICD9	300.4, 296.1, 296.3, 296.4, 296.5, 296.6, 296.8, 296.9, 298.0, 311
Depression	ICD9CM	296, 296.2, 296.20, 296.21, 296.22, 296.23, 296.24, 296.3, 296.30, 296.31, 296.32, 296.33, 296.34, 296.35, 296.82, 296.90, 300.4, 301.12, 311
Depression	ICPC	P76
Depression	MTHICD9	292.84, 296.20, 296.21, 296.22, 296.23, 296.24, 296.30, 296.31, 296.32, 296.33, 296.34, 296.35, 296.90, 298.0, 300.4, 301.12, 311
Depression	RCD2	62T1, E02y3, E11, E112, E1120, E1121, E1122, E112z, E113, E1130, E1131, E1135, E113z, E118, E11y2, E11z2, E130, E135, E2003, E204, E2112, E2B, Eu3, Eu32, Eu320, Eu321, Eu322, Eu323, Eu326, Eu32y, Eu32z, Eu33, Eu331, Eu332, Eu333, Eu334, Eu33z, Eu34, Eu341, Eu34z, Eu3z
Depression	SNOMED	147016002, 154872008, 154873003, 154876006, 154889000, 154963001, 154964007, 154967000, 154969002, 15639000, 18818009, 191495003, 191580002, 191599006, 191600009, 191601008, 191602001, 191607007, 191608002, 191609005, 191610000, 191614009, 191617002, 191655007, 191659001, 191665001, 191676002, 191681006, 191707004, 191740008, 192078003, 192348001, 192366006, 192367002, 192368007, 192369004, 192370003, 192371004, 192372006, 192374007, 192376009, 192377000, 192378005, 192379002, 192381000, 192382007, 192384008, 192386005, 192391006, 192402009, 192475007, 192605002, 2,11E+13, 231498003, 231500002, 231504006, 231542000, 247803002, 268620009, 268621008, 268702009, 268704005, 268705006, 268706007, 268707003, 268708008, 268709000, 268710005, 268713007, 268750008, 268753005, 268756002, 277538003, 28475009, 300706003, 307537002, 310465006, 310497006, 33135002, 35489007, 36474008, 36923009, 41006004, 430852001, 442057004, 46206005, 58703003, 66344007, 68019004, 74421008, 76441001, 78667006, 79298009, 83458005, 871840004, 87414006, 9,49E+13
Depression	SNOMEDCT_US	147016002, 154872008, 154873003, 154876006, 154889000, 154963001, 154964007, 154967000, 154969002, 15639000, 18818009, 191495003, 191580002, 191599006, 191600009, 191601008, 191602001, 191607007, 191608002, 191609005, 191610000, 191614009, 191617002, 191655007, 191659001, 191665001, 191676002, 191681006, 191707004, 191740008, 192078003, 192348001, 192366006, 192367002, 192368007, 192369004, 192370003, 192371004, 192372006, 192374007, 192376009, 192377000, 192378005, 192379002, 192381000, 192382007, 192384008, 192386005, 192391006, 192402009, 192475007, 192605002, 2,11E+13, 231498003, 231500002, 231504006, 231542000, 247803002, 268620009, 268621008, 268702009, 268704005, 268705006, 268706007, 268707003, 268708008, 268709000, 268710005, 268713007, 268750008, 268753005, 268756002, 277538003, 28475009, 300706003, 307537002, 310465006, 310497006, 33135002, 35489007, 36474008, 36923009, 41006004, 430852001, 442057004, 46206005, 58703003, 66344007, 68019004, 74421008, 76441001, 78667006, 79298009, 83458005, 871840004, 87414006, 9,49E+13
Elective abortion	ICD10	O00.0, O00.1, O00.2, O00.3, O00.4, O00.5, O00.6, O00.7, O00.8, O00.9, O01.0, O01.1, O01.2, O01.3, O01.4, O01.5, O01.6, O01.7, O01.8, O01.9, O02.0, O02.1, O02.2, O02.3, O02.4, O02.5, O02.6, O02.7, O02.8, O02.9, O03.0, O03.1, O03.2, O03.3, O03.4, O03.5, O03.6, O03.7, O03.8, O03.9, O04.0, O04.1, O04.2, O04.3, O04.4, O04.5, O04.6, O04.7, O04.8, O04.9, O05.0, O05.1, O05.2, O05.3, O05.4, O05.5, O05.6, O05.7, O05.8, O05.9, O06, O06.0, O06.1, O06.2, O06.3, O06.4, O06.5, O06.6, O06.7, O06.8, O06.9, O07.0, O07.1, O07.2, O07.3, O07.4, O07.5, O07.6, O07.7, O07.8, O07.9, O08.0, O08.1, O08.2, O08.3, O08.4, O08.5, O08.6, O08.7, O08.8, O08.9, P96.4
Elective abortion	ICD10CM	O00, O01, O02, O03, O04, O05, O06, O07, O08
Elective abortion	ICD9	635, 635.0, 635.1, 635.2, 635.3, 635.4, 635.5, 635.6, 635.7, 635.8, 635.9, 636, 636.0, 636.1, 636.2, 636.3, 636.4, 636.5, 636.6, 636.7, 636.8, 636.9, 637, 637.0, 637.1, 637.2, 637.3, 637.4, 637.5, 637.6, 637.7, 637.8, 637.9, 779.6
Elective abortion	ICD9CM	635, 635.2, 635.20, 635.4, 635.40, 635.5, 635.50, 635.6, 635.60, 635.9, 635.90, 636, 636.9, 636.90, 637, 74.91, 75.0, 779.6
Elective abortion	ICPC	W83
Elective abortion	MTHICD9	74.91, 75.0, 779.6
Elective abortion	RCD2	7,00E+66, L0, L05, L050, L0500, L0502, L0504, L0505, L0506, L050y, L050z, L05z, L06, L060, L060y, L060z, L06z, L07, L070z, L097, L0z, Lyu03
Elective abortion	SNOMED	111431001, 1321008, 149996005, 156070002, 156075007, 156076008, 156077004, 156079001, 156096000, 18302006, 18391007, 198690009, 198691008, 198692001, 198694000, 198696003, 198697007, 198698002, 198702003, 198703008, 198729008, 198730003, 198731004, 198741001, 198742008, 198767006,

		198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 198860004, 198880003, 200480007, 200485002, 267192009, 267195006, 267295002, 267296001, 267297005, 27169005, 288045002, 3634007, 363681007, 386639001, 39406005, 49632008, 57734001, 57797005, 70317007, 7802000
Elective abortion	SNOMEDCT_US	111431001, 1321008, 149996005, 156070002, 156075007, 156076008, 156077004, 156079001, 156096000, 18302006, 18391007, 198690009, 198691008, 198692001, 198694000, 198696003, 198697007, 198698002, 198702003, 198703008, 198729008, 198730003, 198731004, 198741001, 198742008, 198767006, 198768001, 198769009, 198780009, 198805006, 198860004, 198880003, 200480007, 200485002, 267192009, 267195006, 267295002, 267296001, 267297005, 27169005, 288045002, 3634007, 363681007, 386639001, 39406005, 49632008, 57734001, 57797005, 70317007, 7802000
Epilepsy	ICD10	G40, G40.0, G40.2, G40.3, G40.4, G40.5, G40.6, G40.7, G40.8, G40.9, G41, G41.0, G41.1, G41.2, G41.8, G41.9
Epilepsy	ICD10CM	G40.0, G40.009, G40.2, G40.209, G40.3, G40.309, G40.4, G40.40, G40.80, G40.802, G40.9, G40.90, G40.909, G40.91, G40.A, R56.9
Epilepsy	ICD9	345, 345.0, 345.1, 345.2, 345.3, 345.4, 345.5, 345.6, 345.7, 345.8, 345.9, 780.3
Epilepsy	ICD9CM	345.0, 345.1, 345.2, 345.3, 345.9, 345.90, 345.91, 780.3
Epilepsy	ICPC	N88
Epilepsy	MTHICD9	293.0, 345.0, 345.1, 345.2, 345.3, 345.4, 345.5, 345.8, 345.9, 780.39
Epilepsy	RCD2	1B63, 1B64, 2828, F132z, F25, F250, F2500, F2501, F2502, F2503, F2504, F250z, F251, F2510, F2511, F2512, F2513, F2514, F2516, F251z, F252, F253, F254, F2540, F2541, F2542, F2544, F254z, F255, F2550, F2551, F2552, F2555, F255z, F25A, F25C, F25H, F25y, F25y0, F25y2, F25y3, F25yz, F25z, Fyu50, Fyu51, Fyu52, Fyu59, R003, R0032, R003z, SC200
Epilepsy	SNOMED	1,18E+14, 128612007, 128613002, 13973009, 140805008, 155036009, 155038005, 155039002, 155040000, 155041001, 155043003, 155044009, 155045005, 157437008, 158138006, 158141002, 158142009, 163596002, 16757004, 189198006, 192979009, 192981006, 192982004, 192987005, 192988000, 192989008, 192990004, 192991000, 192993002, 192994008, 192995009, 192997001, 192998006, 192999003, 193000002, 193001003, 193002005, 193004006, 193005007, 193006008, 193007004, 193008009, 193011005, 193013008, 193019007, 193020001, 193021002, 193022009, 193023004, 193025006, 193026007, 194490007, 194491006, 194492004, 194499008, 19598007, 206732001, 206735004, 206738002, 2198002, 230381009, 230414008, 230421008, 230422001, 230441003, 230456007, 230460005, 246543009, 246545002, 246554004, 267593008, 267698007, 271788002, 29753000, 307358009, 309847002, 312078006, 313290005, 32631004, 352818000, 35796005, 361123003, 365883006, 36803009, 407675009, 42365007, 4,32E+14, 4619009, 54200006, 6204001, 65120008, 65155005, 67139004, 7033004, 71427006, 73714002, 75023009, 79348005, 79631006, 79745005, 82401000, 8,29E+12, 84340007, 84757009, 91175000
Epilepsy	SNOMEDCT_US	1,18E+14, 128612007, 128613002, 13973009, 140805008, 155036009, 155038005, 155039002, 155040000, 155041001, 155043003, 155044009, 155045005, 157437008, 158138006, 158141002, 158142009, 163596002, 16757004, 189198006, 192979009, 192981006, 192982004, 192987005, 192988000, 192989008, 192990004, 192991000, 192993002, 192994008, 192995009, 192997001, 192998006, 192999003, 193000002, 193001003, 193002005, 193004006, 193005007, 193006008, 193007004, 193008009, 193011005, 193013008, 193019007, 193020001, 193021002, 193022009, 193023004, 193025006, 193026007, 194490007, 194491006, 194492004, 194499008, 19598007, 206732001, 206735004, 206738002, 2198002, 230381009, 230414008, 230421008, 230422001, 230441003, 230456007, 230460005, 246543009, 246545002, 246554004, 267593008, 267698007, 271788002, 29753000, 307358009, 309847002, 312078006, 313290005, 32631004, 352818000, 35796005, 361123003, 365883006, 36803009, 407675009, 42365007, 4,32E+14, 4619009, 54200006, 6204001, 65120008, 65155005, 67139004, 7033004, 71427006, 73714002, 75023009, 79348005, 79631006, 79745005, 82401000, 8,29E+12, 84340007, 84757009, 91175000
Fetal growth restriction	ICD10CM	O36.511, O36.5110, O36.5111, O36.5112, O36.5113, O36.5114, O36.5115, O36.5119, O36.512, O36.5120, O36.5121, O36.5122, O36.5123, O36.5124, O36.5125, O36.5129, O36.513, O36.5130, O36.5131, O36.5132, O36.5133, O36.5134, O36.5135, O36.5139, O36.591, O36.5910, O36.5911, O36.5912, O36.5913, O36.5914, O36.5915, O36.5919, O36.592, O36.5920, O36.5921, O36.5922, O36.5923, O36.5924, O36.5925, O36.5929, O36.593, O36.5930, O36.5931, O36.5932, O36.5933, O36.5934, O36.5935, O36.5939, O41.0, O41.00, P05.9
Fetal growth restriction	ICD9	656.5, 764, 764.0, 764.1, 764.2, 764.9
Fetal growth restriction	ICD9CM	656.50, 656.51, 656.53, 658.0, 764, 764.9, 764.90
Fetal growth restriction	MTHICD9	656.50, 656.51, 656.53, 764.9, 764.90
Fetal growth restriction	RCD2	L280, L2800, L280z, Q10z
Fetal growth restriction	SNOMED	156185006, 156190009, 157051001, 18471004, 199652007, 199656005, 206162003, 206166000, 22033007, 267337006, 268814006, 268815007, 59566000
Fetal growth restriction	SNOMEDCT_US	156185006, 156190009, 157051001, 18471004, 199652007, 199656005, 206162003, 206166000, 22033007, 267337006, 268814006, 268815007, 59566000
Gestational diabetes	ICD10	O24.4

Gestational diabetes	ICD10CM	O24, O24.4, O24.41, O24.410, O24.414, O24.419, O24.42, O24.420, O24.424, O24.429, O24.43, O24.430, O24.434, O24.439, O24.9
Gestational diabetes	ICD9	648.0, 648.8
Gestational diabetes	ICD9CM	648.0, 648.00, 648.01, 648.02, 648.04, 648.8, 648.80, 648.81, 648.82
Gestational diabetes	MTHICD9	648.00, 648.01, 648.02, 648.04, 648.8, 648.80, 648.81, 648.82
Gestational diabetes	RCD2	L180, L1801, L1802, L1804, L1808, L180z
Gestational diabetes	SNOMED	1,08E+16, 11687002, 156138000, 199223000, 199225007, 199226008, 199228009, 199232003, 199234002, 237629002, 359964007, 393568003, 39763004, 76751001
Gestational diabetes	SNOMEDCT_US	1,08E+16, 11687002, 156138000, 199223000, 199225007, 199226008, 199228009, 199232003, 199234002, 237629002, 359964007, 393568003, 39763004, 76751001
Major congenital anomalies	ICD10	Q00, Q00.0, Q00.1, Q00.2, Q00.3, Q00.4, Q00.5, Q00.6, Q00.7, Q00.8, Q00.9, Q01.0, Q01.1, Q01.2, Q01.3, Q01.4, Q01.5, Q01.6, Q01.7, Q01.8, Q01.9, Q02.0, Q02.1, Q02.2, Q02.3, Q02.4, Q02.5, Q02.6, Q02.7, Q02.8, Q02.9, Q03.0, Q03.1, Q03.2, Q03.3, Q03.4, Q03.5, Q03.6, Q03.7, Q03.8, Q03.9, Q04.0, Q04.1, Q04.2, Q04.3, Q04.4, Q04.5, Q04.6, Q04.7, Q04.8, Q04.9, Q05, Q05.0, Q05.1, Q05.2, Q05.3, Q05.4, Q05.5, Q05.6, Q05.7, Q05.8, Q05.9, Q06.0, Q06.1, Q06.2, Q06.3, Q06.4, Q06.5, Q06.6, Q06.7, Q06.8, Q06.9, Q07.0, Q07.1, Q07.2, Q07.3, Q07.4, Q07.5, Q07.6, Q07.7, Q07.8, Q07.9, Q10.0, Q10.1, Q10.2, Q10.3, Q10.4, Q10.5, Q10.6, Q10.7, Q10.8, Q10.9, Q11.0, Q11.1, Q11.2, Q11.3, Q11.4, Q11.5, Q11.6, Q11.7, Q11.8, Q11.9, Q12.0, Q12.1, Q12.2, Q12.3, Q12.4, Q12.5, Q12.6, Q12.7, Q12.8, Q12.9, Q13.0, Q13.1, Q13.2, Q13.3, Q13.4, Q13.5, Q13.6, Q13.7, Q13.8, Q13.9, Q14.0, Q14.1, Q14.2, Q14.3, Q14.4, Q14.5, Q14.6, Q14.7, Q14.8, Q14.9, Q15.0, Q15.1, Q15.2, Q15.3, Q15.4, Q15.5, Q15.6, Q15.7, Q15.8, Q15.9, Q16.0, Q16.1, Q16.2, Q16.3, Q16.4, Q16.5, Q16.6, Q16.7, Q16.8, Q16.9, Q17.0, Q17.1, Q17.2, Q17.3, Q17.4, Q17.5, Q17.6, Q17.7, Q17.8, Q17.9, Q18.0, Q18.1, Q18.2, Q18.3, Q18.4, Q18.5, Q18.6, Q18.7, Q18.8, Q18.9, Q20.0, Q20.1, Q20.2, Q20.3, Q20.4, Q20.5, Q20.6, Q20.7, Q20.8, Q20.9, Q21.0, Q21.1, Q21.2, Q21.3, Q21.4, Q21.5, Q21.6, Q21.7, Q21.8, Q21.9, Q22.0, Q22.1, Q22.2, Q22.3, Q22.4, Q22.5, Q22.6, Q22.7, Q22.8, Q22.9, Q23.0, Q23.1, Q23.2, Q23.3, Q23.4, Q23.5, Q23.6, Q23.7, Q23.8, Q23.9, Q24, Q24.0, Q24.1, Q24.2, Q24.3, Q24.4, Q24.5, Q24.6, Q24.7, Q24.8, Q24.9, Q25.0, Q25.1, Q25.2, Q25.3, Q25.4, Q25.5, Q25.6, Q25.7, Q25.8, Q25.9, Q26.0, Q26.1, Q26.2, Q26.3, Q26.4, Q26.5, Q26.6, Q26.7, Q26.8, Q26.9, Q27.0, Q27.1, Q27.2, Q27.3, Q27.4, Q27.5, Q27.6, Q27.7, Q27.8, Q27.9, Q28, Q28.0, Q28.1, Q28.2, Q28.3, Q28.4, Q28.5, Q28.6, Q28.7, Q28.8, Q28.9, Q30.0, Q30.1, Q30.2, Q30.3, Q30.4, Q30.5, Q30.6, Q30.7, Q30.8, Q30.9, Q31.0, Q31.1, Q31.2, Q31.3, Q31.4, Q31.5, Q31.6, Q31.7, Q31.8, Q31.9, Q32.0, Q32.1, Q32.2, Q32.3, Q32.4, Q32.5, Q32.6, Q32.7, Q32.8, Q32.9, Q33.0, Q33.1, Q33.2, Q33.3, Q33.4, Q33.5, Q33.6, Q33.7, Q33.8, Q33.9, Q34.0, Q34.1, Q34.2, Q34.3, Q34.4, Q34.5, Q34.6, Q34.7, Q34.8, Q34.9, Q35.0, Q35.1, Q35.2, Q35.3, Q35.4, Q35.5, Q35.6, Q35.7, Q35.8, Q35.9, Q36.0, Q36.1, Q36.2, Q36.3, Q36.4, Q36.5, Q36.6, Q36.7, Q36.8, Q36.9, Q37, Q37.0, Q37.1, Q37.2, Q37.3, Q37.4, Q37.5, Q37.6, Q37.7, Q37.8, Q37.9, Q38.0, Q38.1, Q38.2, Q38.3, Q38.4, Q38.5, Q38.6, Q38.7, Q38.8, Q38.9, Q39.0, Q39.1, Q39.2, Q39.3, Q39.4, Q39.5, Q39.6, Q39.7, Q39.8, Q39.9, Q40, Q40.0, Q40.1, Q40.2, Q40.3, Q40.4, Q40.5, Q40.6, Q40.7, Q40.8, Q40.9, Q41.0, Q41.1, Q41.2, Q41.3, Q41.4, Q41.5, Q41.6, Q41.7, Q41.8, Q41.9, Q42.0, Q42.1, Q42.2, Q42.3, Q42.4, Q42.5, Q42.6, Q42.7, Q42.8, Q42.9, Q43.0, Q43.1, Q43.2, Q43.3, Q43.4, Q43.5, Q43.6, Q43.7, Q43.8, Q43.9, Q44.0, Q44.1, Q44.2, Q44.3, Q44.4, Q44.5, Q44.6, Q44.7, Q44.8, Q44.9, Q45, Q45.0, Q45.1, Q45.2, Q45.3, Q45.4, Q45.5, Q45.6, Q45.7, Q45.8, Q45.9, Q50.0, Q50.1, Q50.2, Q50.3, Q50.4, Q50.5, Q50.6, Q50.7, Q50.8, Q50.9, Q51.0, Q51.1, Q51.2, Q51.3, Q51.4, Q51.5, Q51.6, Q51.7, Q51.8, Q51.9, Q52.0, Q52.1, Q52.2, Q52.3, Q52.4, Q52.5, Q52.6, Q52.7, Q52.8, Q52.9, Q53.0, Q53.1, Q53.2, Q53.3, Q53.4, Q53.5, Q53.6, Q53.7, Q53.8, Q53.9, Q54.0, Q54.1, Q54.2, Q54.3, Q54.4, Q54.5, Q54.6, Q54.7, Q54.8, Q54.9, Q55.0, Q55.1, Q55.2, Q55.3, Q55.4, Q55.5, Q55.6, Q55.7, Q55.8, Q55.9, Q56.0, Q56.1, Q56.2, Q56.3, Q56.4, Q56.5, Q56.6, Q56.7, Q56.8, Q56.9, Q60.0, Q60.1, Q60.2, Q60.3, Q60.4, Q60.5, Q60.6, Q60.7, Q60.8, Q60.9, Q61.0, Q61.1, Q61.2, Q61.3, Q61.4, Q61.5, Q61.6, Q61.7, Q61.8, Q61.9, Q62.0, Q62.1, Q62.2, Q62.3, Q62.4, Q62.5, Q62.6, Q62.7, Q62.8, Q62.9, Q63.0, Q63.1, Q63.2, Q63.3, Q63.4, Q63.5, Q63.6, Q63.7, Q63.8, Q63.9, Q64.0, Q64.1, Q64.2, Q64.3, Q64.4, Q64.5, Q64.6, Q64.7, Q64.8, Q64.9, Q68, Q80.0, Q80.1, Q80.2, Q80.3, Q80.4, Q80.5, Q80.6, Q80.7, Q80.8, Q80.9, Q81.0, Q81.1, Q81.2, Q81.3, Q81.4, Q81.5, Q81.6, Q81.7, Q81.8, Q81.9, Q82.0, Q82.1, Q82.2, Q82.3, Q82.4, Q82.5, Q82.6, Q82.7, Q82.8, Q82.9, Q83.0, Q83.1, Q83.2, Q83.3, Q83.4, Q83.5, Q83.6, Q83.7, Q83.8, Q83.9, Q84.0, Q84.1, Q84.2, Q84.3, Q84.4, Q84.5, Q84.6, Q84.7, Q84.8, Q84.9, Q85.0, Q85.1, Q85.2, Q85.3, Q85.4, Q85.5, Q85.6, Q85.7, Q85.8, Q85.9, Q86.0, Q86.1, Q86.2, Q86.3, Q86.4, Q86.5, Q86.6, Q86.7, Q86.8, Q86.9, Q87.0, Q87.1, Q87.2, Q87.3, Q87.4, Q87.5, Q87.6, Q87.7, Q87.8, Q87.9, Q88.0, Q88.1, Q88.2, Q88.3, Q88.4, Q88.5, Q88.6, Q88.7, Q88.8, Q88.9, Q89.0, Q89.1, Q89.2, Q89.3, Q89.4, Q89.5, Q89.6, Q89.7, Q89.8, Q89.9, Q99.9
Major congenital anomalies	ICD10CM	Q00, Q01, Q02, Q03, Q04, Q05, Q05.9, Q06, Q07, Q07.9, Q10, Q11, Q12, Q13, Q14, Q15, Q15.9, Q16, Q17, Q17.9, Q18, Q20, Q21, Q22, Q23, Q24, Q24.9, Q25, Q26, Q27, Q28, Q28.9, Q30, Q31, Q32, Q33, Q34, Q34.9, Q35, Q36, Q37, Q37.9, Q38, Q39, Q40, Q40.1, Q41, Q42, Q43, Q44, Q45, Q45.9, Q50, Q51, Q52, Q53, Q54, Q55, Q56, Q60, Q61, Q62, Q63, Q64, Q64.9, Q68, Q80, Q81, Q82, Q83, Q84, Q84.9, Q85, Q86, Q87, Q88, Q89, Q89.9, Q99.9
Major congenital anomalies	ICD9	740, 740.0, 740.1, 740.2, 741, 741.0, 741.9, 742, 742.0, 742.1, 742.2, 742.3, 742.4, 742.5, 742.8, 742.9, 743, 743.0, 743.1, 743.2, 743.3, 743.4, 743.5, 743.6, 743.8, 743.9, 744, 744.0, 744.1, 744.2, 744.3, 744.4, 744.5, 744.8, 744.9, 745, 745.0, 745.1, 745.2, 745.3, 745.4, 745.5, 745.6, 745.7, 745.8, 745.9, 746, 746.0, 746.1, 746.2, 746.3, 746.4, 746.5, 746.6, 746.7, 746.8, 746.9, 747, 747.0, 747.1, 747.2, 747.3, 747.4, 747.5, 747.6, 747.7, 747.8, 747.9, 748, 748.0, 748.1, 748.2, 748.3, 748.4, 748.5, 748.6, 748.8, 748.9, 749, 749.0, 749.1, 749.2, 750, 750.0, 750.1, 750.2, 750.3, 750.4, 750.5, 750.6, 750.7, 750.8, 750.9, 751, 751.0, 751.1, 751.2, 751.3,

		757.41, 757.42, 757.43, 757.44, 757.45, 757.46, 757.47, 757.48, 757.49, 757.50, 757.51, 757.52, 757.53, 757.54, 757.55, 757.56, 757.57, 757.58, 757.59, 757.60, 757.61, 757.62, 757.63, 757.64, 757.65, 757.66, 757.67, 757.68, 757.69, 757.70, 757.71, 757.72, 757.73, 757.74, 757.75, 757.76, 757.77, 757.78, 757.79, 757.80, 757.81, 757.82, 757.83, 757.84, 757.85, 757.86, 757.87, 757.88, 757.89, 757.9, 757.90, 757.91, 757.92, 757.93, 757.94, 757.95, 757.96, 757.97, 757.98, 757.99, 758, 758.00, 758.01, 758.02, 758.03, 758.04, 758.05, 758.06, 758.07, 758.08, 758.09, 758.10, 758.11, 758.12, 758.13, 758.14, 758.15, 758.16, 758.17, 758.18, 758.19, 758.20, 758.21, 758.22, 758.23, 758.24, 758.25, 758.26, 758.27, 758.28, 758.29, 758.30, 758.31, 758.32, 758.33, 758.34, 758.35, 758.36, 758.37, 758.38, 758.39, 758.40, 758.41, 758.42, 758.43, 758.44, 758.45, 758.46, 758.47, 758.48, 758.49, 758.50, 758.51, 758.52, 758.53, 758.54, 758.55, 758.56, 758.57, 758.58, 758.59, 758.60, 758.61, 758.62, 758.63, 758.64, 758.65, 758.66, 758.67, 758.68, 758.69, 758.70, 758.71, 758.72, 758.73, 758.74, 758.75, 758.76, 758.77, 758.78, 758.79, 758.80, 758.81, 758.82, 758.83, 758.84, 758.85, 758.86, 758.87, 758.88, 758.89, 758.9, 758.90, 758.91, 758.92, 758.93, 758.94, 758.95, 758.96, 758.97, 758.98, 758.99, 759, 759.00, 759.01, 759.02, 759.03, 759.04, 759.05, 759.06, 759.07, 759.08, 759.09, 759.10, 759.11, 759.12, 759.13, 759.14, 759.15, 759.16, 759.17, 759.18, 759.19, 759.20, 759.21, 759.22, 759.23, 759.24, 759.25, 759.26, 759.27, 759.28, 759.29, 759.30, 759.31, 759.32, 759.33, 759.34, 759.35, 759.36, 759.37, 759.38, 759.39, 759.40, 759.41, 759.42, 759.43, 759.44, 759.45, 759.46, 759.47, 759.48, 759.49, 759.50, 759.51, 759.52, 759.53, 759.54, 759.55, 759.56, 759.57, 759.58, 759.59, 759.60, 759.61, 759.62, 759.63, 759.64, 759.65, 759.66, 759.67, 759.68, 759.69, 759.70, 759.71, 759.72, 759.73, 759.74, 759.75, 759.76, 759.77, 759.78, 759.79, 759.80, 759.81, 759.82, 759.83, 759.84, 759.85, 759.86, 759.87, 759.88, 759.89, 759.9, 759.90, 759.91, 759.92, 759.93, 759.94, 759.95, 759.96, 759.97, 759.98, 759.99
Major congenital anomalies	ICPC	D81, H80, N85, R89, U85
Major congenital anomalies	MTHICD9	742.9, 743.9, 744.3, 746.9, 747.9, 748.9, 749.2, 750.6, 751.9, 752.9, 753.9, 757.9
Major congenital anomalies	RCD2	P, P0, P0z, P1, P1z, P2, P2y, P2yz, P2z, P3, P3z, P43, P6, P68, P6zz, P7, P7z, P8, P8z, P9, P92, P92z, PA, PA6, PB, PBz, PC, PCz, PD, PDz, PE, PE9, PF, PG, PHz, PJ, Pjz, Pjzz, PK, PKz, Pyu0, Pyu1, Pyu1D, Pyu2, Pyu2K, Pyu3, Pyu5, Pyu6, Pyu7, Pyu9, Pz
Major congenital anomalies	SNOMED	107656002, 112635002, 118642009, 13213009, 156884008, 156888006, 156897005, 156902006, 156903001, 156906009, 156911006, 156926008, 156933008, 156939007, 156942001, 156963004, 156971000, 156980000, 156994004, 157009008, 157017000, 157018005, 157023005, 157028001, 157033002, 157034008, 19416009, 203922009, 203930005, 204017003, 204018008, 204093003, 204096006, 204097002, 204222005, 204262009, 204338002, 204405005, 204413006, 204414000, 204494001, 204507004, 204592004, 204610002, 204611003, 204622004, 204624003, 204684000, 204820005, 204821009, 204937002, 205028008, 205033007, 205116003, 205118002, 205407005, 205589009, 205610005, 205724000, 205729005, 205730000, 205839007, 205842001, 205845004, 205854001, 205871000, 205893005, 205894004, 205902007, 205905009, 205925008, 205939008, 205973003, 205999005, 21390004, 231789000, 253210009, 253819001, 253859003, 253983005, 268191000, 268238001, 268249007, 268291009, 268310007, 268311006, 268312004, 268315002, 268318000, 268321003, 268329001, 268353007, 268354001, 268355000, 268359006, 275259005, 275260000, 276654001, 276655000, 304086001, 38164009, 385297003, 409709004, 41859001, 443341004, 47028006, 66091009, 66948001, 67531005, 69518005, 73262007, 74345006, 77868001, 8380000, 88425004
Major congenital anomalies	SNOMEDCT_US	107656002, 112635002, 118642009, 13213009, 156884008, 156888006, 156897005, 156902006, 156903001, 156906009, 156911006, 156926008, 156933008, 156939007, 156942001, 156963004, 156971000, 156980000, 156994004, 157009008, 157017000, 157018005, 157023005, 157028001, 157033002, 157034008, 19416009, 203922009, 203930005, 204017003, 204018008, 204093003, 204096006, 204097002, 204222005, 204262009, 204338002, 204405005, 204413006, 204414000, 204494001, 204507004, 204592004, 204610002, 204611003, 204622004, 204624003, 204684000, 204820005, 204821009, 204937002, 205028008, 205033007, 205116003, 205118002, 205407005, 205589009, 205610005, 205724000, 205729005, 205730000, 205839007, 205842001, 205845004, 205854001, 205871000, 205893005, 205894004, 205902007, 205905009, 205925008, 205939008, 205973003, 205999005, 21390004, 231789000, 253210009, 253819001, 253859003, 253983005, 268191000, 268238001, 268249007, 268291009, 268310007, 268311006, 268312004, 268315002, 268318000, 268321003, 268329001, 268353007, 268354001, 268355000, 268359006, 275259005, 275260000, 276654001, 276655000, 304086001, 38164009, 385297003, 409709004, 41859001, 443341004, 47028006, 66091009, 66948001, 67531005, 69518005, 73262007, 74345006, 77868001, 8380000, 88425004
Microcephaly	ICD10	Q02
Microcephaly	ICD10CM	Q02
Microcephaly	ICD9CM	742.1
Microcephaly	RCD2	P21, P210, P211, P21z
Microcephaly	SNOMED	156893009, 1829003, 204029007, 204030002, 204031003, 78071008
Microcephaly	SNOMEDCT_US	156893009, 1829003, 204029007, 204030002, 204031003, 78071008
Migraine	ICD10	G43, G43.0, G43.1, G43.3, G43.8, G43.9
Migraine	ICD10CM	G43, G43.0, G43.009, G43.1, G43.109, G43.4, G43.409, G43.5, G43.509, G43.6, G43.7, G43.8, G43.9, G43.90, G43.909, G43.91, G43.B, G43.D, G44.00

Migraine	ICD9	346, 346.0, 346.1, 346.2, 346.8, 346.9
Migraine	ICD9CM	346, 346.0, 346.1, 346.2, 346.3, 346.5, 346.6, 346.8, 346.9, 346.90, 346.91, 346.92, 346.93
Migraine	ICPC	N89
Migraine	MTHICD9	339.00, 346.0, 346.1, 346.2, 346.5
Migraine	RCD2	F26, F260, F261, F2610, F261z, F2622, F2623, F2624, F26y, F26y0, F26y1, F26y3, F26yz, F26z, Fyu53, R090D
Migraine	SNOMED	155046006, 155047002, 155048007, 193027003, 193029000, 193033007, 193037008, 193039006, 193040008, 193041007, 194493009, 207219003, 230462002, 230463007, 26150009, 267699004, 37796009, 427419006, 4473006, 49605003, 56097005, 59292006, 75879005, 79267007, 83351003, 95655001
Migraine	SNOMEDCT_US	155046006, 155047002, 155048007, 193027003, 193029000, 193033007, 193037008, 193039006, 193040008, 193041007, 194493009, 207219003, 230462002, 230463007, 26150009, 267699004, 37796009, 427419006, 4473006, 49605003, 56097005, 59292006, 75879005, 79267007, 83351003, 95655001
Multiple gestation	ICD10	O30, O30.0, O30.1, O30.2, O30.8, O30.9, O31.2, Z37.2
Multiple gestation	ICD10CM	O30, O30.0, O30.00, O30.009, O30.03, O30.1, O30.2, O30.8, O30.9, O30.90, O30.91, O30.92, O30.93, O31.2, O31.20, Z37.2
Multiple gestation	ICD9	651, 651.0, 651.1, 651.2, 651.8, 651.9, 652.6, 660.5
Multiple gestation	ICD9CM	651, 651.0, 651.00, 651.1, 651.10, 651.2, 651.20, 651.3, 651.4, 651.5, 651.6, 651.7, 651.8, 651.9, 651.90, 651.91, 651.93, V27.2
Multiple gestation	MTHICD9	633.8, 651.00, 651.10, 651.20, 651.4, 651.90, 651.91, V27.2
Multiple gestation	RCD2	L03y3, L192, L21, L210, L2100, L210z, L211, L2110, L211z, L212, L2120, L212z, L21y, L21y0, L21yz, L21z, L21z0, L21z2, Lyu30
Multiple gestation	SNOMED	156150006, 156151005, 156152003, 156153008, 156154002, 16356006, 199307003, 199316004, 199319006, 199320000, 199323003, 199324009, 199327002, 199332001, 199333006, 199336003, 199337007, 199338002, 199340007, 199341006, 200508000, 315960005, 31601007, 459168005, 60810003, 64254006, 65147003
Multiple gestation	SNOMEDCT_US	156150006, 156151005, 156152003, 156153008, 156154002, 16356006, 199307003, 199316004, 199319006, 199320000, 199323003, 199324009, 199327002, 199332001, 199333006, 199336003, 199337007, 199338002, 199340007, 199341006, 200508000, 315960005, 31601007, 459168005, 60810003, 64254006, 65147003
Multiple sclerosis	ICD10	G35, G36.0, H46
Multiple sclerosis	ICD10CM	G35, G36.0, H46, H46.9
Multiple sclerosis	ICD9	340, 341, 341.0, 341.1, 341.8, 341.9, 377.3, 377.30
Multiple sclerosis	ICD9CM	340, 341.0, 377.3, 377.30
Multiple sclerosis	ICPC	N86
Multiple sclerosis	MTHICD9	340
Multiple sclerosis	RCD2	F20, F200, F201, F202, F203, F20z, F210, F4H3, F4H30, F4H3z
Multiple sclerosis	SNOMED	155023009, 155189007, 16092000, 18353007, 192926004, 192927008, 192928003, 192929006, 192930001, 194051001, 194052008, 194054009, 230373008, 24700007, 25044007, 267743006, 425500002, 426373005, 428700003, 66760008, 816984002
Multiple sclerosis	SNOMEDCT_US	155023009, 155189007, 16092000, 18353007, 192926004, 192927008, 192928003, 192929006, 192930001, 194051001, 194052008, 194054009, 230373008, 24700007, 25044007, 267743006, 425500002, 426373005, 428700003, 66760008, 816984002
Neonatal death	ICD10	R95, R96.0, R96.1, R98
Neonatal death	ICD10CM	G93.82, R99
Neonatal death	ICD9	768.0, 768.1, 798, 798.0, 798.1, 798.2, 798.9
Neonatal death	ICD9CM	348.82, 798, 798.0, 798.1, 798.2, 798.9
Neonatal death	ICPC	A94, A95, A96
Neonatal death	MTHICD9	798.0, 798.9
Neonatal death	RCD2	13M2, 22J, 22J4, 22J8, 22JZ, Q48y7, Q4z, R21, R210, R2100, R2101, R210z, R211, R212, R212z, R213, R2131, R213z, R21z
Neonatal death	SNOMED	10588007, 138274000, 140067002, 140074007, 15355001, 157167009, 158717006, 158718001, 158719009, 158720003, 158723001, 158724007, 158726009, 158727000, 158728005, 160956009, 162851009, 162858003, 206602000, 207533004, 207534005, 207535006, 207536007, 207538008, 207539000, 207540003, 207543001, 207544007, 207546009, 207547000, 207548005, 207671002, 240297000,

		26636000, 268887007, 268923008, 274641005, 274644002, 276505002, 276506001, 390729007, 397709008, 399347008, 419620001, 419973004, 50514002, 51178009, 53559009, 61626005, 6254007, 87309006, 90049009
Neonatal death	SNOMEDCT_US	10588007, 138274000, 140067002, 140074007, 15355001, 157167009, 158717006, 158718001, 158719009, 158720003, 158723001, 158724007, 158726009, 158727000, 158728005, 160956009, 162851009, 162858003, 206602000, 207533004, 207534005, 207535006, 207536007, 207538008, 207539000, 207540003, 207543001, 207544007, 207546009, 207547000, 207548005, 207671002, 240297000, 26636000, 268887007, 268923008, 274641005, 274644002, 276505002, 276506001, 390729007, 397709008, 399347008, 419620001, 419973004, 50514002, 51178009, 53559009, 61626005, 6254007, 87309006, 90049009
Preeclampsia	ICD10	O12.1, O14.1, O14.9, O15, O15.0, O15.9
Preeclampsia	ICD10CM	O12.1, O13, O14, O14.1, O14.9, O14.90, O15, O15.9
Preeclampsia	ICD9	642, 642.0, 642.1, 642.3, 642.4, 642.5, 642.7, 642.9
Preeclampsia	ICD9CM	642.3, 642.4, 642.40, 642.41, 642.42, 642.43, 642.44, 642.5, 642.50, 642.51, 642.52, 642.53, 642.54, 642.63, 642.7, 642.70, 642.71, 642.72, 642.73, 642.74
Preeclampsia	ICPC	W81
Preeclampsia	MTHICD9	642.3, 642.4, 642.40, 642.41, 642.42, 642.43, 642.44, 642.5, 642.50, 642.51, 642.52, 642.53, 642.54, 642.63, 642.70, 642.71, 642.72, 642.73, 642.74
Preeclampsia	RCD2	L1230, L1235, L1236, L123z, L124, L1240, L1245, L1246, L124z, L125, L1250, L125z, L126, L1260, L1263, L126z, L12B, L16C0
Preeclampsia	SNOMED	156106005, 156107001, 156108006, 156109003, 156110008, 156111007, 156125008, 15938005, 198963003, 198964009, 198970003, 198971004, 198972006, 198973001, 198978005, 198979002, 198980004, 198981000, 198982007, 198987001, 198988006, 198989003, 198992004, 198994003, 198996001, 199011002, 199140001, 237279007, 267200002, 267306006, 288201007, 30354006, 34165000, 398254007, 41114007, 46764007, 6758009
Preeclampsia	SNOMEDCT_US	156106005, 156107001, 156108006, 156109003, 156110008, 156111007, 156125008, 15938005, 198963003, 198964009, 198970003, 198971004, 198972006, 198973001, 198978005, 198979002, 198980004, 198981000, 198982007, 198987001, 198988006, 198989003, 198992004, 198994003, 198996001, 199011002, 199140001, 237279007, 267200002, 267306006, 288201007, 30354006, 34165000, 398254007, 41114007, 46764007, 6758009
Preterm birth	ICD10	O60, P07.2, P07.3
Preterm birth	ICD10CM	O60, P07.2, P07.20, P07.21, P07.22, P07.23, P07.24, P07.25, P07.26, P07.3, P07.30, P07.31, P07.32, P07.33, P07.34, P07.35, P07.36, P07.37, P07.38, P07.39
Preterm birth	ICD9	641.2, 658.1, 761.1, 765.0, 765.1, 774.2, 776.6
Preterm birth	ICD9CM	644.2, 765.0, 765.1, 765.10, 765.11, 765.12, 765.13, 765.14, 765.15, 765.16, 765.17, 765.18, 765.19, 765.21, 765.22, 765.23, 765.24, 765.25, 765.26, 765.27, 765.28
Preterm birth	ICPC	A93
Preterm birth	MTHICD9	644.2, 765.10, 765.19
Preterm birth	RCD2	62X0, 62X1, 6352, 6353, 6356, 6357, 6358, 635B, L14, L142, L142z, Q11, Q110, Q112, Q116, Q11z, Qyu11
Preterm birth	SNOMED	147035002, 147036001, 147079004, 147081002, 147082009, 147085006, 147086007, 147087003, 147090009, 156118001, 156120003, 157080005, 169806005, 169807001, 169848003, 169850006, 169851005, 169853008, 169854002, 169855001, 169858004, 199046005, 199056009, 199059002, 206167009, 206168004, 206170008, 206177006, 206621008, 267310009, 268817004, 270496001, 276658003, 282020008, 310523002, 310527001, 310530008, 310548004, 310661005, 313178001, 313179009, 367494004, 395507008, 43963002, 47243004, 4886009, 49550006, 6383007, 65588006, 69471007, 771299009
Preterm birth	SNOMEDCT_US	147035002, 147036001, 147079004, 147081002, 147082009, 147085006, 147086007, 147087003, 147090009, 156118001, 156120003, 157080005, 169806005, 169807001, 169848003, 169850006, 169851005, 169853008, 169854002, 169855001, 169858004, 199046005, 199056009, 199059002, 206167009, 206168004, 206170008, 206177006, 206621008, 267310009, 268817004, 270496001, 276658003, 282020008, 310523002, 310527001, 310530008, 310548004, 310661005, 313178001, 313179009, 367494004, 395507008, 43963002, 47243004, 4886009, 49550006, 6383007, 65588006, 69471007, 771299009
Rheumatoid arthritis	ICD10	M05, M05.0, M05.2, M05.3, M05.8, M05.9, M06.0, M06.1, M06.3, M06.8, M06.9, M08.4
Rheumatoid arthritis	ICD10CM	M05.0, M05.00, M05.6, M06.1, M06.3, M06.8, M06.80, M06.9, M08.4, M08.40
Rheumatoid arthritis	ICD9	714, 714.0, 714.1, 714.2, 714.3, 714.4, 714.8, 714.9
Rheumatoid arthritis	ICD9CM	714.0, 714.1, 714.2, 714.30, 714.32
Rheumatoid arthritis	ICPC	L88
Rheumatoid arthritis	MTHICD9	714.0, 714.1

Rheumatoid arthritis	RCD2	66H3, N005, N040, N0400, N0401, N0402, N0403, N0404, N0405, N0406, N0407, N0408, N0409, N040A, N040B, N040C, N040D, N040E, N040F, N040G, N040H, N040J, N040K, N040L, N040M, N040N, N040P, N040S, N040T, N041, N042, N0422, N0432, N047, N04X, Nyu11, Nyu12, Nyu1G
Rheumatoid arthritis	SNOMED	111218008, 148074006, 156471009, 156472002, 156473007, 156474001, 156475000, 156477008, 156478003, 156481008, 156482001, 170848008, 201449008, 201764007, 201765008, 201766009, 201767000, 201768005, 201769002, 201770001, 201771002, 201772009, 201773004, 201774005, 201775006, 201776007, 201777003, 201778008, 201779000, 201780002, 201781003, 201782005, 201783000, 201784006, 201785007, 201786008, 201787004, 201789001, 201790005, 201791009, 201792002, 201809006, 201810001, 201811002, 201815006, 203730003, 203732006, 203746006, 239791005, 239792003, 239920006, 287006005, 287010008, 308143008, 33719002, 399112009, 400054000, 402426007, 50782009, 57160007, 69896004, 74391003, 80172006
Rheumatoid arthritis	SNOMEDCT_US	111218008, 148074006, 156471009, 156472002, 156473007, 156474001, 156475000, 156477008, 156478003, 156481008, 156482001, 170848008, 201449008, 201764007, 201765008, 201766009, 201767000, 201768005, 201769002, 201770001, 201771002, 201772009, 201773004, 201774005, 201775006, 201776007, 201777003, 201778008, 201779000, 201780002, 201781003, 201782005, 201783000, 201784006, 201785007, 201786008, 201787004, 201789001, 201790005, 201791009, 201792002, 201809006, 201810001, 201811002, 201815006, 203730003, 203732006, 203746006, 239791005, 239792003, 239920006, 287006005, 287010008, 308143008, 33719002, 399112009, 400054000, 402426007, 50782009, 57160007, 69896004, 74391003, 80172006
SLE	ICD10	L93, L93.0, L93.1, L93.2, M32, M32.0, M32.1, M32.8, M32.9
SLE	ICD10CM	A18.4, H01.12, L93, L93.0, L93.1, L93.2, M32, M32.0, M32.1, M32.8, M32.9
SLE	ICD9	695.4, 710.0
SLE	ICD9CM	373.34, 695.4, 710.0
SLE	MTHICD9	017.0, 135, 695.4, 710.0
SLE	RCD2	A1700, A1703, AD530, F4D33, K01x4, M154, M1540, M1541, M1542, M1543, M1544, M1545, M1546, M1547, M154z, Myu78, N000, N0002, N0003, N0005, N000z, Nyu43
SLE	SNOMED	10528009, 13902000, 15084002, 154290000, 156365002, 156450004, 186248003, 186249006, 186251005, 197608009, 200936003, 200937007, 200938002, 200939005, 200940007, 200941006, 200942004, 200943009, 200944003, 201422008, 201435004, 201436003, 201437007, 201439005, 203784000, 238927000, 239887007, 239888002, 239891002, 55464009, 68815009, 7119001, 79291003, 80258006, 95609003
SLE	SNOMEDCT_US	10528009, 13902000, 15084002, 154290000, 156365002, 156450004, 186248003, 186249006, 186251005, 197608009, 200936003, 200937007, 200938002, 200939005, 200940007, 200941006, 200942004, 200943009, 200944003, 201422008, 201435004, 201436003, 201437007, 201439005, 203784000, 238927000, 239887007, 239888002, 239891002, 55464009, 68815009, 7119001, 79291003, 80258006, 95609003
Spontaneous abortion	ICD10	N96, O02.1, O03, O03.0, O03.2, O03.3, O03.4, O03.5, O03.7, O03.8, O03.9
Spontaneous abortion	ICD10CM	N96, O00.1, O02.1, O03, O03.0, O03.2, O03.9
Spontaneous abortion	ICD9	632, 634, 634.0, 634.1, 634.2, 634.3, 634.4, 634.5, 634.6, 634.7, 634.8, 634.9
Spontaneous abortion	ICD9CM	632, 634, 634.0, 634.00, 634.01, 634.1, 634.2, 634.20, 634.3, 634.4, 634.40, 634.5, 634.6, 634.61, 634.7, 634.70, 634.8, 634.80, 634.9, 634.90, 634.91
Spontaneous abortion	ICPC	W82
Spontaneous abortion	MTHICD9	631.8, 633.1, 761.8
Spontaneous abortion	RCD2	L010, L011, L02, L04, L040, L040w, L040x, L040y, L040z, L041y, L04z, L264, L2640, L264z
Spontaneous abortion	SNOMED	102878001, 10697004, 13384007, 146811001, 156071003, 156072005, 156074006, 156086009, 156087000, 156126009, 156184005, 16607004, 16863000, 17369002, 19169002, 198616002, 198621004, 198631006, 198640005, 198641009, 198642002, 198643007, 198650006, 198653008, 198654002, 198689000, 199086002, 199090000, 199605001, 199606000, 199609007, 237245006, 240400006, 267187007, 267191002, 267294003, 267299008, 268574009, 275425008, 276507005, 2781009, 34270000, 34614007, 35999006, 428593008, 43306002, 54726000, 58990004, 609525000, 6176008, 76358005, 77846006, 84122000
Spontaneous abortion	SNOMEDCT_US	102878001, 10697004, 13384007, 146811001, 156071003, 156072005, 156074006, 156086009, 156087000, 156126009, 156184005, 16607004, 16863000, 17369002, 19169002, 198616002, 198621004, 198631006, 198640005, 198641009, 198642002, 198643007, 198650006, 198653008, 198654002, 198689000, 199086002, 199090000, 199605001, 199606000, 199609007, 237245006, 240400006, 267187007, 267191002, 267294003, 267299008, 268574009, 275425008, 276507005, 2781009, 34270000, 34614007, 35999006, 428593008, 43306002, 54726000, 58990004, 609525000, 6176008, 76358005, 77846006, 84122000
Still birth	ICD10	P95
Still birth	ICD10CM	P95

Still birth	ICD9	656.4, 768.0, 768.1
Still birth	RCD2	L264, L2640, L264z, Q48D
Still birth	SNOMED	156184005, 157167009, 198901003, 199605001, 199606000, 199609007, 206581002, 206583004, 237364002, 237366000, 268887007, 276507005, 309759009, 45513003, 76358005, 7860005, 84122000
Still birth	SNOMEDCT_US	156184005, 157167009, 198901003, 199605001, 199606000, 199609007, 206581002, 206583004, 237364002, 237366000, 268887007, 276507005, 309759009, 45513003, 76358005, 7860005, 84122000
TOPFA	ICD10	P96.4, Q89.9
TOPFA	ICD10CM	Q89.9
TOPFA	ICD9	740, 740.0, 740.1, 740.2, 741, 741.0, 741.9, 742, 742.0, 742.1, 742.2, 742.3, 742.4, 742.5, 742.8, 742.9, 743, 743.0, 743.1, 743.2, 743.3, 743.4, 743.5, 743.6, 743.8, 743.9, 744, 744.0, 744.1, 744.2, 744.3, 744.4, 744.5, 744.8, 744.9, 745, 745.0, 745.1, 745.2, 745.3, 745.4, 745.5, 745.6, 745.7, 745.8, 745.9, 746, 746.0, 746.1, 746.2, 746.3, 746.4, 746.5, 746.6, 746.7, 746.8, 746.9, 747, 747.0, 747.1, 747.2, 747.3, 747.4, 747.5, 747.6, 747.8, 747.9, 748, 748.0, 748.1, 748.2, 748.3, 748.4, 748.5, 748.6, 748.8, 748.9, 749, 749.0, 749.1, 749.2, 750, 750.0, 750.1, 750.2, 750.3, 750.4, 750.5, 750.6, 750.7, 750.8, 750.9, 751, 751.0, 751.1, 751.2, 751.3, 751.4, 751.5, 751.6, 751.7, 751.8, 751.9, 752, 752.0, 752.1, 752.2, 752.3, 752.4, 752.5, 752.6, 752.7, 752.8, 752.9, 753, 753.0, 753.1, 753.2, 753.3, 753.4, 753.5, 753.6, 753.7, 753.8, 753.9, 754, 754.0, 754.1, 754.2, 754.3, 754.4, 754.5, 754.6, 754.7, 754.8, 755, 755.0, 755.1, 755.2, 755.3, 755.4, 755.5, 755.6, 755.8, 755.9, 756, 756.0, 756.1, 756.2, 756.3, 756.4, 756.5, 756.6, 756.7, 756.8, 756.9, 757, 757.0, 757.1, 757.2, 757.3, 757.4, 757.5, 757.6, 757.8, 757.9, 758, 758.0, 758.1, 758.2, 758.3, 758.4, 758.5, 758.6, 758.7, 758.8, 758.9, 759, 759.0, 759.1, 759.2, 759.3, 759.4, 759.5, 759.6, 759.7, 759.8, 759.9
TOPFA	ICD9CM	740.00, 740.01, 740.02, 740.03, 740.04, 740.05, 740.06, 740.07, 740.08, 740.09, 740.10, 740.11, 740.12, 740.13, 740.14, 740.15, 740.16, 740.17, 740.18, 740.19, 740.20, 740.21, 740.22, 740.23, 740.24, 740.25, 740.26, 740.27, 740.28, 740.29, 740.30, 740.31, 740.32, 740.33, 740.34, 740.35, 740.36, 740.37, 740.38, 740.39, 740.40, 740.41, 740.42, 740.43, 740.44, 740.45, 740.46, 740.47, 740.48, 740.49, 740.50, 740.51, 740.52, 740.53, 740.54, 740.55, 740.56, 740.57, 740.58, 740.59, 740.60, 740.61, 740.62, 740.63, 740.64, 740.65, 740.66, 740.67, 740.68, 740.69, 740.70, 740.71, 740.72, 740.73, 740.74, 740.75, 740.76, 740.77, 740.78, 740.79, 740.80, 740.81, 740.82, 740.83, 740.84, 740.85, 740.86, 740.87, 740.88, 740.89, 740.90, 740.91, 740.92, 740.93, 740.94, 740.95, 740.96, 740.97, 740.98, 740.99, 741.00, 741.01, 741.02, 741.03, 741.04, 741.05, 741.06, 741.07, 741.08, 741.09, 741.10, 741.11, 741.12, 741.13, 741.14, 741.15, 741.16, 741.17, 741.18, 741.19, 741.20, 741.21, 741.22, 741.23, 741.24, 741.25, 741.26, 741.27, 741.28, 741.29, 741.30, 741.31, 741.32, 741.33, 741.34, 741.35, 741.36, 741.37, 741.38, 741.39, 741.40, 741.41, 741.42, 741.43, 741.44, 741.45, 741.46, 741.47, 741.48, 741.49, 741.50, 741.51, 741.52, 741.53, 741.54, 741.55, 741.56, 741.57, 741.58, 741.59, 741.60, 741.61, 741.62, 741.63, 741.64, 741.65, 741.66, 741.67, 741.68, 741.69, 741.70, 741.71, 741.72, 741.73, 741.74, 741.75, 741.76, 741.77, 741.78, 741.79, 741.80, 741.81, 741.82, 741.83, 741.84, 741.85, 741.86, 741.87, 741.88, 741.89, 741.90, 741.91, 741.92, 741.93, 741.94, 741.95, 741.96, 741.97, 741.98, 741.99, 742.00, 742.01, 742.02, 742.03, 742.04, 742.05, 742.06, 742.07, 742.08, 742.09, 742.10, 742.11, 742.12, 742.13, 742.14, 742.15, 742.16, 742.17, 742.18, 742.19, 742.20, 742.21, 742.22, 742.23, 742.24, 742.25, 742.26, 742.27, 742.28, 742.29, 742.30, 742.31, 742.32, 742.33, 742.34, 742.35, 742.36, 742.37, 742.38, 742.39, 742.40, 742.41, 742.42, 742.43, 742.44, 742.45, 742.46, 742.47, 742.48, 742.49, 742.50, 742.51, 742.52, 742.53, 742.54, 742.55, 742.56, 742.57, 742.58, 742.59, 742.60, 742.61, 742.62, 742.63, 742.64, 742.65, 742.66, 742.67, 742.68, 742.69, 742.70, 742.71, 742.72, 742.73, 742.74, 742.75, 742.76, 742.77, 742.78, 742.79, 742.80, 742.81, 742.82, 742.83, 742.84, 742.85, 742.86, 742.87, 742.88, 742.89, 742.90, 742.91, 742.92, 742.93, 742.94, 742.95, 742.96, 742.97, 742.98, 742.99, 743.00, 743.01, 743.02, 743.03, 743.04, 743.05, 743.06, 743.07, 743.08, 743.09, 743.10, 743.11, 743.12, 743.13, 743.14, 743.15, 743.16, 743.17, 743.18, 743.19, 743.20, 743.21, 743.22, 743.23, 743.24, 743.25, 743.26, 743.27, 743.28, 743.29, 743.30, 743.31, 743.32, 743.33, 743.34, 743.35, 743.36, 743.37, 743.38, 743.39, 743.40, 743.41, 743.42, 743.43, 743.44, 743.45, 743.46, 743.47, 743.48, 743.49, 743.50, 743.51, 743.52, 743.53, 743.54, 743.55, 743.56, 743.57, 743.58, 743.59, 743.60, 743.61, 743.62, 743.63, 743.64, 743.65, 743.66, 743.67, 743.68, 743.69, 743.70, 743.71, 743.72, 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TOPFA	ICPC	D81, N85, W83
TOPFA	MTHICD9	69.51
TOPFA	RCD2	P, Pz
TOPFA	SNOMED	107656002, 112635002, 1321008, 156075007, 157028001, 157033002, 157034008, 198690009, 205842001, 205999005, 21390004, 267295002, 268359006, 276654001, 276655000, 385297003, 386641000, 443341004, 57797005, 66091009
TOPFA	SNOMEDCT_US	107656002, 112635002, 1321008, 156075007, 157028001, 157033002, 157034008, 198690009, 205842001, 205999005, 21390004, 267295002, 268359006, 276654001, 276655000, 385297003, 386641000, 443341004, 57797005, 66091009

event_definition	event_abbreviation	coding_system	code_original
ongoing_pregnancy	24weeksUNK	ICD10CM	Z3A.24
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10	O32.4
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10	O60.2
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10	O60.20
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10	O60.22
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10	O60.23
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX0
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX1
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX2
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX3
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX4
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX5
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O32.4XX9
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O60.2
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O60.20
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O60.22
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD10CM	O60.23
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD9CM	652.5
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD9CM	652.5
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD9CM	652.51
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	ICD9CM	652.53
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	MTHICD9	652.5
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	MTHICD9	652.5
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	MTHICD9	652.51
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	MTHICD9	652.53
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L227.
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L2270
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L2271
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L2272
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L227z
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	RCD2	L3982
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	17333005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	199373000
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	199375007
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	199376008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	200147006
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	21127004

end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	21243004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	23667007
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	299124003
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	302253005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	440425000
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	50758004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	52483005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	52942000
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	75697004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	7888004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	83121003
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	8333008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	86803008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	87527008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SCTSPA	9343003
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	17333005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	199375007
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	199376008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	200147006
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	21127004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	21243004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	23667007
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	299124003
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	302253005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	440425000
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	50758004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	52483005
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	52942000
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	7888004
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	8333008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	86803008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	87527008
end_of_pregnancy	AtTerm	SNOMEDCT_US	9343003
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	N85.5
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O32.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O32.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.0
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.00
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.01
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.02
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.1

end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.10
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.11
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.12
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.90
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.91
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O42.92
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O60.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O60.10
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O60.12
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O60.13
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O60.14
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O61
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O61.0
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O61.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O61.8
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O61.9
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.0
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.4
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.8
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O62.9
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end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O63.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O63.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O63.9
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.0
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.4
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.5
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.8
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O64.9
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end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.1
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.4

end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.5
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O65.8
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end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.4
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.40
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.41
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.5
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O66.6
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end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O68.9
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O69.0
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end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O69.2
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O69.3
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O69.4
end_of_pregnancy	BirthNarrow	ICD10	O69.5
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible2	RCD2	L306z
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible2	RCD2	L310z
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible2	RCD2	L311z
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible2	RCD2	L352z
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible2	SCTSPA	199785006
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible3	SCTSPA	49756002
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ongoing_pregnancy	BirthPossible3	SNOMEDCT_US	64177003
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interruption_pregnancy	SpontaneousAbortion	RCD	L0426
interruption_pregnancy	SpontaneousAbortion	RCD	L042x
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end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	646
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	646.03
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	651.4
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	656.4
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	656.4
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	656.41

end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	656.43
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	V27.1
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	V27.3
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	V27.4
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	MTHICD9	V27.7
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	6332
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	L160.
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	L1600
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	L1601
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	L160z
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	X40E0
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	X40E3
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	X40E5
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	X70EM
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	XE0ve
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	XaC1G
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	ZV271
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD	ZV276
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	6332
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L160.
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L1600
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L1601
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L160z
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L264.
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L2640
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L2641
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	L264z
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	Q486.
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	Q48D.
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	RCD2	Q4z..
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	10588007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	14022007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	16607004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169827000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169829002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169830007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169832004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169833009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	169834003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	1762004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	17766007

end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	198901003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199068000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199069008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199071008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199605001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199606000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199607009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199608004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	199609007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	206258000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	206259008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	22514005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237361005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237362003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237363008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237364002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237365001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	237366000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	276503009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	276505002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	276506001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	276507005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	28996007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	30165006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	309759009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	315959000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	315964001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	316756005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	35608009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	3798002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	38257001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	38651009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	391181005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	39213008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	399363000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	408796008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	414249001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	44174001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	445548006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	445862009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	445868008

end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	446035009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	45513003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	54650005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	67313008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	68509000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	70112005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	713202001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	72543004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	7428005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	762612009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	762613004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	762614005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	76358005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	77714001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	77814006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	7860005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	84122000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	84382006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SCTSPA	90127001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	F31660
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	F33820
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	F35250
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	F35260
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	M28110
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	M28130
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNM	M28140
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	10588007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	14022007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	147058004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	156087000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	156131006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	156184005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	157167009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	16607004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	169827000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	1762004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	17766007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	198616002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	198901003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199068000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199069008

end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199071008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199605001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199606000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199607009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199608004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	199609007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206258000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206259008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206574009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206581002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206583004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	206602000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	237361005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	237362003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	237363008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	237364002
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	237366000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	267187007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	267314000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	268887007
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	276503009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	276507005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	309759009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	315959000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	315964001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	38651009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	399363000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	414249001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	44174001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	445548006
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	445862009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	445868008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	446035009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	45513003
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	67313008
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	713202001
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	72543004
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	740597009
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	7428005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	76358005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	77714001

end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	7860005
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	84122000
end_of_pregnancy	StillBirth	SNOMEDCT_US	90127001

Pregnancy Codelist used by FERR, RDRU_FISABIO, THL, PHARMO, UOSL and USWAN**Pregnancy Codelist used by BPE, ARS, CNR, SIDIAP, and CHUT**

event_definition	coding_system	event_abbreviation	code
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P21,P84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P10,P11,P12,P13,P14,P15
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O88.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O42
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P53
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.70
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P96.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P39.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P07.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P29.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O72
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P22
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P35.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P83.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O60
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		R04.89
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O66.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		L53.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O44.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O46.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O46.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O15.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O15.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O75.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O66.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O72.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O73
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O73.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O75.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O87
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O86.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O88.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01

end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P08.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P08.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P21.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P22.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P38
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P39.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P39
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P50
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P55.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P59.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P59
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P70.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P72.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P74.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P61.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P60
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P61.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P61.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P61.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P78.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P76.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P78.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P78.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P80,P81,P82,P83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P80.0

end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P80.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P90
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P92
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P96.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O90.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		N85.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O72.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.81
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P39.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z39
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z39.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O46.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O61.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O60,O61,O62,O63,O64,O65,O66,O67,O68,O69,O70,O71,O72,O73,O74,O75,O76,O77
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O66.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O70.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O70.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O70.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O72.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O73.0

end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O85
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O91.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O91.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O92.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P96.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P07.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P13.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P11.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P54.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P55.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P57.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P76.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P78.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P61.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P37.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O71.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O24
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O14.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O87.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O22.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		A33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P76.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O62.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P11.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P01.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P00.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P56.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P27
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P21.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O62.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O72.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P51

end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P26
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O62.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O87.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P02.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P08.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P15.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P83.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O75.6,O42.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O75.6,O42.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O62.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O66.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O87.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P03.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P04.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P74.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z38.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z39.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P28.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		E84.11,P76.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P91.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O90.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P29.11
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O48
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P96.83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P29.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P96.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O70.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z37.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		L40.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P29.81

end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P83.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O98.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P24.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P24.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P77.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P77
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P91.61
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P91.62
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P91.63
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P92.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P92.09
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O86.81
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P08.22
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P77.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P77.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		P77.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O75.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		O90.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		65.220.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		673.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		658.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		656
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		776
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		766.21
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V20.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.420.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.129.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		641.3,641.33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		641.3,641.33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.179.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		641.8,641.83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		641.8,641.83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.270.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.641.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.720.000.000.000.000

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.780.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.870.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		65.129.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		65.270.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		65.379.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		65.470.000.000.000.000
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		666.3,666.34
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		668.81,668.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		668.81,668.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.42,676.44
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.42,676.44
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.52,676.54
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.52,676.54
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.82,676.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.82,676.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.8,771.89
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.8,771.89
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		6,71E+14
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		666.1,666.14
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V24
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V24.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V24.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V30.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V30.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V30.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V30.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V32.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V33.00

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V33.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V33.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V34.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V35.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V36
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V36.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V36.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V36.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V36.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V37.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39.00
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V39.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		792.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		648.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		659
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		665.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		665.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		671.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		674.24
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.5

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		676.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.6
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.4
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		773.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		773.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		774.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		776.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		648
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		648.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		648.02
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		648.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		642
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.23
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.24
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		654.21
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		657.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		659.61
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		669.43
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		672.02
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		672.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		677
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.76
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V29.2

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		646.71
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		653.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		658.91
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		659.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		675.14
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		761.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		761.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		761.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.4
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		773.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		646.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		644.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		644
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		666.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		661.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		671.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		762.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		762.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		762.6
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		766.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		767.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		778.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V30.2
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V31
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.21
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		647.22
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		664.14

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V29.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		671.24
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.9
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		775.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V33.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V24.0
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		277.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		655.71
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		655.73
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		659.71
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		659.73
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.81
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.83
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		660.41
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.7
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		674.5
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.30
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.31
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.32
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.34
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V21.35
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		645
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.11
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.13
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		772.14
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.81
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.89
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.81

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		771.83
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		645.11
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.520.000.000.000.000
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		674.54
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.83
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.0,V30
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.0,V30
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V27.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		694.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		650
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.85
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		778.7
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.71
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.77
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		760.78
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		763.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.11
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.13
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.15
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.16
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.17
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.18
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.85
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.02
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.03
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.1
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.11
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.13

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.14
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.34
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.53
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		649.64
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.3
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		775.81
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		775.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		665.03
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		664.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		674.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		766
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		770.88
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		678.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		678.03
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.01
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.02
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.03
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.04
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.12
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		679.14
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.5
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.14
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.34
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.8
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.82
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		670.84
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.71
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.72
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		768.73
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.32
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.33
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V20.31
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V20.32
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V20.3

end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		779.3
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end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.51
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.52
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		777.53
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		786.31
end_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		64.980.999.999.999.900
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A94003
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W84027
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A94018
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W19010
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A94023
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W17001,W17002
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W17001,W17002
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A74004
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W92020
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W19012
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		S06003
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W99002
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A94021
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		R04015
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		A94015,
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W03001,W03004
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W03001,W03004
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W92002
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W92008,
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W70002
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W70001
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W19011
end_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		X21013
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa08o,XE1el
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa08o,XE1el
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q20...,Q20z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q20...,Q20z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L281.,X40Bg,L2810,L281z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2600,L260z,L260.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2600,L260z,L260.

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2600,L260z,L260.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q450.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0Kb,Xa09e
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0Kb,Xa09e
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		X40Ag
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q485.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q406z,Q406.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q406z,Q406.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu11
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q493.,X2001
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q493.,X2001
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L36.,L36z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L36.,L36z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1em
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1er
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q471.,Q471z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q471.,Q471z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L23.,Xa0lv
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L23.,Xa0lv
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L142z,XE2QQ,Xa1xq
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L142z,XE2QQ,Xa1xq
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L142z,XE2QQ,Xa1xq
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0zJ,R0631,X1059
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0zJ,R0631,X1059
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0zJ,R0631,X1059
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		X50C2
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vo
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L111.,L1110,L111z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L111.,L1110,L111z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L111.,L1110,L111z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vq,L1130,L113z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vq,L1130,L113z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vq,L1130,L113z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L11y.,L11y0,L11yz,Lyu3E
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		642.61
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1263
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa9FQ
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		647.5
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QT,L22z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QT,L22z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2201
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2271
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2321
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2331
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2371
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2431
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2801
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2811
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2951
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L307.,L307z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L307.,L307z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L30y.,L30yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L30y.,L30yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3101
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x2
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x6,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x6,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x6,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3541
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xA,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xA,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xA,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L40z.,L40z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L40z.,L40z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XaBMD
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XaBML
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L42...,L4200
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L42...,L4200
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xM,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xM,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xM,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xN,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xN,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xN,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2sl,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2sl,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2sl,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xP,XE0xQ
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xP,XE0xQ
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Lyu68
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4641
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4642,L4644
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4642,L4644
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4643
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4651
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4652,L4654
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4652,L4654
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4653
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QZ,L46y0,L46yz,Lyu69
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46y1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46y4,L46y2
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46y4,L46y2
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L46y3

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q01...,Q01z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q01...,Q01z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q020.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q023.,Q023z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q023.,Q023z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q024.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q027.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1eO
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q032.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q033.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q034.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q036.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1eR,Q037z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1eR,Q037z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa09U,Xa09T
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa09U,Xa09T
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa09a,L2660,L266z,L2661,Q120.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa9D9,Xa3wl
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa9D9,Xa3wl
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q31..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu37
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q316.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1et,Xa4Ua
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1et,Xa4Ua
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q405.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu45
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q410.,Q4100,Q410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q410.,Q4100,Q410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q410.,Q4100,Q410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q41yy
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1f3
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q43..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q430z,Q430.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q430z,Q430.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q432.,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q433.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q434.,Q434z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q434.,Q434z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q441.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q442.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q443.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q447.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q448.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q451z,Q451.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q451z,Q451.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q452.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu5D,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q456.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q457z,Q457.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q457z,Q457.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q46z.,Q46..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q46z.,Q46..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q463.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q465.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu72
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu8.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q472.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q473.,Qyu80
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q473.,Qyu80
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q474.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q480.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q483.,XE1fD,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q483.,XE1fD,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q483.,XE1fD,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		QyuA3
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4z.,L4...,L44z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4z.,L4...,L44z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4z.,L4...,L44z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L361.,L3610,L361z,Lyu4D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q40y1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV24.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV242

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV310
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV32.,ZV32z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV32.,ZV32z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV320
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		4H13.,R123.,XM09H
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		4H13.,R123.,XM09H
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		4H13.,R123.,XM09H
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0kf,L11zz,L11z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0kf,L11zz,L11z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0kf,L11zz,L11z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		X40AZ
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L182.,L182z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L182.,L182z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L229.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2900,L290z,L290.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2900,L290z,L290.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L2900,L290z,L290.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3...,L39z0,L3z...,Lyu4.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L35z.,L35z0,X40DI
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L35z.,L35z0,X40DI
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L35z.,L35z0,X40DI
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L344.,L3440,L344z,X40DR,X76WF
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x3,L340z,L3400
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x3,L340z,L3400
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x3,L340z,L3400
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x4,L341z,L3410
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x4,L341z,L3410
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x4,L341z,L3410
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x5,L342z,L3420
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x5,L342z,L3420
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0x5,L342z,L3420

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3560,L356z,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3560,L356z,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3570,L357z,L357.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3570,L357z,L357.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3570,L357z,L357.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3600,L360z,XE0x9
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3600,L360z,XE0x9
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3600,L360z,XE0x9
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3700,XE0xD,XE0xC
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3700,XE0xD,XE0xC
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3700,XE0xD,XE0xC
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xH,L403.,L403z,L4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xI,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xI,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xI,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu0A
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2R6,Qzâ€†
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2R6,Qzâ€†
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0AU
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q201.,Q201z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q201.,Q201z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q202.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q31z.,Q3â€†
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q31z.,Q3â€†
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2nT,Xa07d
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2nT,Xa07d
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q314.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0ml
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q411.

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q421.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q424.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q436.,Q436z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q436.,Q436z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q4660,XE1f9
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q4660,XE1f9
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q462.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q484.,Q484z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q484.,Q484z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q454z,Q454.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q454z,Q454.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QR,L175z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QR,L175z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q407.,Q407z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q407.,Q407z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L180.,L180z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L180.,L180z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1804
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1802
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1801
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L125.,L125z,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L125.,L125z,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L125.,L125z,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L292.,L292z,XE0z4
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L292.,L292z,XE0z4
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L292.,L292z,XE0z4
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xL,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xL,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xL,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q461.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1671
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L243.,L243z,L2430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L243.,L243z,L2430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L243.,L243z,L2430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L18..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0w4,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0w4,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0w4,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L236.,L2360,L236z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L236.,L2360,L236z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L236.,L2360,L236z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L28z1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L291z,L2910
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L291z,L2910
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4511
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q204.,Q204z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q204.,Q204z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q011.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q00.,Q00z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q00.,Q00z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1eB
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q002.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV274
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L220.,L2200,L220z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L220.,L2200,L220z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L220.,L2200,L220z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L227.,L2270,L227z,XE0ye
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L227.,L2270,L227z,XE0ye

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L227.,L2270,L227z,XE0ye
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L227.,L2270,L227z,XE0ye
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q470.,Xa07b
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q470.,Xa07b
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q423.,Xa07e
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q423.,Xa07e
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q317.,Q317z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q317.,Q317z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0AA,Xa9DA
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa0AA,Xa9DA
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L1612
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L140.,L1400,L140z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L140.,L1400,L140z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L140.,L1400,L140z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L31.,L31z.,L31z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L31.,L31z.,L31z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L31.,L31z.,L31z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q03..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q313z,Q313.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q313z,Q313.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0wx,L312z,Lyu41,L3120
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Lyu63
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Lyu71
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu05
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu06
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu07

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu09
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu12
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q20y.,XE1eh,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q20y.,XE1eh,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q20y.,XE1eh,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu38
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Qyu83
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV272
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV273
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV277,ZVu2C
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV277,ZVu2C
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV302
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV31.,ZV31z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV31.,ZV31z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0tU,L2815,L2823
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0tU,L2815,L2823
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XM0tU,L2815,L2823
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XaBMG
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Lyu70
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q446.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV330
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Xa086
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		C3701
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1ed
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q431.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q200.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L343.,L343z,L3430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L343.,L343z,L3430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L343.,L343z,L3430
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV270
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV271
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		M051.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE2QS
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		772.6
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		Q477.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L173.,L173z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L173.,L173z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1f2,Q41z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE1f2,Q41z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xJ,L4110,L411z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xJ,L4110,L411z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xJ,L4110,L411z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4420,L442z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD		L4420,L442z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q21z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q20...,Q20z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q20...,Q20z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L281.,L2810,L281z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L281.,L2810,L281z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L281.,L2810,L281z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L260z,L260.,L2600
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L260z,L260.,L2600
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L260z,L260.,L2600
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q450.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		6355
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46z.,L46z0,L46zz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		1522
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q485.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q406.,Q406z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q406.,Q406z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu11
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q493.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L36z.,L36..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L36z.,L36..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q30..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q471.,Q471z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q471.,Q471z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L23..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L142z,L142.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L142z,L142.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		R0631
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L30.,L30z.,L30z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L464.,L464z,L4640
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		M150.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L11..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L111.,L1110,L111z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L111.,L1110,L111z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L111.,L1110,L111z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L113.,L1130,L113z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L113.,L1130,L113z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L113.,L1130,L113z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L11y.,L11y0,L11yz,Lyu3E
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L122.,L1220,L122z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1263
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L22.,L22z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L22.,L22z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2201
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2271
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2321
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2331
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2371
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2431
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2801
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2811
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2951
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L307.,L307z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L307.,L307z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L30y.,L30yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L30y.,L30yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3101
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L34..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L345.,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L345.,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L345.,L3450,L345z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3541
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L363.,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L363.,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L363.,L3630,L363z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L39y.,L39y0,L39yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L391.,L3910,L391z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L40z.,L40z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L40z.,L40z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4106
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41y.,L41y0,L41yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41z6
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L42.,L4200
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L42.,L4200
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4311
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L433.,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L433.,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L433.,L4330,L433z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L43y.,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L43y.,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L43y.,L43y0,L43yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L440.,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L440.,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L440.,L4400,L440z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L44y.,L44yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L44y.,L44yz
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu68
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4641
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4642,L4644
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4642,L4644
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4643
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4651
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4652,L4654
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4652,L4654
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4653
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46y.,L46y0,L46yz,Lyu69
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46y1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46y2,L46y4
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46y2,L46y4

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L46y3
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q01...,Q01z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q01...,Q01z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q020.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q023.,Q023z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q023.,Q023z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q024.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q027.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q030.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q032.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q033.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q034.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q036.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q037.,Q037z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q037.,Q037z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2660,L266z,L2661,Q120.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q215.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q31..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu37
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q316.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q404.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q405.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu45
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q410.,Q410z,Q4100
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q410.,Q410z,Q4100
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q410.,Q410z,Q4100
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q41yy
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q420.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q43..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q430.,Q430z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q430.,Q430z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q432.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q433.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q434.,Q434z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q434.,Q434z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q441.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q442.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q443.

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q447.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q448.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q451.,Q451z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q451.,Q451z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q452.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu5D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q456.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q457.,Q457z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q457.,Q457z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q46.,Q46z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q46.,Q46z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q463.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q465.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu72
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu8.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q472.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q473.,Qyu80
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q473.,Qyu80
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q474.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q480.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q483.,Q483z,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q483.,Q483z,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q483.,Q483z,Q4830
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		QyuA3
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4...,L44z0,L4z..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4...,L44z0,L4z..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4...,L44z0,L4z..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L352.,L3520,L352z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L361.,L3610,L361z,Lyu4D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q40y1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV24.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV242
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV310
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV32.,ZV32z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV32.,ZV32z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV320

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		4H13.,R123.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		4H13.,R123.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L11z0,L11zz,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L11z0,L11zz,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L182.,L182z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L182.,L182z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L229.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L290.,L2900,L290z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L290.,L2900,L290z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L290.,L2900,L290z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3...,L39z0,L3z...,Lyu4.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3050,L305z,L305.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L35z.,L35z0,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L35z.,L35z0,
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L344.,L3440,L344z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L344.,L3440,L344z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L344.,L3440,L344z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L340.,L3400,L340z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L340.,L3400,L340z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L340.,L3400,L340z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L341.,L3410,L341z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L341.,L3410,L341z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L341.,L3410,L341z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L342.,L3420,L342z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L342.,L3420,L342z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L342.,L3420,L342z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3560,L356z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3560,L356z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L357.,L3570,L357z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L357.,L3570,L357z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L357.,L3570,L357z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L360.,L3600,L360z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L360.,L3600,L360z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L360.,L3600,L360z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L370.,L3700,L370z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L370.,L3700,L370z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L370.,L3700,L370z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L400.,L400z,L4000
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L403.,L403z,L40.,L4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41.,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41.,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L41.,L41z.,L41z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L412.,L4120,L412z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L465.,L465z,L4650
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu0A
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qz...,Q....
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qz...,Q....
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q112.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q201.,Q201z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q201.,Q201z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q202.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q3...,Q31z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q3...,Q31z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q31y1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q314.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q41..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q411.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q421.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q424.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q436.,Q436z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q436.,Q436z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q466z,Q4660
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q466z,Q4660
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q462.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q484.,Q484z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q484.,Q484z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q454z,Q454.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q454z,Q454.

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L175.,L175z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L175.,L175z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q407.,Q407z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q407.,Q407z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L180.,L180z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L180.,L180z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1804
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1802
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1801
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L120.,L1200,L120z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L125z,L125.,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L125z,L125.,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L125z,L125.,L1250
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L292.,L292z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L292.,L292z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L415.,L4150,L415z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L414.,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L414.,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L414.,L4140,L414z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L410.,L4100,L410z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q403z,Q403.,Q4030
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q461.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1671
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L243.,L2430,L243z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L243.,L2430,L243z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L243.,L2430,L243z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L18..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L237.,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L237.,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L237.,L2370,L237z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L236.,L2360,L236z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L236.,L2360,L236z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L236.,L2360,L236z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L28z1
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L311.,L311z,L3110
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L3060,L306z,L306.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2910,L291z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2910,L291z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4511
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q204.,Q204z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q204.,Q204z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q011.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q014.,Q0140,Q014z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q015.,Q0150,Q015z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q00.,Q00z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q00.,Q00z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q000.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q002.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV274
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2200,L220z,L220.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2200,L220z,L220.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2200,L220z,L220.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L227.,L2270,L227z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L227.,L2270,L227z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L227.,L2270,L227z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q470.,Q479.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q470.,Q479.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q423.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q317.,Q317z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q317.,Q317z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q216.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L1612
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L141.,L1410,L141z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L140.,L1400,L140z

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L140.,L1400,L140z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L140.,L1400,L140z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L31z.,L31z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L31z.,L31z0
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L313.,L3130,L313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L362.,L3620,L362z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q413.,Q4130,Q413z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q03..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q313.,Q313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q313.,Q313z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L312.,L312z,Lyu41,L3120
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu63
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu71
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu05
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu06
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu07
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu09
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu12
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q20y.,Q20yz,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q20y.,Q20yz,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q20y.,Q20yz,Qyu25
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu38
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Qyu83
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV272
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV273
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV277,ZVu2C
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV277,ZVu2C
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV302
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV31.,ZV31z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV31.,ZV31z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2815,L282.,L2823
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2815,L282.,L2823

end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L2815,L282.,L2823
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4126
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu70
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q446.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV330
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q319.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		C3701
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q203.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q431.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q200.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L343.,L3430,L343z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L343.,L3430,L343z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L343.,L3430,L343z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV270
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV271
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		M143.,M051.,M161D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		M143.,M051.,M161D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		M143.,M051.,M161D
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L20.,Ly0..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L20.,Ly0..
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q477.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L173.,L173z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L173.,L173z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		Q41z.
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L411.,L4110,L411z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L411.,L4110,L411z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L411.,L4110,L411z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4420,L442z
end_of_pregnancy	RCD2		L4420,L442z
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157098009,206278008,268831004,28314004,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157089006,157097004,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157089006,157097004,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		306727001
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		17263003
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156189000,156191008,199657001,199663005,237266003,

end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156189000,156191008,199657001,199663005,237266003,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199576009,199579002,206392000,24141009,71028008,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		12546009
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		147079004,147084005,16207008,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		147079004,147084005,16207008,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		147079004,147084005,16207008,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		200459001,200460006,200465001,35046003,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		138997008
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		414819007,61628006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		414819007,61628006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		206345004,206354001,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		206345004,206354001,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		206621008
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		204507004,206597007,233815004,35604006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156239004,156243000,47821001,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156239004,156243000,47821001,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156239004,156243000,47821001,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157107007,206281003,3774009,46775006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157117002,206332003,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		157117002,206332003,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		2.06539E+25
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		2.06539E+25
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		2.06539E+25
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156162005,199397009,25749005,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156162005,199397009,25749005,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		156162005,199397009,25749005,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199056009,199059002,270496001,282020008,49550006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199056009,199059002,270496001,282020008,49550006,

end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199056009,199059002,270496001,282020008,49550006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199056009,199059002,270496001,282020008,49550006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		199056009,199059002,270496001,282020008,49550006,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		158386009,207070002,274252009,78144005,
end_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		111448009,156209009,199813003,
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interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W73002
interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W80001
interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W80003
interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W92009
interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W83003
interruption_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W83002
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L04z.,L040.,L040z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L04z.,L040.,L040z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L04z.,L040.,L040z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vl,L060.,L06z.,L060z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0ve
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vp,L112z,L1120
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vp,L112z,L1120
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0vp,L112z,L1120
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L000.,BBR0.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L000.,BBR0.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L030.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L03..,L03z.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L03..,L03z.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L032.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L031.,L031z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L031.,L031z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L310.,L310z,L3100

interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L310.,L310z,L3100
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L310.,L310z,L3100
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L4440,L444z,L444.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L4440,L444z,L444.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L4440,L444z,L444.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L040w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L041w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L040x
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L041x
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L042x
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L040y
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0520
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0521
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0525
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0526
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L050w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L051w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L052w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L052x
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L050y
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L060w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L061w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L062w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L10z.,L10z0,L10..
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L10z.,L10z0,L10..
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L10z.,L10z0,L10..
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L35...,L35yz,L35y0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L35...,L35yz,L35y0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L35...,L35yz,L35y0
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L353.,L3530,L353z

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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		Lyu4J
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xO,L4430,L443z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xO,L4430,L443z
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0423
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L0413
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		B911z,B911.
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L051y
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L041y
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L052y
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		L050.,L050z,L05z.,XE0vi
interruption_pregnancy	RCD		XE0xa
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L04z.,L04..,L040.,L040z

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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L06.,L060.,L06z.,L060z
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L02.,L011.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L112.,L112z,L1120
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L112.,L112z,L1120
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L112.,L112z,L1120
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L00.,BBR0.,L000.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L00.,BBR0.,L000.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L03y.,L03yz,Lyu00
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L030.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L03.,L03z.
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L03.,L03z.
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L031.,L031z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L031.,L031z
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L061w
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L062w
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L10..,L10z.,L10z0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L35..,L35yz,L35y0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L35..,L35yz,L35y0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L35..,L35yz,L35y0
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L353.,L3530,L353z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L353.,L3530,L353z
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu4C
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		Lyu4J
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L443.,L4430,L443z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L443.,L4430,L443z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L443.,L4430,L443z
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L060y
interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L050x
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L060x
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L0603

interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		L0604
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interruption_pregnancy	RCD2		B911.,B911z
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		L08x.
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		ZV28.,ZV28z
ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		ZVu26
ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		ZVu28
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		ZV74.
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		XE0y2,L13z.,L13z0,L13zz
ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		XE0y2,L13z.,L13z0,L13zz

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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		L413.,L4130,L413z
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		L08.,L08z.
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD		L131.,L131z,L1310
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD2		L100z,L100.,L1000
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ongoing_pregnancy	RCD2		Q42.,Q422.,Q42z.
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ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156172008,199481003,199486008,36836005,

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		111468003,123307003,157130001,206429000,206431009,206436004,25121006,387705004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		12867002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156185006,206166000,22033007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156185006,206166000,22033007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156185006,206166000,22033007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1.56188E+70
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		14094001,156113005,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		14094001,156113005,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156114004,199024002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156114004,199024002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316385002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156150006,156154002,199338002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156150006,156154002,199338002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156150006,156154002,199338002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156122006,199062004,199065002,199066001,90968009,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315901007,315904004,316748007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315901007,315904004,316748007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315901007,315904004,316748007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156190009,199652007,199656005,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156190009,199652007,199656005,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156190009,199652007,199656005,

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156151005,199316004,199319006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156151005,199316004,199319006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156151005,199316004,199319006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1.56152E+34
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156153008,199324009,199327002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156153008,199324009,199327002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156153008,199324009,199327002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198613005,198615003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198613005,198615003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		26623000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		29421008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		5939002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		67042008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		13943000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198814001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198815000,59919008,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198815000,59919008,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		111434009
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198883001,71115004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198883001,71115004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		111435005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156099007,198898004,198902005,7792000,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156116002,199031003,199034006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156116002,199031003,199034006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156116002,199031003,199034006,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199032005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200497001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199042007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199046005,199060007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199046005,199060007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1.56131E+52

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1.56131E+52
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199072001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199079005,199080008,199085003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199079005,199080008,199085003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199079005,199080008,199085003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156127000,199098007,199103009,267312001,31563000,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156128005,199105002,199115008,267204006,63020008,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		15230009,199116009,199119002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		15230009,199116009,199119002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		15230009,199116009,199119002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156135002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199250005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199317008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199321001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199325005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156165007,199421000,199424008,31805001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199482005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		66064007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		3554000,397949005,398276003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		3554000,397949005,398276003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		3554000,397949005,398276003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		22173004
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199677008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199717006,199720003,29399001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199717006,199720003,29399001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199717006,199720003,29399001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200210002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		206012006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		18471004,206162003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		18471004,206162003,

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		157118007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		72892002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315900008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315907006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316750004
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315968003,315976001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315968003,315976001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316751000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316753002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315975002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316604008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198816004,90645002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		198816004,90645002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		7822001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156108006,198972006,198973001,198980004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156113005,156117006,199040004,199041000,199045009,90325002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		40096002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		27342004
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156107001,198964009,198971004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156107001,198964009,198971004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156107001,198964009,198971004,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200110006,200115001,88887003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200110006,200115001,88887003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200110006,200115001,88887003,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156268003,200231004,200234007,49956009,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200228000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1.56078E+34
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		72860003

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199687007,199688002,199691002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199687007,199688002,199691002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199687007,199688002,199691002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		17787002,199092008,199097002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		17787002,199092008,199097002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		17787002,199092008,199097002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199025001,199026000,199029007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199025001,199026000,199029007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		199025001,199026000,199029007,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316597000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315903005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		156248009,200098002,200103000,87383005,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200498006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315912007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		200274001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		144196006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315947004
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316381006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		315899003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		147035002,313178001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		147035002,313178001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		147036001,313179009,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		147036001,313179009,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		267316003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316383009
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		189445003,267258002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		189445003,267258002,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		20011004,206165001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		20011004,206165001,
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		430933008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		16756008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		54048003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		6383007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		720406004
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		17382005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		161805006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		275412000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		721153000

ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		11687002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		241491007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		237285000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		77376005
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		424525001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		609496007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		8,28E+13
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		307534009
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		36813001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		135881001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		65147003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		58532003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		289830002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		1,71E+11
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		713117007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		430881000
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		86081009
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		173300003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		40609001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		9,12E+12
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		83620003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		717696001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		16356006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		51885006
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		422587007
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		289261003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		125586008
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		169588002
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		384634009
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		44795003
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		237284001
ongoing_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		422400008
start_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		N91.2
start_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		Z3A
start_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		
start_of_pregnancy	ICD10CM		
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		626
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		69.92
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V72.42
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		V72.40

start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		765.2
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		
start_of_pregnancy	ICD9CM		
start_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		X05001
start_of_pregnancy	ICPC2P		W59002
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		K590.,K590z
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		K590.,K590z
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		XE0hz
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		X76xx
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		ZV724
start_of_pregnancy	RCD		X76Qv
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		K590.,K590z
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		K590.,K590z
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		8C81.
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		6211
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		ZV724
start_of_pregnancy	RCD2		62X..
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		14302001,156037007,
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		14302001,156037007,
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		58533008
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		250423000
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		316583008
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		6099009
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		74036000
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		250421003
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMED		102874004
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		14302001,156037007,
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		14302001,156037007,
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		58533008
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		250423000
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		316583008
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		6099009
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		74036000
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		250421003
start_of_pregnancy	SNOMEDCT_US		102874004

8. Annex II Incidence rates for condition of interest

event_defii	year	age_band	IR	DEAP
ADHD	2011	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2012	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2013	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2014	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2015	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2016	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2017	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2018	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2019	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2020	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2021	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2009	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2010	0-11	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2021	12-19	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2005	30-39	0	UOSL
ADHD	2006	30-39	0	UOSL
ADHD	2007	30-39	0	UOSL
ADHD	2008	30-39	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2009	30-39	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2009	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2010	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2011	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2012	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2013	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2014	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2015	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2016	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2017	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2018	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2019	40-49	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2019	50-55	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2020	50-55	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2021	50-55	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2005	0-11	0	UOSL
ADHD	2006	0-11	0	UOSL
ADHD	2007	0-11	0	UOSL
ADHD	2008	0-11	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2008	12-19	0.02	UOSL
ADHD	2009	12-19	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2010	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2011	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2012	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2013	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2014	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2015	12-19	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2016	12-19	0.001	UOSL

ADHD	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2021 20-29	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
ADHD	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
ADHD	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
ADHD	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2017 12-19	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2018 12-20	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2005 12-21	0 UOSL
ADHD	2006 12-22	0 UOSL
ADHD	2007 12-23	0 UOSL
ADHD	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
ADHD	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
ADHD	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
ADHD	2008 20-29	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL

ADHD	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
ADHD	2019 12-19	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2020 12-19	0.01 UOSL
ADHD	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
ADHD	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
ADHD	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
ADHD	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
ADHD	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2010 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
ADHD	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
ADHD	2007 56+	0 UOSL
ADHD	2008 56+	0.001 UOSL
ADHD	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
ADHD	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
ADHD	2006 56+	0 UOSL
ADHD	2005 56+	0 UOSL
ADHD	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL

Autism	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Autism	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Autism	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2011 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2013 56+	0 UOSL

Autism	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2008 56+	0.001 UOSL
Autism	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Autism	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Autism	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Autism	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 50-55	0.02 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 56+	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 56+	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Breast canc	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL

Breast canc	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 56+	0.04 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 56+	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 56+	0.16 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 56+	0.03 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 56+	0.01 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 56+	0.18 UOSL
Breast canc	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2010 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2013 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2014 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2015 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL

Breast canc	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Depression	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 30-39	0.03 UOSL
Depression	2009 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2010 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2011 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2011 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2012 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2014 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2017 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2018 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2019 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2020 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2021 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2021 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 20-29	0.03 UOSL
Depression	2009 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2012 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2014 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2017 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2018 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2019 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2010 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2011 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2012 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2014 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2017 20-29	0.02 UOSL

Depression	2018 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2020 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2021 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2010 40-49	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2020 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 40-49	0.04 UOSL
Depression	2009 40-49	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2012 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2014 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2017 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2018 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2018 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2019 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2013 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2014 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2015 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2016 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2017 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2018 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2019 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2020 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2021 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2021 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2009 50-55	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2010 50-55	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2011 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2009 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2010 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2011 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2019 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2020 20-29	0.02 UOSL

Depression	2012 12-19	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 50-55	0.05 UOSL
Depression	2010 56+	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2011 56+	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2019 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2012 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Depression	2021 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2020 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Depression	2014 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2017 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013 56+	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Depression	2008 56+	0.09 UOSL
Depression	2009 56+	0.03 UOSL
Depression	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Depression	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Depression	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Depression	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Depression	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Depression	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Depression	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Depression	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 30-39	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL

Elective ab	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 20-29	0.03 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 20-29	0.03 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 20-29	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 20-29	0 UOSL

Elective ab	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 0-11	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL

Elective ab	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008 56+	0.001 UOSL
Elective ab	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL

Epilepsy	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Epilepsy	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 56+	0.02 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2008 0-11	0.01 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 40-49	0 UOSL

Epilepsy	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 12-19	0 UOSL

Gestationa	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL

Gestationa	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL

Major cong	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Major cong	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL

Major cong	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Major cong	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2008 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL

Major cong	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Major cong	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Major cong	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Migraine	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL

Migraine	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2016 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2017 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2018 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2019 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2020 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2020 20-29	0.01 UOSL

Migraine	2021 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Migraine	2021 12-19	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Migraine	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008 56+	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2009 56+	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Migraine	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Migraine	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL

Migraine	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Migraine	2010 56+	0.01 UOSL
Migraine	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Migraine	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Migraine	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL

Multiple ge	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL

Multiple ge	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL

Multiple sc	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Multiple sc	2008 50-55	0.01 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 56+	0.02 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL

Multiple sc	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2014 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 30-39	0 UOSL

Neonatal d	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2007 50-55	0 UOSL

Neonatal d	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2017 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 0-11	0 UOSL

Neonatal d	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Neonatal d	2021 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Neonatal d	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Preeclamps	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Preeclamps:	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013 50-55	0 UOSL

Preeclamps:	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2009 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2014 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2015 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL

Preterm bii	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL

Preterm bii	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 56+	0 UOSL

Preterm bii	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 40-49	0 UOSL

Rheumatoi	2008 40-49	0.01 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL

Rheumatoi	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 56+	0.04 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 50-55	0.02 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010 56+	0.01 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL

Rheumatoi	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009 56+	0.01 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004 56+	0 UOSL
SLE	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
SLE	2008 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
SLE	2008 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2008 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 30-39	0 UOSL

SLE	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
SLE	2009 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 30-39	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
SLE	2011 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
SLE	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL

SLE	2015 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2019 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 56+	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2008 56+	0.01 UOSL
SLE	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
SLE	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
SLE	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 20-29	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
SLE	2009 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2008 0-11	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
SLE	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2007 56+	0 UOSL
SLE	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
SLE	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
SLE	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
SLE	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
SLE	2006 56+	0 UOSL
SLE	2005 56+	0 UOSL
SLE	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 30-39	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 30-39	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 30-39	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 30-39	0.01 UOSL

Spontaneo	2009 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 20-29	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 20-29	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 20-29	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 12-19	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 12-19	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 12-19	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 20-29	0.01 UOSL

Spontaneo	2021 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 20-29	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 30-39	0.01 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 40-49	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 30-39	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 20-29	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 40-49	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 12-19	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 40-49	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 40-49	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2015 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 50-55	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 50-55	0.001 UOSL

Spontaneo	2015 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2016 0-11	0.001 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2019 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2020 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2021 0-11	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 40-49	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2018 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 12-19	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 50-55	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2014 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2017 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 50-55	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 50-55	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2012 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2013 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 50-55	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2008 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2009 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2010 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2011 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2007 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 50-55	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2006 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2005 56+	0 UOSL
Spontaneo	2004 56+	0 UOSL
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2004 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Breast canc	2017 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2004 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2009 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2010 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2008 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2009 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2004 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2010 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2009 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2010 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2008 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2010 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2008 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2009 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2008 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Breast canc	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2013 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019 40-49	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2012 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2013 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019 12-19	0.05	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2012 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2008 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2009 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2009 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2008 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2012 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2013 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Depression	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2004 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2009 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011 12-19	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2008 40-49	0.08	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2004 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2004 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2012 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2013 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2012 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.06	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2012 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2012 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2013 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2006 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2007 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2012 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2004 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2005 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2005 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2009 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2009 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2006 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2007 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2013 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2008 30-39	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2006 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2007 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2004 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2005 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2006 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2005 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2008 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2013 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017 12-19	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2004 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2007 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2012 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2013 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2008 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2013 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.05	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017 30-39	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.11	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017 40-49	0.09	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017 20-29	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017 50-55	1	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005 30-39	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006 30-39	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.08	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.07	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.09	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2009 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2010 20-29	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2004 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2013 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.2	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.05 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012 40-49	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2010 30-39	0.04 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006 40-49	0.09 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007 40-49	0.13 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019 50-55	1 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2008 20-29	0.05 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2009 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2009 40-49	0.03 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2010 40-49	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.08 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2004 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2008 30-39	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007 20-29	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005 40-49	0.06 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2013 40-49	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2013 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2008 40-49	0.18 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2004 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2004 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2009 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2008 12-19	0.07 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.04 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2010 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 50-55	1 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016 50-55	1 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014 56+	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Major cong	2016 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2017 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2016 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2017 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2010 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2011 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2019 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2019 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2011 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2011 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2012 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2019 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2012 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2005 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2006 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2006 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2007 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2009 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2010 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2013 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2008 30-39	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2004 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2009 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2013 30-39	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2007 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2005 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2004 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2008 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2005 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2006 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2012 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2013 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2008 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2009 40-49	0.03 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2016 12-19	0.03 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2004 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2016 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Major cong	2017 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2017 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2017 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2019 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2006 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2007 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2012 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2013 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2005 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2007 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2011 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2012 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2012 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2013 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2013 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2009 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2009 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2012 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Migraine	2013 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2012 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2005 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2005 40-49	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2006 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014 12-19	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2004 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2005 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2005 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2004 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2006 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2007 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2010 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2006 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2007 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2008 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2004 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2008 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2007 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2013 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2008 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2006 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2007 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Multiple sc	2012 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019 40-49	0.03 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2013 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2006 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2007 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2013 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2005 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2006 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2012 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2007 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2009 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2010 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2008 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2011 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2010 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2006 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2007 40-49	0.03 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2009 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2012 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2013 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017 40-49	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2004 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2005 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2004 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2005 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2004 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Multiple sc	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2008 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2012 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2013 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2008 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2005 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2006 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2007 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2004 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2016 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2017 30-39	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2016 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2017 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2018 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2018 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2018 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2014 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2019 30-39	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2005 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2006 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2017 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2012 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2013 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2012 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2013 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2019 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2019 40-49	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2018 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2019 12-19	0.05	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2012 12-19	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2007 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Preeclamps:	2008 30-39	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2015 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2011 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2009 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2010 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2011 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2012 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2014 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2014 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2007 20-29	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2008 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2009 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2005 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2015 20-29	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2006 30-39	0.001 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2010 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2009 40-49	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2005 40-49	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2006 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2013 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2009 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2010 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2004 30-39	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2016 40-49	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2007 40-49	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2004 20-29	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2008 40-49	0.08 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2014 50-55	1 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2013 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2006 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2007 12-19	0.01 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2015 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2016 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2017 12-19	0.02 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2004 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2005 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2017 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2011 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2018 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2019 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2008 12-19	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2004 40-49	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2016 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2012 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps:	2005 50-55	0 CHUT_EFEMERIS

Preeclamp:	2006 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2007 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2011 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2014 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2015 56+	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2016 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2011 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2012 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2009 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2011 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2012 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2007 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2008 20-29	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2005 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2005 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2006 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2013 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2004 20-29	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2013 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2007 30-39	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2006 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2008 30-39	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2004 40-49	0.3	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2005 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2016 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017 20-29	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2012 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2013 40-49	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2004 30-39	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018 40-49	0.02	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2004 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2005 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2016 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS

SLE	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2006 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2007 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2012 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2013 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2008 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2008 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2006 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2007 12-19	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2011 30-39	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2010 40-49	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2011 40-49	0.11	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2011 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2010 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10

Epilepsy	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2010 20-29	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2010 30-39	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0.09	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0.12	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2010 40-49	0.07	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0.26	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2010 12-19	0.03	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2011 20-29	0.04	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2011 30-39	0.03	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2011 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2010 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2011 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2011 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2010 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2011 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10

Multiple sc	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2011 30-39	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2010 40-49	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2011 40-49	0.11	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2011 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamp:	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2009 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2010 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2010 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2011 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2011 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2009 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2009 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2010 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2010 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2011 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2011 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2009 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2014 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016 40-49	0.09	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2014 56+	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015 56+	0	CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15

Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.01 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.02 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.25 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.03 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.17 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014 20-29	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.01 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.06 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.34 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.09 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.03 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.14 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016 50-55	1 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014 56+	0 CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2014 20-29	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015 20-29	0.001 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015 30-39	0.001 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016 30-39	0.03 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016 40-49	0.16 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2014 30-39	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016 20-29	0.01 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2014 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2015 40-49	0.03 CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2014 20-29	0 CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2015 20-29	0.001 CHUT_POMME15

Migraine	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2014 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016 30-39	0.02	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016 40-49	0.09	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016 20-29	0.03	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016 12-19	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016 50-55	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014 56+	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015 56+	0	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2015 30-39	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016 30-39	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2014 20-29	0	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2015 20-29	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2014 30-39	0	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016 20-29	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2014 40-49	0	CHUT_POMME15

SLE	2015 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2014 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2015 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016 40-49	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016 12-19	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2015 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016 50-55	0 CHUT_POMME15
ADHD	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
ADHD	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Autism	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE

Autism	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Autism	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Autism	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Autism	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Depression	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Depression	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Depression	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Depression	2018 40-49	0.01 BPE
Depression	2019 40-49	0.01 BPE
Depression	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Depression	2018 56+	0.01 BPE
Depression	2018 50-55	0.01 BPE
Depression	2019 50-55	0.01 BPE
Depression	2020 50-55	0.01 BPE
Depression	2020 56+	0.01 BPE
Depression	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Depression	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Depression	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Depression	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Depression	2019 56+	0.01 BPE
Depression	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Depression	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Depression	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Depression	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Depression	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE

Depression	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2018 20-29	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2019 20-29	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2020 20-29	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2018 30-39	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2019 30-39	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2020 30-39	0.01 BPE
Elective ab	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2020 56+	0 BPE
Elective ab	2018 56+	0 BPE
Elective ab	2019 56+	0 BPE
Elective ab	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Elective ab	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Elective ab	2017 0-11	0 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.01 BPE
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.01 BPE

Gestationa	2020 30-39	0.01 BPE
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.01 BPE
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018 56+	0 BPE
Gestationa	2019 56+	0 BPE
Gestationa	2018 0-11	0 BPE
Gestationa	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Gestationa	2017 0-11	0 BPE
Gestationa	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Gestationa	2020 56+	0 BPE
Major cong	2018 0-11	0.01 BPE
Major cong	2019 0-11	0.01 BPE
Major cong	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2017 0-11	0.02 BPE
Major cong	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE

Microceph:	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 50-55	0 BPE
Microceph:	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2019 56+	0 BPE
Microceph:	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Microceph:	2020 50-55	0 BPE
Microceph:	2018 56+	0 BPE
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE

Multiple ge	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Multiple ge	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020 56+	0 BPE
Multiple ge	2018 56+	0 BPE
Multiple ge	2019 56+	0 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2017 0-11	0 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 12-19	0 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE

Neonatal d	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019 20-29	0 BPE
Neonatal d	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 0-11	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2017 0-11	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2020 56+	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2018 56+	0 BPE
Preeclamps	2019 56+	0 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 20-29	0.01 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2017 0-11	0.02 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE

Preterm bii	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Preterm bii	2020 56+	0 BPE
Preterm bii	2018 56+	0 BPE
Preterm bii	2019 56+	0 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 56+	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2017 0-11	0 BPE
SLE	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 56+	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 56+	0.001 BPE

SLE	2019 56+	0.001 BPE
SLE	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
SLE	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
SLE	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 40-49	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 12-19	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 50-55	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 50-55	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 56+	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 56+	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 56+	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2018 0-11	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2017 0-11	0 BPE
Spontaneo	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Still birth	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2018 30-39	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 30-39	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 30-39	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2018 20-29	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 20-29	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2020 20-29	0 BPE
Still birth	2018 12-19	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 12-19	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 12-19	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 0-11	0 BPE
Still birth	2018 40-49	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 40-49	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 40-49	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 0-11	0 BPE
Still birth	2018 50-55	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 50-55	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 50-55	0 BPE
Still birth	2020 56+	0 BPE

Still birth	2018 56+	0 BPE
Still birth	2019 56+	0 BPE
TOPFA	2017 0-11	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018 0-11	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2019 0-11	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2020 0-11	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018 30-39	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018 40-49	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2019 40-49	0 BPE
TOPFA	2020 40-49	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018 20-29	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2019 20-29	0 BPE
TOPFA	2019 30-39	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2020 30-39	0 BPE
TOPFA	2018 12-19	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2019 12-19	0 BPE
TOPFA	2020 12-19	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2020 20-29	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018 50-55	0 BPE
TOPFA	2019 50-55	0 BPE
TOPFA	2020 50-55	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2020 56+	0 BPE
TOPFA	2018 56+	0 BPE
TOPFA	2019 56+	0 BPE
anxiety	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO

anxiety	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 50-55	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 50-55	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 50-55	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 50-55	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 56+	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 56+	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 56+	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 56+	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 56+	0.02 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 56+	0.01 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO

anxiety	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
anxiety	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO

Arthritis rh	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 20-29	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.05 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0.16 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0.13 FISABIO

Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.14 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.13 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.04 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0.05 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0.04 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.03 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.02 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 50-55	0.02 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 50-55	0.02 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0.02 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.04 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.03 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 56+	0.02 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0.03 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 56+	0.14 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 56+	0.05 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.05 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 56+	3.03 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 20-29	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 56+	0.14 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 56+	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 56+	0.02 FISABIO

Breast canc	2012 56+	0.1 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO

Demyelinat	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021 12-19	0 FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016 56+	0 FISABIO

Demyelinal	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Demyelinal	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO

Elective ter	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Elective ter	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO

Epilepsy	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 56+	0.01 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO

Epilepsy	2017 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 12-19	0.02 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO

Fetal growt	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2018 56+	0 FISABIO

Fetal growt	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Fetal growt	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.02 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 30-39	0.02 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.02 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.02 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO

Gestationa	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Gestationa	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Gestationa	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 12-19	0.02 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 12-19	0.03 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 12-19	0.01 FISABIO

Low Birth V	2019 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018 56+	0 FISABIO

Low Birth V	2018 0-11	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 0-11	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017 0-11	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019 0-11	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 0-11	0.01 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2010 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO

Microceph:	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 20-29	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2010 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2020 56+	0 FISABIO

Microceph:	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Microceph:	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO

Migraine	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 56+	0.01 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Migraine	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Migraine	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO

Multifoetal	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO

Multifoetal	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 12-19	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Multifoetal	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Pain	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO

Pain	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Pain	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Pain	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Pain	2019 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2021 20-29	0 FISABIO
Pain	2021 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Pain	2017 56+	0.01 FISABIO
Pain	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 12-19	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Pain	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Pain	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2015 56+	0 FISABIO

Pain	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Pain	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2013 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2019 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps	2018 12-19	0.01 FISABIO

Preeclamps:	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2017 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2016 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2020 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2021 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2020 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Preeclamps:	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 12-19	0.02 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 12-19	0.03 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 20-29	0.01 FISABIO

Preterm de	2021 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 20-29	0.02 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO

Preterm de	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Preterm de	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO

Spontaneo	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 50-55	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014 56+	0 FISABIO

Spontaneo	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 30-39	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 30-39	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 30-39	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 30-39	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 40-49	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 20-29	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 40-49	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 40-49	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 12-19	0.01 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO

Stillbirth	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 56+	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 0-11	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018 50-55	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 40-49	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 40-49	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 40-49	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 30-39	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 30-39	0.001 FISABIO

Systemic lu	2013 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 30-39	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 40-49	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 20-29	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 20-29	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 20-29	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 20-29	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 20-29	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 20-29	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 30-39	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 50-55	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 50-55	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 50-55	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 50-55	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 50-55	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 0-11	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 0-11	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 0-11	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 12-19	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 12-19	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2010 0-11	0 FISABIO

Systemic lu	2014 0-11	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 0-11	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021 0-11	0.001 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 50-55	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013 56+	0 FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012 56+	0 FISABIO
ADHD	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP

ADHD	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP

ADHD	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP

Autism	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP

Autism	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP

Breast canc	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP

Breast canc	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021 0-11	0 SIDIAP

Breast canc	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 40-49	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 50-55	0.02 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 50-55	0.02 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 56+	0.02 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 56+	0.02 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP

Depression	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 12-19	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 50-55	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP

Depression	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014 56+	0.03 SIDIAP
Depression	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP

Elective ab	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP

Elective ab	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP

Epilepsy	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP

Epilepsy	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP

Fetal growt	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP

Fetal growt	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP

Fetal growt	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP

Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP

Gestationa	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 0-11	0.02 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP

Major cong	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP

Major cong	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014 56+	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP

Microceph:	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP

Microceph:	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP

Migraine	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP

Migraine	2015 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 20-29	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 30-39	0.01 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP

Migraine	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Migraine	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP

Multiple ge	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP

Multiple ge	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP

Multiple sc	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP

Multiple sc	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP

Neonatal d	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP

Neonatal d	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamp:	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamp:	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP

Preeclamps:	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP

Preeclamps:	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP

Preeclamps:	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps:	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP

Preterm bii	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP

Preterm bii	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP

Rheumatoi	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP

Rheumatoi	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP

SLE	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
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SLE	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP

SLE	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
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SLE	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
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SLE	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
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SLE	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
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SLE	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP

Spontaneo	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP

Spontaneo	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP

Spontaneo	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP

Still birth	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 12-19	0 SIDIAP

Still birth	2019 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 12-19	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013 0-11	0 SIDIAP

TOPFA	2013 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 12-19	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 0-11	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 12-19	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 40-49	0 SIDIAP

TOPFA	2013 40-49	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 50-55	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2006 0-11	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2020 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013 20-29	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 20-29	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021 30-39	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 30-39	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 40-49	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014 56+	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 50-55	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008 56+	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011 56+	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2013 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2010 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 0-11	0 IMER

ADHD	2007 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2006 0-11	0 IMER
ADHD	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2007 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2010 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2013 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2007 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2013 20-29	0 IMER
ADHD	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2007 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2010 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 40-49	0 IMER

ADHD	2013 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2009 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2010 30-39	0 IMER
ADHD	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2010 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2013 12-19	0 IMER
ADHD	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2007 40-49	0 IMER
ADHD	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2011 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2013 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2008 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2010 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
ADHD	2013 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2007 50-55	0 IMER
ADHD	2010 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2012 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2009 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2007 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2008 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2011 56+	0 IMER

Autism	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Autism	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Autism	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Autism	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Autism	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Autism	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2012 40-49	0 IMER

Autism	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Autism	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Autism	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Autism	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Autism	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Autism	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Autism	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Autism	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Autism	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2014 56+	0 IMER

Autism	2015 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2016 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Autism	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Autism	2013 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Autism	2010 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2012 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2009 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2007 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2008 56+	0 IMER
Autism	2011 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER

Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER

Breast canc	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0 IMER
Breast canc	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Breast canc	2013 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2015 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2016 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2021 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Breast canc	2010 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2012 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2007 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2008 56+	0 IMER
Breast canc	2011 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2014 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2014 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2015 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2016 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2017 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2018 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2019 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2021 40-49	0.01 IMER
Depression	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2014 50-55	0.02 IMER

Depression	2015 50-55	0.02 IMER
Depression	2015 56+	0.02 IMER
Depression	2016 56+	0.02 IMER
Depression	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Depression	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Depression	2019 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2021 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2016 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2017 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2017 56+	0.01 IMER
Depression	2018 56+	0.01 IMER
Depression	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Depression	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2021 12-19	0.01 IMER
Depression	2018 50-55	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020 56+	0.01 IMER
Depression	2021 56+	0.01 IMER
Depression	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Depression	2021 20-29	0.01 IMER
Depression	2019 56+	0.01 IMER
Depression	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2011 20-29	0 IMER

Depression	2015 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2016 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2017 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2018 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2019 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2021 30-39	0.01 IMER
Depression	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Depression	2014 20-29	0.01 IMER
Depression	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Depression	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Depression	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Depression	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Depression	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2019 20-29	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Depression	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Depression	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2014 56+	0.03 IMER
Depression	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Depression	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Depression	2013 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2010 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2012 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2009 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2007 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2008 56+	0 IMER
Depression	2011 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER

Elective ab	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2007 0-11	0 IMER

Elective ab	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2021 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2017 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2018 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2019 0-11	0 IMER
Elective ab	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2017 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2009 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2007 56+	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008 56+	0 IMER

Elective ab	2011 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER

Epilepsy	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2021 56+	0.001 IMER

Epilepsy	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2010 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2007 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008 56+	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 20-29	0 IMER

Fetal growt	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 50-55	0 IMER

Fetal growt	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Fetal growt	2020 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2021 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2019 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2016 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2014 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2015 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2017 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2018 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2013 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2010 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2012 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2009 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2007 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2008 56+	0 IMER
Fetal growt	2011 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Gestationa	2013 20-29	0 IMER

Gestationa	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Gestationa	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Gestationa	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Gestationa	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER

Gestationa	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2019 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2020 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2016 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2017 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Gestationa	2013 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Gestationa	2015 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Gestationa	2010 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2012 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2009 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2007 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2008 56+	0 IMER
Gestationa	2011 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2015 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER

Major cong	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2021 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2016 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2017 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2018 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2019 0-11	0.02 IMER
Major cong	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER

Major cong	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Major cong	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Major cong	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2014 56+	0.01 IMER
Major cong	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Major cong	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Major cong	2013 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2010 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2012 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2009 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2007 56+	0 IMER

Major cong	2008 56+	0 IMER
Major cong	2011 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Microceph:	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2020 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 12-19	0 IMER

Microceph:	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2021 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Microceph:	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Microceph:	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Microceph:	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Microceph:	2015 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2016 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2021 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2014 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2016 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 50-55	0 IMER

Microceph:	2014 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2015 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2017 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2018 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2019 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2020 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2013 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Microceph:	2010 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2012 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2009 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2007 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2008 56+	0 IMER
Microceph:	2011 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Migraine	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Migraine	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Migraine	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Migraine	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Migraine	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Migraine	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Migraine	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Migraine	2014 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2015 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2016 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2017 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2018 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2019 30-39	0.01 IMER
Migraine	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2007 0-11	0 IMER

Migraine	2013	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2014	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2015	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2016	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2017	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2018	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2019	12-19	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2021	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2007	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2008	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2009	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2010	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2011	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2012	12-19	0	IMER
Migraine	2012	20-29	0	IMER
Migraine	2013	20-29	0	IMER
Migraine	2014	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2015	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2016	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2017	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2018	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2019	20-29	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2020	20-29	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2010	20-29	0	IMER
Migraine	2011	20-29	0	IMER
Migraine	2020	30-39	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2021	30-39	0.01	IMER
Migraine	2012	40-49	0	IMER
Migraine	2013	40-49	0	IMER
Migraine	2014	40-49	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2014	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2015	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2016	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2017	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2018	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2019	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2020	50-55	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2020	56+	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2021	56+	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2007	30-39	0	IMER
Migraine	2008	30-39	0	IMER
Migraine	2016	40-49	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2017	40-49	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2018	40-49	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2015	40-49	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2011	40-49	0	IMER
Migraine	2021	50-55	0.001	IMER

Migraine	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Migraine	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Migraine	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Migraine	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Migraine	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Migraine	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Migraine	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Migraine	2013 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2010 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2012 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2009 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2007 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2008 56+	0 IMER
Migraine	2011 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER

Multiple ge	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER

Multiple ge	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2021 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple ge	2019 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2020 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2016 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2014 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2015 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2017 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2018 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2013 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2010 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2012 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2009 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2007 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2008 56+	0 IMER
Multiple ge	2011 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER

Multiple sc	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER

Multiple sc	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Multiple sc	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2013 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2010 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2012 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2009 56+	0 IMER

Multiple sc	2007 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2008 56+	0 IMER
Multiple sc	2011 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 56+	0.001 IMER

Neonatal d	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 12-19	0 IMER

Neonatal d	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2013 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2010 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2012 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2009 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2007 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2008 56+	0 IMER
Neonatal d	2011 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Preeclamps	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER

Preeclamps:	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2016 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2020 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2021 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER

Preeclamps:	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2019 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2016 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2017 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Preeclamps:	2015 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2013 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2010 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2012 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2009 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2007 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2008 56+	0 IMER
Preeclamps:	2011 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 20-29	0 IMER

Preterm bii	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER

Preterm bii	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Preterm bii	2020 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2021 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2019 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2016 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2014 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2015 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2017 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2018 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2013 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2010 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2012 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2009 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2007 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2008 56+	0 IMER
Preterm bii	2011 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 30-39	0 IMER

Rheumatoi	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 30-39	0 IMER

Rheumatoi	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Rheumatoi	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2013 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2010 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2012 56+	0 IMER

Rheumatoi	2009 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2007 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2008 56+	0 IMER
Rheumatoi	2011 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2012 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2013 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2008 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2009 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2009 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2010 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2011 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2010 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2011 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2012 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2013 30-39	0 IMER
SLE	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
SLE	2008 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2009 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2010 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2010 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2011 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2012 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2013 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER

SLE	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2008 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2009 20-29	0 IMER
SLE	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2008 40-49	0 IMER
SLE	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2010 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2011 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2012 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2013 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2008 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2009 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2010 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2011 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2012 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2012 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2013 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
SLE	2011 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2013 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER

SLE	2008 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2009 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 12-19	0 IMER
SLE	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
SLE	2007 50-55	0 IMER
SLE	2013 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2006 0-11	0 IMER
SLE	2010 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2012 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2009 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2007 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2008 56+	0 IMER
SLE	2011 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER

Spontaneo	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 56+	0 IMER

Spontaneo	2021 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2018 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2019 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2020 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2021 0-11	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
Spontaneo	2015 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2016 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2017 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2013 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2010 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2012 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2009 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2007 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2008 56+	0 IMER
Spontaneo	2011 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2011 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2020 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2007 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 30-39	0 IMER
Still birth	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER

Still birth	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2009 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2011 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 20-29	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2011 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2011 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2020 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2017 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2018 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2019 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
Still birth	2018 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2019 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2020 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2016 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 40-49	0 IMER

Still birth	2008 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 40-49	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2011 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2015 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2016 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2016 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2011 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2018 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2019 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2020 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 12-19	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2014 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2015 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2017 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2021 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2017 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2018 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2015 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2019 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2020 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2006 0-11	0 IMER
Still birth	2013 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 50-55	0 IMER
Still birth	2010 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2012 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2009 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2007 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2008 56+	0 IMER
Still birth	2011 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2007 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2010 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 30-39	0 IMER

TOPFA	2013 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2020 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2007 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2010 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2013 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2013 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2020 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 12-19	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2009 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2019 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2007 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2010 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2013 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2014 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 0-11	0.001 IMER

TOPFA	2020 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 0-11	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2007 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2010 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 12-19	0 IMER
TOPFA	2015 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2020 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2010 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2013 40-49	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2020 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 50-55	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2010 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2020 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2006 0-11	0 IMER
TOPFA	2020 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2011 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2012 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2013 20-29	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 20-29	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021 30-39	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2007 30-39	0 IMER
TOPFA	2017 40-49	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2008 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014 56+	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2013 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2007 50-55	0 IMER
TOPFA	2010 56+	0 IMER

TOPFA	2012 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2009 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2007 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2008 56+	0 IMER
TOPFA	2011 56+	0 IMER
ADHD	2007 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2008 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2008 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2009 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2007 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2008 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2008 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2009 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2015 56+	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2009 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2007 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2008 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2009 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2010 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 30-39	0.001 ARS

ADHD	2012 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2006 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2014 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2009 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 56+	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2007 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2008 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2009 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2019 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2007 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013 20-29	0.001 ARS

ADHD	2011 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1995 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	1996 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	1997 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	1997 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	1998 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	1999 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2000 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2001 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2002 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2003 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2004 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	2005 30-39	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2006 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	1998 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	1999 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2000 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2001 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2002 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2003 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2004 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2005 20-29	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2006 20-29	0 ARS
ADHD	2006 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2002 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2003 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2004 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2005 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1995 0-11	0 ARS
ADHD	1996 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1997 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1998 0-11	0 ARS
ADHD	1999 0-11	0 ARS
ADHD	2000 0-11	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2001 0-11	0 ARS
ADHD	2002 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	2003 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2004 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2005 12-19	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2000 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	2001 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	2005 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2006 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	1996 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	1997 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	1998 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	1999 12-19	0 ARS

ADHD	1995 12-19	0 ARS
ADHD	1995 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	1996 30-39	0 ARS
ADHD	1996 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	1997 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	1998 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	1999 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2000 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2001 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2002 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2003 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2004 40-49	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2006 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2007 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2012 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2013 56+	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	1995 40-49	0 ARS
ADHD	2005 50-55	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2003 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2004 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2009 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2010 56+	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2001 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2002 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2007 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2008 56+	0 ARS
ADHD	2000 50-55	0 ARS
ADHD	2006 56+	0 ARS
Autism	1996 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	1997 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	1998 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	1999 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2000 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2000 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2001 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2002 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2003 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2004 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2005 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2006 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2007 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2008 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2009 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2010 20-29	0.001 ARS
Autism	2009 30-39	0 ARS

Autism	2010 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2011 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2012 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2013 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2014 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2015 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2016 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2017 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2018 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2019 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2019 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2020 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	1997 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	1998 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	1999 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2000 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2001 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2001 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2002 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2003 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2004 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2005 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2006 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2007 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2008 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2009 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2011 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2012 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2013 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2014 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2015 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2016 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2017 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2018 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2019 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2020 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	1995 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	1995 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	1996 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	1997 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	1998 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	1999 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2005 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2006 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2007 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2008 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2015 40-49	0 ARS

Autism	2016 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2017 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2018 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	1995 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	1996 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	1997 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	1998 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	1999 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2000 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2001 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2002 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2003 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2004 30-39	0 ARS
Autism	2004 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2005 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2006 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2007 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2008 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2009 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2010 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2011 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2012 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2013 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2014 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2014 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2015 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2016 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2017 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2018 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2019 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2020 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2020 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2002 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2003 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2012 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2013 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2018 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2019 56+	0 ARS
Autism	1998 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	1999 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2000 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2001 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2008 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2009 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2010 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2011 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2014 56+	0 ARS

Autism	2015 56+	0 ARS
Autism	1995 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	1996 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	1997 40-49	0 ARS
Autism	2000 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2001 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2002 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2003 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2004 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2005 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2006 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2006 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2007 56+	0 ARS
Autism	1995 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	1996 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2007 50-55	0 ARS
Autism	2010 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2011 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2016 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2017 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2009 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2012 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2013 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2008 56+	0 ARS
Autism	2010 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2020 20-29	0 ARS
Autism	2002 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2011 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2003 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2004 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2012 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2013 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2005 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2006 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2014 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2018 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2019 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2020 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2013 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2014 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2015 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2015 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2016 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2017 12-19	0 ARS
Autism	2007 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2008 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2009 0-11	0 ARS

Autism	2010 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2011 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2012 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2016 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2020 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2017 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2018 0-11	0 ARS
Autism	2019 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2011 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2011 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2015 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2010 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2010 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2011 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2015 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2015 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016 30-39	0.001 ARS

Breast canc	2010 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2010 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2011 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2015 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2010 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2011 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2009 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2010 12-19	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2011 12-19	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2013 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2015 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009 56+	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2015 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2016 12-19	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2008 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2009 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2010 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2011 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2012 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2013 0-11	0 ARS

Breast canc	2014 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2015 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2016 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2017 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2018 12-19	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019 12-19	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2006 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2017 0-11	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2019 0-11	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2004 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2005 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2006 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1995 30-39	0 ARS
Breast canc	1996 30-39	0 ARS
Breast canc	1997 30-39	0 ARS
Breast canc	1998 30-39	0 ARS
Breast canc	1999 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2000 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2001 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2002 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2003 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2004 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1996 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1997 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1998 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1999 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2000 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2001 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2002 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2003 40-49	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2006 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1995 40-49	0 ARS
Breast canc	2002 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2003 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2004 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2005 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2005 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2006 30-39	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1995 20-29	0 ARS
Breast canc	1996 20-29	0 ARS
Breast canc	1997 20-29	0 ARS
Breast canc	1995 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	1998 20-29	0 ARS
Breast canc	1999 20-29	0 ARS

Breast canc	2000 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2001 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2002 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2003 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2004 20-29	0 ARS
Breast canc	2005 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1996 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2006 20-29	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1997 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	1998 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	1999 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2000 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2001 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2002 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2003 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2004 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2005 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2006 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	2007 12-19	0 ARS
Breast canc	1995 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	1996 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	1997 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	1998 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	1999 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2000 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2001 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2002 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2003 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2004 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2005 0-11	0 ARS
Breast canc	2000 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2001 50-55	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2006 56+	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2017 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 0-11	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 0-11	0 ARS

Fetal growt	2011 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2017 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 30-39	0 ARS
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Fetal growt	2011 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 30-39	0 ARS
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Fetal growt	2017 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1999 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 20-29	0 ARS

Fetal growt	2013 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2017 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998 20-29	0 ARS
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Fetal growt	2001 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 20-29	0 ARS
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Fetal growt	2006 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2017 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1999 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 30-39	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014 40-49	0 ARS

Fetal growt	2014 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2017 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2018 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2019 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1999 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1999 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997 40-49	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2002 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2003 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2004 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996 0-11	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007 50-55	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2016 56+	0 ARS

Fetal growt	2017 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008 56+	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020 20-29	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013 12-19	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015 0-11	0 ARS

event_defii	year	IR	DEAP
ADHD	2011	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2012	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2013	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2014	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2015	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2016	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2017	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2018	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2019	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2020	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2021	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2009	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2010	0.001	UOSL
ADHD	2005	0	UOSL
ADHD	2006	0	UOSL
ADHD	2007	0	UOSL
ADHD	2008	0.01	UOSL
ADHD	2004	0	UOSL
Autism	2010	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2011	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2012	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2013	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2014	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2015	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2016	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2017	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2018	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2019	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2020	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2021	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2009	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2005	0	UOSL
Autism	2006	0	UOSL
Autism	2007	0	UOSL
Autism	2008	0.001	UOSL
Autism	2004	0	UOSL
Breast canc	2005	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2006	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2007	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2008	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2009	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2010	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2011	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2012	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2013	0.001	UOSL
Breast canc	2014	0.001	UOSL

Breast canc	2015	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2016	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2017	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2018	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2019	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2020	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2021	0.001 UOSL
Breast canc	2004	0 UOSL
Depression	2005	0 UOSL
Depression	2006	0 UOSL
Depression	2007	0 UOSL
Depression	2008	0.02 UOSL
Depression	2009	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2010	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2011	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2012	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2013	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2014	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2015	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2016	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2017	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2018	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2019	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2020	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2021	0.01 UOSL
Depression	2004	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2005	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2006	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2007	0 UOSL
Elective ab	2008	0.02 UOSL
Elective ab	2009	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2010	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2011	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2012	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2013	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2014	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2015	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2016	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2017	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2018	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2019	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2020	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2021	0.01 UOSL
Elective ab	2004	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2005	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2006	0 UOSL
Epilepsy	2007	0 UOSL

Epilepsy	2008	0.01 UOSL
Epilepsy	2009	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2010	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2011	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2012	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2013	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2014	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2015	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2016	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2017	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2018	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2019	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2020	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2021	0.001 UOSL
Epilepsy	2004	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2005	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2006	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2007	0 UOSL
Gestationa	2008	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2009	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2010	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2011	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2012	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2013	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2014	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2015	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2016	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2017	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2018	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2019	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2020	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2021	0.001 UOSL
Gestationa	2004	0 UOSL
Major cong	2010	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2011	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2012	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2013	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2014	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2015	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2016	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2017	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2018	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2019	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2020	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2021	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2005	0 UOSL
Major cong	2006	0 UOSL

Major cong	2007	0 UOSL
Major cong	2008	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2009	0.001 UOSL
Major cong	2004	0 UOSL
Migraine	2011	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2012	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2013	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2014	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2015	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2016	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2017	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2018	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2019	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2020	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2021	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2005	0 UOSL
Migraine	2006	0 UOSL
Migraine	2007	0 UOSL
Migraine	2008	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2009	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2010	0.001 UOSL
Migraine	2004	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2005	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2006	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2007	0 UOSL
Multiple ge	2008	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2009	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2010	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2011	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2012	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2013	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2014	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2015	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2016	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2017	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2018	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2019	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2020	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2021	0.001 UOSL
Multiple ge	2004	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2005	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2006	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2007	0 UOSL
Multiple sc	2008	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2009	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2010	0.001 UOSL
Multiple sc	2011	0.001 UOSL

Multiple sc	2012	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2013	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2014	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2015	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2016	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2017	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2018	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2019	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2020	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2021	0.001	UOSL
Multiple sc	2004	0	UOSL
Neonatal d	2010	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2011	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2005	0	UOSL
Neonatal d	2006	0	UOSL
Neonatal d	2007	0	UOSL
Neonatal d	2008	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2009	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2012	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2013	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2014	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2015	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2016	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2017	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2018	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2019	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2020	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2021	0.001	UOSL
Neonatal d	2004	0	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2005	0	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2006	0	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2007	0	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2008	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2009	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2010	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2011	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2012	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2013	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2014	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2015	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2016	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2017	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2018	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2019	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2020	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2021	0.001	UOSL
Preeclamps:	2004	0	UOSL

Preterm bii	2005	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2006	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2007	0 UOSL
Preterm bii	2008	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2009	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2010	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2011	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2012	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2013	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2014	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2015	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2016	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2017	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2018	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2019	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2020	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2021	0.001 UOSL
Preterm bii	2004	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2005	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2006	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2007	0 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2008	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2009	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2010	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2011	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2012	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2013	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2014	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2015	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2016	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2017	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2020	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2021	0.001 UOSL
Rheumatoi	2004	0 UOSL
SLE	2005	0 UOSL
SLE	2006	0 UOSL
SLE	2007	0 UOSL
SLE	2008	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2009	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2010	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2011	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2012	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2013	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2014	0.001 UOSL
SLE	2015	0.001 UOSL

SLE	2016	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2017	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2018	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2019	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2020	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2021	0.001	UOSL
SLE	2004	0	UOSL
Spontaneo	2005	0	UOSL
Spontaneo	2006	0	UOSL
Spontaneo	2007	0	UOSL
Spontaneo	2008	0.01	UOSL
Spontaneo	2009	0.01	UOSL
Spontaneo	2010	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2011	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2012	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2013	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2014	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2015	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2016	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2017	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2018	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2019	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2020	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2021	0.001	UOSL
Spontaneo	2004	0	UOSL
Breast canc	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2018	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2011	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2015	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2005	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2014	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2017	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2009	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2010	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2006	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2007	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Breast canc	2008	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Depression	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2008	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Epilepsy	2008	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2013	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2014	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2016	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2017	0.04	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2005	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2006	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2018	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2019	0.08	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2012	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2009	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2010	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2007	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2011	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2015	0.03	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Gestationa	2008	0.06	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Major cong	2019	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2013	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2008	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Major cong	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2008	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2006	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Migraine	2007	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2005	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2009	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2008	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Multiple sc	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2016	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2017	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamp:	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS

Preeclamps	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2019	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2012	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2008	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Preeclamps	2004	0	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2016	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2017	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2018	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2019	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2011	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2012	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2009	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2010	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2015	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2007	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2008	0.01	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2005	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2014	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2006	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2013	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
SLE	2004	0.001	CHUT_EFEMERIS
Depression	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2011	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2010	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Epilepsy	2011	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2010	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Gestationa	2011	0.11	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2011	0.03	CHUT_POMME10
Major cong	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2011	0	CHUT_POMME10
Migraine	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2011	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Multiple sc	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamps	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10

Preeclamps	2011	0.02	CHUT_POMME10
Preeclamps	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2009	0	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2010	0.001	CHUT_POMME10
SLE	2011	0.01	CHUT_POMME10
Depression	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Depression	2016	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Epilepsy	2016	0.02	CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2015	0.02	CHUT_POMME15
Gestationa	2016	0.14	CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Major cong	2016	0.03	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Migraine	2016	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2016	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
Multiple sc	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2016	0.02	CHUT_POMME15
Preeclamps	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2015	0.001	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2016	0.01	CHUT_POMME15
SLE	2014	0	CHUT_POMME15
ADHD	2018	0.001	BPE
ADHD	2019	0.001	BPE
ADHD	2020	0.001	BPE
ADHD	2017	0.001	BPE
Autism	2017	0.001	BPE
Autism	2018	0.001	BPE
Autism	2019	0.001	BPE
Autism	2020	0.001	BPE
Breast canc	2018	0.001	BPE
Breast canc	2019	0.001	BPE
Breast canc	2020	0.001	BPE
Breast canc	2017	0.001	BPE
Depression	2018	0.001	BPE
Depression	2019	0.001	BPE
Depression	2020	0.001	BPE
Depression	2017	0.001	BPE
Elective ab	2018	0.001	BPE
Elective ab	2019	0.001	BPE

Elective ab	2020	0.001 BPE
Elective ab	2017	0 BPE
Epilepsy	2018	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2019	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2020	0.001 BPE
Epilepsy	2017	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2018	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2019	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2020	0.001 BPE
Gestationa	2017	0 BPE
Major cong	2018	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2019	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2020	0.001 BPE
Major cong	2017	0.02 BPE
Microceph	2019	0.001 BPE
Microceph	2020	0.001 BPE
Microceph	2017	0.001 BPE
Microceph	2018	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2018	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2019	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2020	0.001 BPE
Migraine	2017	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2018	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2019	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2020	0.001 BPE
Multiple ge	2017	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2018	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2019	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2020	0.001 BPE
Multiple sc	2017	0 BPE
Neonatal d	2018	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2019	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2020	0.001 BPE
Neonatal d	2017	0.001 BPE
Preeclamp	2018	0.001 BPE
Preeclamp	2019	0.001 BPE
Preeclamp	2020	0.001 BPE
Preeclamp	2017	0 BPE
Preterm bi	2018	0.001 BPE
Preterm bi	2019	0.001 BPE
Preterm bi	2020	0.001 BPE
Preterm bi	2017	0.02 BPE
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2020	0.001 BPE
Rheumatoi	2017	0 BPE
SLE	2018	0.001 BPE

SLE	2019	0.001 BPE
SLE	2020	0.001 BPE
SLE	2017	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2018	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2019	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2020	0.001 BPE
Spontaneo	2017	0 BPE
Still birth	2018	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2017	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2019	0.001 BPE
Still birth	2020	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2017	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2018	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2019	0.001 BPE
TOPFA	2020	0.001 BPE
anxiety	2011	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2012	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2013	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2014	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2015	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2016	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2017	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2018	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2019	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2020	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2021	0.001 FISABIO
anxiety	2010	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2011	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2012	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2013	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2014	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2015	0 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2016	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2017	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2018	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2019	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2020	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2021	0.001 FISABIO
Arthritis rh	2010	0 FISABIO
Breast canc	2011	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2012	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2013	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2014	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2015	0.001 FISABIO
Breast canc	2016	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2017	0.01 FISABIO
Breast canc	2018	0.001 FISABIO

Breast canc	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Breast canc	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Breast canc	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Breast canc	2010	0	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2011	0	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2014	0	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Demyelinat	2010	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2011	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2012	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2013	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2014	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2015	0	FISABIO
Elective ter	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Elective ter	2010	0	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Epilepsy	2010	0	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2016	0.01	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2017	0.01	FISABIO

Fetal growt	2018	0.01	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2019	0.01	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Fetal growt	2010	0	FISABIO
Gestationa	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2016	0.01	FISABIO
Gestationa	2017	0.01	FISABIO
Gestationa	2018	0.01	FISABIO
Gestationa	2019	0.01	FISABIO
Gestationa	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Gestationa	2010	0	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2016	0.01	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2017	0.01	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2018	0.01	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2019	0.01	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2020	0.01	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Low Birth V	2010	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2015	0	FISABIO
Microceph:	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Microceph:	2010	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2011	0	FISABIO
Migraine	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2016	0.001	FISABIO

Migraine	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Migraine	2010	0	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Multifoetal	2010	0	FISABIO
Pain	2011	0	FISABIO
Pain	2012	0	FISABIO
Pain	2013	0	FISABIO
Pain	2014	0	FISABIO
Pain	2015	0	FISABIO
Pain	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Pain	2010	0	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Preeclamps	2010	0	FISABIO
Preterm de	2011	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2015	0.001	FISABIO

Preterm de	2016	0.01	FISABIO
Preterm de	2017	0.01	FISABIO
Preterm de	2018	0.01	FISABIO
Preterm de	2019	0.01	FISABIO
Preterm de	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Preterm de	2010	0	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2011	0	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2012	0	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2013	0	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2014	0	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Spontaneo	2010	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2011	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2012	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2013	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2014	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2015	0	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Stillbirth	2010	0	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2011	0	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2012	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2013	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2014	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2015	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2016	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2017	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2018	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2019	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2020	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2021	0.001	FISABIO
Systemic lu	2010	0	FISABIO
ADHD	2013	0	SIDIAP
ADHD	2014	0.001	SIDIAP
ADHD	2015	0.001	SIDIAP
ADHD	2016	0.001	SIDIAP

ADHD	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
ADHD	2010	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2011	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2012	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2007	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2008	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2009	0 SIDIAP
ADHD	2006	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2010	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2011	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2012	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2013	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Autism	2006	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2007	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2008	0 SIDIAP
Autism	2009	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2010	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2011	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2012	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2013	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2007	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2008	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2009	0 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Breast canc	2006	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2009	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2010	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2011	0 SIDIAP

Depression	2012	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2013	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2014	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2015	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2016	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2017	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2018	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2019	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Depression	2021	0.01 SIDIAP
Depression	2007	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2008	0 SIDIAP
Depression	2006	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2007	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2008	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2009	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2010	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2011	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2012	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2013	0 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Elective ab	2006	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2007	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2008	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2009	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2010	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2011	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2012	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2013	0 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Epilepsy	2006	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2007	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2008	0 SIDIAP

Fetal growt	2009	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2010	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2011	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2012	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2013	0 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Fetal growt	2006	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2007	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2008	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2009	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2010	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2011	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2012	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2013	0 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Gestationa	2006	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2007	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2008	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2009	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2010	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2011	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2012	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2013	0 SIDIAP
Major cong	2014	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2015	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2016	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2017	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2018	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2019	0.01 SIDIAP
Major cong	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Major cong	2006	0 SIDIAP
Microceph:	2020	0.001 SIDIAP

Microceph:	2021	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2016	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2017	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2018	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2019	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2014	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2015	0.001	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2013	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2007	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2008	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2009	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2010	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2011	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2012	0	SIDIAP
Microceph:	2006	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2007	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2008	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2009	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2010	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2011	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2012	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2013	0	SIDIAP
Migraine	2014	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2015	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2016	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2017	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2018	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2019	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2020	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2021	0.001	SIDIAP
Migraine	2006	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2007	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2008	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2009	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2010	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2011	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2012	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2013	0	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2014	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2015	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2016	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2017	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2018	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2019	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2020	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2021	0.001	SIDIAP
Multiple ge	2006	0	SIDIAP

Multiple sc	2007	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2008	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2009	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2010	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2011	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2012	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2013	0 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Multiple sc	2006	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2007	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2008	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2009	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2010	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2011	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2012	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2013	0 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Neonatal d	2006	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2007	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2008	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2009	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2010	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2011	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2012	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2013	0 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Preeclamps	2021	0.001 SIDIAP

Preeclamps	2006	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2007	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2008	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2009	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2010	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2011	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2012	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2013	0 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Preterm bii	2006	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2007	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2008	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2009	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2010	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2011	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2012	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2013	0 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Rheumatoi	2006	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2012	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2013	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
SLE	2007	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2008	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2009	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2010	0 SIDIAP

SLE	2011	0 SIDIAP
SLE	2006	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2007	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2008	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2009	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2010	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2011	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2012	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2013	0 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Spontaneo	2006	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2007	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2008	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2009	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2010	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2011	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2012	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2013	0 SIDIAP
Still birth	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2019	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2020	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2021	0.001 SIDIAP
Still birth	2006	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2007	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2008	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2009	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2010	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2011	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2012	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2013	0 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2014	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2015	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2016	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2017	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2018	0.001 SIDIAP
TOPFA	2019	0.001 SIDIAP

TOPFA	2020	0.001	SIDIAP
TOPFA	2021	0.001	SIDIAP
TOPFA	2006	0	SIDIAP
ADHD	2013	0	IMER
ADHD	2014	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2015	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2016	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2017	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2018	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2019	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2020	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2021	0.001	IMER
ADHD	2010	0	IMER
ADHD	2011	0	IMER
ADHD	2012	0	IMER
ADHD	2007	0	IMER
ADHD	2008	0	IMER
ADHD	2009	0	IMER
ADHD	2006	0	IMER
Autism	2010	0	IMER
Autism	2011	0	IMER
Autism	2012	0	IMER
Autism	2013	0	IMER
Autism	2014	0.001	IMER
Autism	2015	0.001	IMER
Autism	2016	0.001	IMER
Autism	2017	0.001	IMER
Autism	2018	0.001	IMER
Autism	2019	0.001	IMER
Autism	2020	0.001	IMER
Autism	2021	0.001	IMER
Autism	2006	0	IMER
Autism	2007	0	IMER
Autism	2008	0	IMER
Autism	2009	0	IMER
Breast canc	2010	0	IMER
Breast canc	2011	0	IMER
Breast canc	2012	0	IMER
Breast canc	2013	0	IMER
Breast canc	2014	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2015	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2016	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2017	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2018	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2019	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2020	0.001	IMER
Breast canc	2007	0	IMER

Breast canc	2008	0 IMER
Breast canc	2009	0 IMER
Breast canc	2021	0.001 IMER
Breast canc	2006	0 IMER
Depression	2009	0 IMER
Depression	2010	0 IMER
Depression	2011	0 IMER
Depression	2012	0 IMER
Depression	2013	0 IMER
Depression	2014	0.01 IMER
Depression	2015	0.01 IMER
Depression	2016	0.01 IMER
Depression	2017	0.01 IMER
Depression	2018	0.01 IMER
Depression	2019	0.01 IMER
Depression	2020	0.001 IMER
Depression	2021	0.01 IMER
Depression	2007	0 IMER
Depression	2008	0 IMER
Depression	2006	0 IMER
Elective ab	2007	0 IMER
Elective ab	2008	0 IMER
Elective ab	2009	0 IMER
Elective ab	2010	0 IMER
Elective ab	2011	0 IMER
Elective ab	2012	0 IMER
Elective ab	2013	0 IMER
Elective ab	2014	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2015	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2016	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2017	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2018	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2019	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2020	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2021	0.001 IMER
Elective ab	2006	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2007	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2008	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2009	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2010	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2011	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2012	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2013	0 IMER
Epilepsy	2014	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2015	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2016	0.001 IMER
Epilepsy	2017	0.001 IMER

Epilepsy	2018	0.001	IMER
Epilepsy	2019	0.001	IMER
Epilepsy	2020	0.001	IMER
Epilepsy	2021	0.001	IMER
Epilepsy	2006	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2007	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2008	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2009	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2010	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2011	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2012	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2013	0	IMER
Fetal growt	2014	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2015	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2016	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2017	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2018	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2019	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2020	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2021	0.001	IMER
Fetal growt	2006	0	IMER
Gestationa	2007	0	IMER
Gestationa	2008	0	IMER
Gestationa	2009	0	IMER
Gestationa	2010	0	IMER
Gestationa	2011	0	IMER
Gestationa	2012	0	IMER
Gestationa	2013	0	IMER
Gestationa	2014	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2015	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2016	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2017	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2018	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2019	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2020	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2021	0.001	IMER
Gestationa	2006	0	IMER
Major cong	2007	0	IMER
Major cong	2008	0	IMER
Major cong	2009	0	IMER
Major cong	2010	0	IMER
Major cong	2011	0	IMER
Major cong	2012	0	IMER
Major cong	2013	0	IMER
Major cong	2014	0.01	IMER
Major cong	2015	0.01	IMER
Major cong	2016	0.01	IMER

Major cong	2017	0.01	IMER
Major cong	2018	0.01	IMER
Major cong	2019	0.01	IMER
Major cong	2020	0.001	IMER
Major cong	2021	0.001	IMER
Major cong	2006	0	IMER
Microceph:	2020	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2021	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2016	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2017	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2018	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2019	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2014	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2015	0.001	IMER
Microceph:	2013	0	IMER
Microceph:	2007	0	IMER
Microceph:	2008	0	IMER
Microceph:	2009	0	IMER
Microceph:	2010	0	IMER
Microceph:	2011	0	IMER
Microceph:	2012	0	IMER
Microceph:	2006	0	IMER
Migraine	2007	0	IMER
Migraine	2008	0	IMER
Migraine	2009	0	IMER
Migraine	2010	0	IMER
Migraine	2011	0	IMER
Migraine	2012	0	IMER
Migraine	2013	0	IMER
Migraine	2014	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2015	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2016	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2017	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2018	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2019	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2020	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2021	0.001	IMER
Migraine	2006	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2007	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2008	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2009	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2010	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2011	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2012	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2013	0	IMER
Multiple ge	2014	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2015	0.001	IMER

Multiple ge	2016	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2017	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2018	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2019	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2020	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2021	0.001	IMER
Multiple ge	2006	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2007	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2008	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2009	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2010	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2011	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2012	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2013	0	IMER
Multiple sc	2014	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2015	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2016	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2017	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2018	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2019	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2020	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2021	0.001	IMER
Multiple sc	2006	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2007	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2008	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2009	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2010	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2011	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2012	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2013	0	IMER
Neonatal d	2014	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2015	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2016	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2017	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2018	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2019	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2020	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2021	0.001	IMER
Neonatal d	2006	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2007	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2008	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2009	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2010	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2011	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2012	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2013	0	IMER
Preeclamp:	2014	0.001	IMER

Preeclamps	2015	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2016	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2017	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2018	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2019	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2020	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2021	0.001	IMER
Preeclamps	2006	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2007	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2008	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2009	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2010	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2011	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2012	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2013	0	IMER
Preterm bii	2014	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2015	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2016	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2017	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2018	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2019	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2020	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2021	0.001	IMER
Preterm bii	2006	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2015	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2016	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2017	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2020	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2021	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2007	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2008	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2009	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2010	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2011	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2012	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2013	0	IMER
Rheumatoi	2014	0.001	IMER
Rheumatoi	2006	0	IMER
SLE	2012	0	IMER
SLE	2013	0	IMER
SLE	2014	0.001	IMER
SLE	2015	0.001	IMER
SLE	2016	0.001	IMER
SLE	2017	0.001	IMER
SLE	2018	0.001	IMER

SLE	2019	0.001	IMER
SLE	2020	0.001	IMER
SLE	2021	0.001	IMER
SLE	2007	0	IMER
SLE	2008	0	IMER
SLE	2009	0	IMER
SLE	2010	0	IMER
SLE	2011	0	IMER
SLE	2006	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2007	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2008	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2009	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2010	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2011	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2012	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2013	0	IMER
Spontaneo	2014	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2015	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2016	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2017	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2018	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2019	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2020	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2021	0.001	IMER
Spontaneo	2006	0	IMER
Still birth	2007	0	IMER
Still birth	2008	0	IMER
Still birth	2009	0	IMER
Still birth	2010	0	IMER
Still birth	2011	0	IMER
Still birth	2012	0	IMER
Still birth	2013	0	IMER
Still birth	2014	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2015	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2016	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2017	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2018	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2019	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2020	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2021	0.001	IMER
Still birth	2006	0	IMER
TOPFA	2007	0	IMER
TOPFA	2008	0	IMER
TOPFA	2009	0	IMER
TOPFA	2010	0	IMER
TOPFA	2011	0	IMER
TOPFA	2012	0	IMER

TOPFA	2013	0 IMER
TOPFA	2014	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2015	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2016	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2017	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2018	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2019	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2020	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2021	0.001 IMER
TOPFA	2006	0 IMER
ADHD	2007	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2008	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2009	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2010	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2011	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2012	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2013	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2014	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2015	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2016	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2017	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2018	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2019	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2020	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2006	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1995	0 ARS
ADHD	1996	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1997	0.001 ARS
ADHD	1998	0 ARS
ADHD	1999	0 ARS
ADHD	2000	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2001	0 ARS
ADHD	2002	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2003	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2004	0.001 ARS
ADHD	2005	0.001 ARS
Autism	1996	0 ARS
Autism	1997	0 ARS
Autism	1998	0 ARS
Autism	1999	0 ARS
Autism	2000	0 ARS
Autism	2001	0 ARS
Autism	2002	0 ARS
Autism	2003	0 ARS
Autism	2004	0 ARS
Autism	2005	0 ARS
Autism	2006	0 ARS

Autism	2007	0 ARS
Autism	2008	0 ARS
Autism	2009	0 ARS
Autism	2010	0.001 ARS
Autism	2011	0 ARS
Autism	2012	0 ARS
Autism	2013	0 ARS
Autism	2014	0 ARS
Autism	2015	0 ARS
Autism	2016	0 ARS
Autism	2017	0 ARS
Autism	2018	0 ARS
Autism	2019	0 ARS
Autism	2020	0 ARS
Autism	1995	0 ARS
Breast canc	2011	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2012	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2013	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2014	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2015	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2016	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2017	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2018	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2019	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2020	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2007	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2008	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2009	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2010	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2006	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2004	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2005	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1995	0 ARS
Breast canc	1996	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1997	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1998	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	1999	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2000	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2001	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2002	0.001 ARS
Breast canc	2003	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2004	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2016	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2017	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2018	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2019	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2020	0.001 ARS

Fetal growt	2002	0.001 ARS
Fetal growt	2003	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2005	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2006	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2007	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2008	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2009	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2010	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2011	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2012	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2013	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2014	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2015	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1997	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1998	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1999	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2000	0 ARS
Fetal growt	2001	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1995	0 ARS
Fetal growt	1996	0 ARS
ADHD	2010	0.001 THL
ADHD	2011	0.001 THL
ADHD	2012	0.001 THL
ADHD	2013	0.001 THL
ADHD	2014	0.001 THL
ADHD	2015	0.001 THL
ADHD	2016	0.001 THL
ADHD	2017	0.001 THL
ADHD	2018	0.001 THL
ADHD	2019	0.001 THL
ADHD	1996	0 THL
ADHD	1997	0.001 THL
ADHD	1998	0.001 THL
ADHD	1999	0.001 THL
ADHD	2000	0.001 THL
ADHD	2001	0.001 THL
ADHD	2002	0.001 THL
ADHD	2003	0.001 THL
ADHD	2004	0.001 THL
ADHD	2005	0.001 THL
ADHD	2006	0.001 THL
ADHD	2007	0.001 THL
ADHD	2008	0.001 THL
ADHD	2009	0.001 THL
Autism	1997	0 THL
Autism	1998	0.001 THL
Autism	1999	0.001 THL

Autism	2000	0.001 THL
Autism	2001	0.001 THL
Autism	2002	0.001 THL
Autism	2003	0.001 THL
Autism	2004	0.001 THL
Autism	2005	0.001 THL
Autism	2006	0.001 THL
Autism	2007	0.001 THL
Autism	2008	0.001 THL
Autism	2009	0.001 THL
Autism	2010	0.001 THL
Autism	2011	0.001 THL
Autism	2012	0.001 THL
Autism	2013	0.001 THL
Autism	2014	0.001 THL
Autism	2015	0.001 THL
Autism	2016	0.001 THL
Autism	2017	0.001 THL
Autism	2018	0.001 THL
Autism	2019	0.001 THL
Autism	1996	0 THL
Breast canc	1996	0.001 THL
Breast canc	1997	0.001 THL
Breast canc	1998	0.001 THL
Breast canc	1999	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2000	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2001	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2002	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2003	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2004	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2005	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2006	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2007	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2008	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2009	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2010	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2011	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2012	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2013	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2014	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2015	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2016	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2017	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2018	0.001 THL
Breast canc	2019	0.001 THL
Depression	1997	0.001 THL
Depression	1998	0.001 THL

Depression	1999	0.001 THL
Depression	2000	0.001 THL
Depression	2001	0.001 THL
Depression	2002	0.001 THL
Depression	2003	0.001 THL
Depression	2004	0.001 THL
Depression	2005	0.001 THL
Depression	2006	0.001 THL
Depression	2007	0.001 THL
Depression	2008	0.001 THL
Depression	2009	0.001 THL
Depression	2010	0.001 THL
Depression	2011	0.01 THL
Depression	2012	0.01 THL
Depression	2013	0.01 THL
Depression	2014	0.01 THL
Depression	2015	0.01 THL
Depression	2016	0.01 THL
Depression	2017	0.01 THL
Depression	2018	0.01 THL
Depression	2019	0.01 THL
Depression	1996	0.001 THL
Elective ab	1996	0.001 THL
Elective ab	1997	0.02 THL
Elective ab	1998	0.02 THL
Elective ab	1999	0.02 THL
Elective ab	2000	0.02 THL
Elective ab	2001	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2002	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2003	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2004	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2005	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2006	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2007	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2008	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2009	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2010	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2011	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2012	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2013	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2014	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2015	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2016	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2017	0.01 THL
Elective ab	2018	0.001 THL
Elective ab	2019	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	1996	0.001 THL

Epilepsy	1997	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	1998	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	1999	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2000	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2001	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2002	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2003	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2004	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2005	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2006	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2007	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2008	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2009	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2010	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2011	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2012	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2013	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2014	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2015	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2016	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2017	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2018	0.001 THL
Epilepsy	2019	0.001 THL
Gestationa	1996	0.001 THL
Gestationa	1997	0.001 THL
Gestationa	1998	0.001 THL
Gestationa	1999	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2000	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2001	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2002	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2003	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2004	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2005	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2006	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2007	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2008	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2009	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2010	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2011	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2012	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2013	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2014	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2015	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2016	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2017	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2018	0.001 THL
Gestationa	2019	0.001 THL

Major cong	2009	0.01 THL
Major cong	2010	0.01 THL
Major cong	2011	0.01 THL
Major cong	2012	0.01 THL
Major cong	2013	0.01 THL
Major cong	2014	0.01 THL
Major cong	2015	0.01 THL
Major cong	2016	0.01 THL
Major cong	2017	0.01 THL
Major cong	2018	0.001 THL
Major cong	2019	0.001 THL
Major cong	1996	0.06 THL
Major cong	1997	0.001 THL
Major cong	1998	0.01 THL
Major cong	1999	0.01 THL
Major cong	2000	0.01 THL
Major cong	2001	0.01 THL
Major cong	2002	0.01 THL
Major cong	2003	0.01 THL
Major cong	2004	0.01 THL
Major cong	2005	0.01 THL
Major cong	2006	0.01 THL
Major cong	2007	0.01 THL
Major cong	2008	0.01 THL
Microceph:	2010	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2011	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2012	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2013	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2014	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2015	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2016	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2017	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2018	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2019	0.001 THL
Microceph:	1999	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2000	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2001	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2002	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2003	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2004	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2005	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2006	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2007	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2008	0.001 THL
Microceph:	2009	0.001 THL
Microceph:	1997	0.001 THL
Microceph:	1998	0.001 THL

Microceph:	1996	0.001 THL
Migraine	1996	0 THL
Migraine	1997	0.001 THL
Migraine	1998	0.001 THL
Migraine	1999	0.001 THL
Migraine	2000	0.001 THL
Migraine	2001	0.001 THL
Migraine	2002	0.001 THL
Migraine	2003	0.001 THL
Migraine	2004	0.001 THL
Migraine	2005	0.001 THL
Migraine	2006	0.001 THL
Migraine	2007	0.001 THL
Migraine	2008	0.001 THL
Migraine	2009	0.001 THL
Migraine	2010	0.001 THL
Migraine	2011	0.001 THL
Migraine	2012	0.001 THL
Migraine	2013	0.01 THL
Migraine	2014	0.01 THL
Migraine	2015	0.001 THL
Migraine	2016	0.001 THL
Migraine	2017	0.01 THL
Migraine	2018	0.01 THL
Migraine	2019	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	1996	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	1997	0.001 THL
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Multiple ge	2014	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	2015	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	2016	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	2017	0.001 THL

Multiple ge	2018	0.001 THL
Multiple ge	2019	0.001 THL
Multiple sc	1996	0.001 THL
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Multiple sc	2012	0.001 THL
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Multiple sc	2015	0.001 THL
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Multiple sc	2017	0.001 THL
Multiple sc	2018	0.001 THL
Multiple sc	2019	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2010	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2011	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2012	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2013	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2014	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2015	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2016	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2017	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2018	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2019	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	1996	0 THL
Neonatal d	1997	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	1998	0.001 THL
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Neonatal d	2002	0 THL
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Neonatal d	2005	0.001 THL
Neonatal d	2006	0.001 THL

Neonatal d	2007	0.001	THL
Neonatal d	2008	0.001	THL
Neonatal d	2009	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	1996	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	1997	0.001	THL
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Preeclamps	2011	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	2012	0.001	THL
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Preeclamps	2016	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	2017	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	2018	0.001	THL
Preeclamps	2019	0.001	THL
Preterm bir	1996	0.06	THL
Preterm bir	1997	0.001	THL
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Preterm bir	2011	0.001	THL
Preterm bir	2012	0.001	THL
Preterm bir	2013	0.001	THL
Preterm bir	2014	0.001	THL
Preterm bir	2015	0.001	THL

Preterm bi	2016	0.001 THL
Preterm bi	2017	0.001 THL
Preterm bi	2018	0.001 THL
Preterm bi	2019	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	1996	0 THL
Rheumatoi	1997	0.001 THL
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Rheumatoi	2012	0.001 THL
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Rheumatoi	2014	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	2015	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	2016	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	2017	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001 THL
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001 THL
SLE	1996	0 THL
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SLE	2011	0.001 THL
SLE	2012	0.001 THL
SLE	2013	0.001 THL
SLE	2014	0.001 THL

SLE	2015	0.001 THL
SLE	2016	0.001 THL
SLE	2017	0.001 THL
SLE	2018	0.001 THL
SLE	2019	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	1996	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	1997	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	1998	0.01 THL
Spontaneo	1999	0.01 THL
Spontaneo	2000	0.01 THL
Spontaneo	2001	0.01 THL
Spontaneo	2002	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2003	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2004	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2005	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2006	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2007	0.001 THL
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Spontaneo	2010	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2011	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2012	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2013	0.001 THL
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Spontaneo	2015	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2016	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2017	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2018	0.001 THL
Spontaneo	2019	0.001 THL
Still birth	1996	0.001 THL
Still birth	1997	0.001 THL
Still birth	1998	0.001 THL
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Still birth	2000	0.001 THL
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Still birth	2010	0.001 THL
Still birth	2011	0.001 THL
Still birth	2012	0.001 THL
Still birth	2013	0.001 THL

Still birth	2014	0.001 THL
Still birth	2015	0.001 THL
Still birth	2016	0.001 THL
Still birth	2017	0.001 THL
Still birth	2018	0.001 THL
Still birth	2019	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2010	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2011	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2012	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2013	0.001 THL
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TOPFA	2016	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2017	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2018	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2019	0.001 THL
TOPFA	1996	0.001 THL
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TOPFA	2007	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2008	0.001 THL
TOPFA	2009	0.001 THL
ADHD	2010	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2011	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2012	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2013	0.001 USWAN
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ADHD	2015	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2016	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2017	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2018	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2019	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	1996	0 USWAN
ADHD	1997	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	1998	0.001 USWAN
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ADHD	2000	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2001	0.001 USWAN
ADHD	2002	0.001 USWAN

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ADHD	2005	0.001	USWAN
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ADHD	2008	0.001	USWAN
ADHD	2009	0.001	USWAN
Autism	1997	0	USWAN
Autism	1998	0.001	USWAN
Autism	1999	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2000	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2001	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2002	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2003	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2004	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2005	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2006	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2007	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2008	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2009	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2010	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2011	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2012	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2013	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2014	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2015	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2016	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2017	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2018	0.001	USWAN
Autism	2019	0.001	USWAN
Autism	1996	0	USWAN
Breast canc	1996	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	1997	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	1998	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	1999	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2000	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2001	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2002	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2003	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2004	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2005	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2006	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2007	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2008	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2009	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2010	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2011	0.001	USWAN

Breast canc	2012	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2013	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2014	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2015	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2016	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2017	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2018	0.001	USWAN
Breast canc	2019	0.001	USWAN
Depression	1997	0.001	USWAN
Depression	1998	0.001	USWAN
Depression	1999	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2000	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2001	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2002	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2003	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2004	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2005	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2006	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2007	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2008	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2009	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2010	0.001	USWAN
Depression	2011	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2012	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2013	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2014	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2015	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2016	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2017	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2018	0.01	USWAN
Depression	2019	0.01	USWAN
Depression	1996	0.001	USWAN
Elective ab	1996	0.001	USWAN
Elective ab	1997	0.02	USWAN
Elective ab	1998	0.02	USWAN
Elective ab	1999	0.02	USWAN
Elective ab	2000	0.02	USWAN
Elective ab	2001	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2002	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2003	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2004	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2005	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2006	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2007	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2008	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2009	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2010	0.01	USWAN

Elective ab	2011	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2012	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2013	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2014	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2015	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2016	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2017	0.01	USWAN
Elective ab	2018	0.001	USWAN
Elective ab	2019	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	1996	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	1997	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	1998	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	1999	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2000	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2001	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2002	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2003	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2004	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2005	0.001	USWAN
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Epilepsy	2008	0.001	USWAN
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Epilepsy	2012	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2013	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2014	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2015	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2016	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2017	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2018	0.001	USWAN
Epilepsy	2019	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	1996	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	1997	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	1998	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	1999	0.001	USWAN
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Gestationa	2001	0.001	USWAN
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Gestationa	2003	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2004	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2005	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2006	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2007	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2008	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2009	0.001	USWAN

Gestationa	2010	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2011	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2012	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2013	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2014	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2015	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2016	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2017	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2018	0.001	USWAN
Gestationa	2019	0.001	USWAN
Major cong	2009	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2010	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2011	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2012	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2013	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2014	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2015	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2016	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2017	0.01	USWAN
Major cong	2018	0.001	USWAN
Major cong	2019	0.001	USWAN
Major cong	1996	0.06	USWAN
Major cong	1997	0.001	USWAN
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Major cong	1999	0.01	USWAN
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Major cong	2004	0.01	USWAN
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Major cong	2008	0.01	USWAN
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Microceph:	1996	0.001	USWAN
Migraine	1996	0	USWAN
Migraine	1997	0.001	USWAN
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Multiple sc	2019	0.001	USWAN
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Neonatal d	2017	0.001	USWAN
Neonatal d	2018	0.001	USWAN
Neonatal d	2019	0.001	USWAN
Neonatal d	1996	0	USWAN

Neonatal d	1997	0.001	USWAN
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Preeclamps	1996	0.001	USWAN
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Preeclamps	2005	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2006	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2007	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2008	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2009	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2010	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2011	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2012	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2013	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2014	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2015	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2016	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2017	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2018	0.001	USWAN
Preeclamps	2019	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	1996	0.06	USWAN
Preterm bii	1997	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	1998	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	1999	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2000	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2001	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2002	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2003	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2004	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2005	0.001	USWAN

Preterm bii	2006	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2007	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2008	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2009	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2010	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2011	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2012	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2013	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2014	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2015	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2016	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2017	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2018	0.001	USWAN
Preterm bii	2019	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	1996	0	USWAN
Rheumatoi	1997	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	1998	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	1999	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2000	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2001	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2002	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2003	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2004	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2005	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2006	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2007	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2008	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2009	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2010	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2011	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2012	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2013	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2014	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2015	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2016	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2017	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2018	0.001	USWAN
Rheumatoi	2019	0.001	USWAN
SLE	1996	0	USWAN
SLE	1997	0.001	USWAN
SLE	1998	0.001	USWAN
SLE	1999	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2000	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2001	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2002	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2003	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2004	0.001	USWAN

SLE	2005	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2006	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2007	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2008	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2009	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2010	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2011	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2012	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2013	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2014	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2015	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2016	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2017	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2018	0.001	USWAN
SLE	2019	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	1996	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	1997	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	1998	0.01	USWAN
Spontaneo	1999	0.01	USWAN
Spontaneo	2000	0.01	USWAN
Spontaneo	2001	0.01	USWAN
Spontaneo	2002	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2003	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2004	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2005	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2006	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2007	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2008	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2009	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2010	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2011	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2012	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2013	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2014	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2015	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2016	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2017	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2018	0.001	USWAN
Spontaneo	2019	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	1996	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	1997	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	1998	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	1999	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2000	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2001	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2002	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2003	0.001	USWAN

Still birth	2004	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2005	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2006	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2007	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2008	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2009	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2010	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2011	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2012	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2013	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2014	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2015	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2016	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2017	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2018	0.001	USWAN
Still birth	2019	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2010	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2011	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2012	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2013	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2014	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2015	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2016	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2017	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2018	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2019	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	1996	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	1997	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	1998	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	1999	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2000	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2001	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2002	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2003	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2004	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2005	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2006	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2007	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2008	0.001	USWAN
TOPFA	2009	0.001	USWAN